

Competition Policy and Energy Supply Security in the European Union

A Critical Evaluation

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Abstract

Competition Policy and Energy Supply Security have become closely linked policy fields in the European Union. Since the energy crisis of the 1970s, energy security has been a high-priority topic for European policy makers. Impressed by the economic crisis that followed the 1973 OPEC energy embargo, governments of the OECD member countries have developed institutions and joint approaches to limit the risk of energy supply disruptions to their economies and national security. While the IEA system deals primarily with the management of energy supply crises, competition policy is meant to address the long-term stability of the energy system in the EU. However, both the IEA system and competition policies are based on questionable assumptions and as a result are likely to contribute little to energy supply security in the EU, and may even undermine it in the long run.

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2. Introduction

Since the energy crisis of the 1970s, energy security has been a high-priority topic for European policy makers. Impressed by the economic crisis that followed the 1973 OAPEC energy embargo, governments of the OECD member countries have developed institutions and joint approaches to limit the risk of energy supply disruptions to their economies and national security. Some of these are designed to mitigate the immediate effects of an energy crisis, while other are designed to prevent their occurrence.

In cooperation with other OECD member states, the European governments created the International Energy Agency to mitigate the impact of short-term supply disruptions and thereby reduce the ability of foreign governments to use energy as a 'political weapon'. Internally, Europe embarked on a difficult process of reducing the long-term risks to energy supplies by diversifying the number of countries from which it imports energy and the types of fuels used throughout the economy. Most importantly, the European Commission began to push for a politically difficult process of breaking up the numerous national and regional monopolies in the energy sector that were believed to be at the root of energy insecurity in Europe.

But after almost three decades of continuous efforts to deal with the problem of energy security, few policy goals set by European governments three decades ago have been met: Europe continues to depend on imported energy more than ever, a significant share of oil and gas continues to be imported from countries whose governments are considered unfriendly towards the European Union, short-term disruptions to energy supplies continue to strongly impact energy prices for consumers and industry alike, investment into energy infrastructure remains insufficient, energy markets continue to be regional, and overall energy prices are among the highest in the OECD.

In this paper I will explore the question of why the European Union has been unsuccessful in its efforts to significantly improve energy security for its member states. I will attempt to prove two main arguments: the first is that current energy security policies in the European Union are based on an erroneous interpretation of the energy crisis of the 1970s. The second is that the economic policies of the European Union towards the energy sector are predicated on a fundamentally erroneous understanding of the role of monopoly in the economy.

I will argue that the economic crisis of the 1970s was not the result of the 1973 energy crisis, but that both have been the consequence of long-term economic mismanagement by Western governments. The energy crisis has to be understood as an integral part of the ongoing macro-economic crisis that had been building up since the late 1960s throughout the non-Communist zone. Rather than causing the supply crisis, the OAPEC merely took advantage of a situation that had been largely out of its control and over which it had far less influence than it seemed. Unfortunately, the sequence of events created the false impression that the energy crisis had been responsible for the subsequent economic downturn, and that the embargo had caused the energy crisis. As a result, policy makers in Europe approached energy security as primarily a political rather than economic challenge.

My second argument is that even when the European Union addresses the economic factor impacting energy security, its policies are unlikely to achieve the goal of creating energy security for Europe. Correctly identifying statutory monopolies as a barrier to the development of an integrated and flexible energy market capable of providing long-term energy security and protection against short-term shocks, European policy makers are working towards the creation of a competitive market for energy in Europe. But policy makers fail to recognise that the emergence of transitory monopolies is inevitable in a market economy, and may even be desirable. By trying to eliminate all

monopolies from the economy entirely, even those that are the result of purely competitive actions rather than government action, the European Union is limiting the ability of energy companies to invest into necessary, but risky, energy infrastructures – particularly in the natural gas sector. As a result, energy supply security in the natural gas sector is currently not guaranteed.

In the third chapter of this essay, I will provide a description of how energy supply security is currently understood by most governments, including those in the European Union. I will show that the political definition of energy supply security must be understood in the context of national security politics, and that the primary goal of energy supply security is the guarantee of state power and influence in the international arena of *Realpolitik* competition. I will also provide an overview of the 1970s energy crisis and how it has contributed to the current understanding of, and approach to, energy supply security in Europe. This will include a very brief description of the essential elements of the International Energy Agency emergency system as it relates to energy supply security in the European Union. The chapter will also include a detailed description of the conceptual framework of European economic policy as it relates to the energy sector and energy security in the European Union. Special emphasis will be given to current understanding of monopoly and its role in the economy.

The fourth chapter of this essay will provide a general overview of the current state of, and challenges to, energy supply security in the European Union. This will include a quantitative and qualitative description of the energy demand and supply structure situation in the European Union, as well as a description of some of the major challenges still remaining. Particularly emphasis will be given to the natural gas sector which is currently emerging as the critical weak spot of European Union energy supply security. The chapter will further discuss the current European policies dealing

with the structural problems of the natural gas sector, particularly the problem of natural monopoly resulting from the technological properties of the natural gas industry.

The fifth chapter will provide a detailed critical examination of key elements of the current energy supply security policy complex in the European Union. I will argue that for historical and political reasons, the role of energy in the economy is frequently misunderstood. Based on a detailed analysis of the political and economic factors contributing to the energy and economic crisis of the 1970s, I will show that the impact of energy prices on the macro-economy tends to be significantly overestimated. I will further show that the subsequently developed emergency measure systems of the International Energy Agency are inadequate to deal with a serious supply shock crisis, and may even have negative impacts. Most importantly, however, I will show that current competition policies in the European Union are at risk of undermining long-term energy security even though they are meant to enhance it.

I will conclude by arguing that to ensure energy supply security in the European Union it will be necessary to reconceptualise the issue as primarily economic, and to focus on the creation of conditions that allow market forces, rather than government policies, to develop the most efficient and effective solutions for long-term energy supply security.

3. The Politics and Economics of Energy Supply Security

The politics and economics of energy supply security are impossible to separate. If energy were economically unimportant, politicians would care little for it. But if energy were politically unimportant, economist would probably think little about it, either. For most of human history, neither economists nor politicians have given energy much thought. It was not until the internal combustion engine and commercially viable electricity became the literal engines of modern civilization that both politicians and economists began to regard energy as a topic meriting significant attention.

While energy supply security has been a key element of international politics and economics for almost a century now, it was not until the energy crisis of the 1970s that it has been addressed by European decision makers in a systematic fashion. In the following I will show how the energy crisis of the 1970 has determined how the problem of energy security is understood and addressed today. But energy supply security is not only a political problem – it is at its very root a question of economics. Politicians and regulators in the European Union have long recognised this connection and have tried to develop policies that would simultaneously address both the economic and political challenges of energy supply security. For this reason, the following chapter will also discuss how the problem of competition regulation is intimately connected to the question of energy supply security.

Headlines such as “US presidential politics to brighten spotlight on energy security issue”¹, “Forget energy independence. Here's a plan for energy security”², “What 'Energy Security' Really Means”³, “Our Path to Energy Security”⁴, and even “Energy Security 101”⁵ appear regularly in

¹ Oil & Gas Journal, January 7, 2008, GENERAL INTEREST; Special Report; Pg. 24

² Christian Science Monitor, November 30, 2007

³ The Washington Post, July 3, 2006 Monday,

newspapers and magazines, and energy security is discussed widely by politicians and analysts. While terrorism and war may dominate the headlines, energy security is always just below the surface: Afghanistan, Iraq, Chechnya, Iraq, even East Timor – there are few international conflicts that cannot be linked to the question of energy security for the Western world.

At the same time, academics have paid relatively little attention to energy security. In a survey of all academic articles in the International Political Science Abstracts database, a German research team found that between 1951 and 1985, out of 30,000 articles dealing with international relations, 855 dealt with energy policy in the most general sense⁶. Since then, little seems to have changed. A similar survey by subjects from 1986 – 2008 of the same database reveals that a total of 306 articles were listed with “energy” as a subject, and 53 with “energy security”, 21 dealt with the “European Union” or “EU” and “energy” - out of a total of 5635 that listed “European Union” or “EU” as a subject. By comparison, 558 articles were listed with the subject of “gender”, 326 with “immigration”, and 136 with “genocide”.

Furthermore, publication of articles dealing with energy “was not anti-cyclical, as one would like to expect from critical experts, but cyclically following the current relevance of the topic.”⁷ Or to put it more bluntly: if the topic didn’t make headlines, it was generally ignored, and as a result “the political sciences have primarily served as an echo chamber of international energy policy, rather than as an innovative guide. Problems are rarely anticipated but only reflected upon in response to

⁴ The Washington Post, October 18, 2007

⁵ The Washington Post, October 9, 2007

⁶ Fischer & Hackel, p. 7

⁷ Fischer & Hackel, p. 8

current events and interests.”⁸ And “as a rule, the relationship to the future remains fully caught up in the present, it is guided by, and changes with, the conventional wisdom of the day.”⁹

But even among energy researchers, energy security is given far less attention than a layperson might have expected. While as far back as 1985 many felt that “apart from the East-West military balance, access to energy represents the most important security issue for the Western industrial democracies,”¹⁰ the journal “Energy Policy” has published 66 articles dealing explicitly with energy security since its first issue in 1973, and out of those 45 were published since 2001 when the terror attacks in the USA, the wars in Afghanistan and Iraq, and the smouldering Russian-European energy conflict made the topic all but inevitable.

Surprisingly, perhaps, the concept of energy security itself is also not very clearly defined. At its most basic, security can mean “freedom from risk or danger; safety ... freedom from doubt, anxiety, or fear; confidence.”¹¹ In the first sense, security is a meaningless concept: a situation free from risk or danger is inconceivable. To define security as the absence of doubt, anxiety, or fear is probably more useful. These are states of mind, and states of mind do not necessarily have to correspond to objective reality. It is easier to create certainty and confidence than it is to remove objective risks and dangers.

Energy security is best understood within the context of national security. As long as the political world is defined by the existence of states, the concept of security is difficult to separate from concept of national (state) security. While there is a small academic fringe that tries to question the legitimacy of the statist perspective on security, the literature leaves little doubt that security is generally considered to be the responsibility of the state institutions. For better or worse, the

⁸ Fischer & Hackel, p. 9

⁹ Fischer & Hackel, p. 9

¹⁰ Adamson, D. M., “Soviet gas and European security”, 1985

¹¹ The American Heritage Dictionary of the English Language

provision of security is widely considered a public good that cannot be provided effectively by the voluntary interaction of individuals and the market¹².

Thinking about security needs to address the following questions: “What is being secured” and “what constitutes the conditions of security?”¹³ Since *national* security is premised on the assumption that “[t]here exist threats to the territory of one state posed by the activities of other states,”¹⁴ the object of security is the state. One American analyst phrased it as follows:

“In the most basic sense, what the American people have to deal with when they adjust to the world outside U.S. frontiers is 170 assorted nation-states, each in control of a certain amount of the earth's territory. These 170 nations, being sovereign, are able to reach decisions on the use of armed forces under their government's control. They can decide to attack other nations”¹⁵

Less easily answered is the question on what constitutes the conditions of security. How do we know that the state is secure, and more importantly: how do we know that it is (no longer) secure? Since the threat to any given states emanates from other states, the only way to fully secure a state would be to eliminate all other states. This is, of course, the well known tragic of the state-centric world system. The elimination of all other states may be desirable from the perspective of any given state, but will logically be resisted by all others. Therefore, the achievement of full security of the state is not possible. The criterion for security must therefore be, by necessity, more modest. It could, for example, be limited to the question of whether the state that is our object of analysis is

¹² My personal reservations on the veracity of this idea would go far beyond the scope of this paper.

¹³ Lipschutz, “On Security”, 1989

¹⁴ Lipschutz, p. ? in “On Security”

¹⁵ Frederick H. Hartmann and Robert L. Wendzel, *Defending America's Security* (Washington: Pergamon-Brassey's, 1988), pp. 3-4., quoted in Lipschutz “On Security”

able to survive despite the existence of other states. Or to put it into more practical terms: does the state in question have the means to secure its survival in an inherently hostile world of other states?

In the past, the concept of national security in this sense was almost always linked to the question of military capabilities. As territorially defined entities, the most immediate threat to a state was the involuntary loss of territory to another state¹⁶ - which generally required that one state would occupy another states territory with its army. The only way to prevent this from happening was for every state to have an army¹⁷. Until very recently, the threat of armed invasion was the most serious threat to the survival of states, but it was not the only one. Armies, at least standing armies, are expensive. Soldiers do not produce value – they can at best protect it, or acquire it by conquest – and states need material means for their provision and maintenance. Unless an army is used for conquest, in which case it can feed itself, states need to tax their populations. This in turn makes it necessary for states to concern themselves not only with the protection of their territory, but also with the generation of the means necessary to maintain armies. In short, states have to pay attention to the question of economics.

As a result, the concept of national security becomes broader, and involves not only the absence of threats to a state's territory, but also “the absence of an external political threat, force or pressure to political and economic institutions.”¹⁸ If these are not safeguarded, the state will not be able to provide for its defence against the armies of other states – should it come to the point that this is necessary. Since modern economies require natural resources of all kinds for their proper functioning, it is therefore logical to say that “national security [is] defined primarily in terms of

¹⁶ To this date, states to cede territory voluntarily, if they perceive it to be in their interest.

¹⁷ Or, in the case of England, at least a navy.

¹⁸ Hall, Darwin C., 1992, Oil and national security in “Energy Policy, November 1992”

military threats to state, society, and industry”¹⁹, and therefore encompasses “concerns about oil and other raw materials whose reliability of supply could never be assured with confidence through global market.”²⁰

Economic welfare, it has to be pointed out, is not an end to itself in the context of national security. Economic welfare matters only in so far that it enables the state as such to survive in a world populated by other states. States always have, and always will, adopt policies that do not necessarily further the material interest of their populations, but are primarily focussed on the continuing existence of themselves as sovereign states. Understanding national security policies, even when it comes to economics, requires to always keep in mind that “the interests of private agents and the nation are not identical,”²¹ and “states are much more concerned with achieving political and security objectives than wealth maximization.”²² Still, sensible and far sighted statesmanship should not ignore economic necessities. In the long run, “actions that would maximize wealth also closely match those that would maximize their political objectives – security and power... After all, more money, one is better able to assist one's friends and to defend oneself against enemies.”²³

But to the eternal frustration of economists, states do “not seek security through reliance on the markets [which] could be controlled by rivals”²⁴ – other states, or their subjects – whose interests are potentially hostile to other states. Rather, states seek security through control, whether direct or indirect. The economist, with his emphasis on the welfare of the individual, often fails to appreciate the essential difference between his outlook and that of the statesman. The overriding concern of

¹⁹ Crawford, Beverly “Hawks, Doves, but no Owls” in “On Security”

²⁰ Ibid.

²¹ Hubbard, R. G., 1985

²² Griffin and Steele, p. 96

²³ Griffin and Steele, p. 98

²⁴ Crawford,

political decision makers is with political, rather than economic, questions. In the short run, politics can override economic concerns, even if in the long run economics will inevitably assert themselves. States will therefore frequently adopt policies that are economically questionable, but politically expedient.

Energy security has only in recent history become a distinct issue of national security policies.²⁵ Until three hundred years, when the most common sources of energy worldwide were fire wood and wind, energy was available to most nations at an almost equal basis. Wood was the most common source of heat, wax and tallow candles provided light, and wind drove not only mills for grain and water, but also the merchant and military navies of the world, while horses and oxen powered overland transportation and agricultural work. Even human labour was more often than not a sufficient source of energy for most needs.

However, with the invention of the steam engine and the beginning of the industrial revolution, wood no longer sufficed to meet the rapidly rising energy demand of Europe. Coal quickly became the most important fuel, particularly in Britain and Western Europe. Coal powered steam ships replaced sailboats, and steam trains moved an increasing share of Europe's freight. Scientific developments also made it possible to use coal for a number of chemical processes and turn it into gas for lighting. Coal fired steam engines also allowed the large-scale generation of electricity, which would soon turn from a scientific curiosity and luxury for the wealthy into the most vital and ubiquitous form of energy for all.

But coal mining was concentrated in only a few regions throughout Europe. The most significant European coal mining regions were in the Donets, Silesia, Saar, Ruhr, Northern England, Scotland, and Wales. With the exception of the Donets and the British mining regions, each of these

²⁵ James R. Schlesinger, 2005

was located close to the borders of countries with traditionally hostile relationships. With the age of coal control over energy resources became an important element of international politics. During the Silesian War of 1740-1742, Prussia successfully set out to conquer the most significant coal mining region of the Austro-Hungarian Empire, which would prove to be an important element of Prussia's future rise to power. Control over coal mining would continue to determine much of Prussia's – and subsequently German – history, when the Saar and Ruhr became the prize for which it fought with France in three major wars between 1870 and 1941²⁶.

Even though energy had become a cause of war over the last two hundred years, it was not until the early 20th century that energy security in its modern sense became central to national security. The Silesian war, as well as the wars between France and Germany, was fought by the different states to integrate the *wealth* of the coal mining regions into their national economies. The concern was not necessarily whether individuals and businesses would have sufficient amounts of energy at reasonable prices – but whether the productive capacities of Silesia, the Ruhr, or the Saar would benefit the treasuries of Prussia, Austro-Hungary, or France.

The internal combustion engine allowed the development of much smaller motors than steam technology. While steam engines could only be used in locomotives, ships, and stationary steam generators, internal combustion engines could be used almost anywhere, even in personal vehicles and airplanes. Within a few decades, internal combustion engines became indispensable for the economic development of nations²⁷ as well as the military capability of their armies.

But internal combustion engines require oil and oil products as fuel. If coal was more unevenly distributed than wood, oil was even more unevenly distributed than coal. Few countries had

²⁶ Ironically, the history of this struggle became the moral rationale for concluding the European Coal and Steel Community, which constituted the first institutional basis for today's European Union

²⁷ It is not by accident that personal car ownership and the proportion of goods transported by trucks is a key indicator of national wealth.

significant oil reserves that could be exploited economically. The largest readily available reserves were located in the Middle East and North America, as well as the Southern Caucasus. At the beginning of the 20th century, British companies controlled most of the oil producing regions outside North America. Since oil powered ships have both greater speed and range than coal powered ones, the decision by Winston Churchill to switch the British navy from coal to oil gave Britain a significant strategic advantage: not only were oil powered ships faster than those fuelled by coal,²⁸ but Britain and her allies also controlled the key resource that gave its navy the edge and provided their armies with a sheer inexhaustible supply of fuel. The allies, the metaphor goes, swam to victory on a sea of oil in both World Wars.

Today, the conquest of energy resources is no longer a practical possibility. Despite their natural inclinations, most states have to find ways to acquire fuel by peaceful means – they have to buy it.²⁹ Rather than being able to exist as more or less independent entities, modern states have to deal with the reality that interconnectedness through commerce is a necessity for maintaining a modern economy that not only provides their populations with adequate goods and services, but also gives them access to those technologies and resources that are necessary for ensuring the security of the state as a state. The logic of the modern economy therefore forces states to rely willy-nilly on economics for their survival. National security has therefore become linked to economics more intimately than ever before. And since a modern economy includes energy, energy security becomes an object of modern national security.

As a result, “the challenge of energy security will grow more urgent in the years ahead because the scale of the global trade in energy will grow substantially as world markets become more

²⁸ Yergin, D. 'Ensuring Energy Security', *Foreign Affairs*, March April 2006

²⁹ If the U.S. did in fact go to war in Iraq to control the oil fields, the economic wisdom of that decision is questionable at best.

integrated.”³⁰ While “[i]n the seventies, it [energy security] was primarily linked to enhancing conservation and developing political strategies to secure guaranteed Western energy supplies in the Middle East”, this is no longer enough, and has instead “to include risks such as underinvestment in infrastructure, which can lead to massive power outages, and poorly designed markets, as well as disruption to energy supplies due to natural disasters, accidents, and international terrorism.”³¹

But the instinct of the state to seek control rather than rely on others for the basics of its survival is reflected in “the traditional inclination among politicians and the media in OECD countries is to regard energy supplies which are produced domestically as 'secure', and supplies which are imported as 'insecure'.”³² For the economist, there is no difference between buying bread from the baker next door and oil from the oilman across the sea. Relationships in the free market are governed by mutually compatible interests, specialisation on comparative advantages, and gains from trade. But for the statesman, the difference is fundamental. For the statesman, free exchange is potentially dangerous. He does not see trade as taking place between individuals, but always defines trade as taking place between states: the importation of fuel from elsewhere is therefore to rely on other states, which could be one’s (potential) enemies. After all, the resources are located in the territory of another state which could, if it so wished, interrupt the supply. Whether or not such interruptions make economic sense in the long run is irrelevant: the narrow time horizon of the politician rarely includes long-term economic considerations.

Today, energy security is about more than just enough supplies for armies and navies (though it still includes this as well). Energy is important because it contributes to national power indirectly, by promoting the economic power of states. Energy security is therefore “a condition when and all, or

³⁰ Yergin, D. 2006, “Ensuring Energy Security”, *Foreign Affairs*, March/April 2006

³¹ Legendre, Thierry, 2007, “The North Atlantic Treaty Organization's Future Role in Energy Security”

³² Stern, J. “The New Security Environment for European Gas: Worsening Geopolitics and Increasing Global Competition for LNG”, October 2006

most ... citizens and businesses have access to sufficient energy resources at reasonable prices for the foreseeable future free from risk of major disruptions of service.”³³ And according to the European Commission, energy security is “the uninterrupted physical availability of energy products on the market, at a price which is affordable for all consumers (private and industrial).”³⁴

But these definitions are not as satisfactory as they may appear to policy makers: what exactly is meant by 'most' – the vast majority around 80 – 90 percent, or just more than half? And neither is the meaning of 'sufficient' any clearer: does it mean just enough to keep the house warm and prevent freezing to death, enough energy to cook three warm meals a day and watch TV, or does there have to be enough energy for everything but the Christmas decoration? The time-frame 'foreseeable future' is also not an exact scientific unit: is the next weekend too far away, or does it include the next three or four months but not the next decade? The EU Commission's definition seems a bit more precise: at the very least it includes everybody, but it does not say what the threshold for affordable should be: no more than 10% or up to half of an individual's monthly income?

The fuzziness of the energy supply security concept is partially the result of its history. As long as it was seen as a military problem, its definition was comparatively simple: how to ensure that enough fuel will be available for a given number of trucks, tanks, planes, and ships to engage in a military conflict of a particular size for a particular duration. In war, economic efficiency is less important than military effectiveness. But decision making in war takes place in relatively short time frames. Decision making in peace, however, tends to be for the long term – and efficiency cannot be ignored without significant economic and political risk. Ironically, however, it is during peace time that the material conditions for the protection of the state are created.

³³ Barton et. al. p. 5

³⁴ European Commission 2001 Green Paper on Energy Supply Security

Policy makers are therefore torn between two fundamentally different approaches to energy security: one is short-term and focussed on effectiveness, the other long-term and focussed on efficiency. Reconciling the two is necessary, but difficult. But as we will see later on, much of current energy security thinking still seems to be influenced at least in parts by the memory of military planning, and policy makers are frequently tempted to adopt short-term solutions without regard for their long-term effects. As we will see below, the post-war era has provided a fertile environment for the continuing national securitization of energy security.

3.1. The Energy Crises: 1973 – 74 and 1978 – 80

In this section, I will provide a brief overview of the energy crisis of the 1970s and how it is generally believed to have impacted the economies of Western nations. The OPEC crisis of 1973-1974 and the Iranian Revolution crisis from late 1978 to 1980 generally believed to have dramatically impacted the economic fortunes of Europe and North America. The overriding goal of energy security policy in the European Union countries has since then been to limit the likelihood of such dramatic supply interruptions to happen again in the future.

The OPEC³⁵ crisis of 1973 has become the defining moment and central reference point of the post-war energy security debate in the European Union. It made the European public aware of the degree to which its current wealth and welfare depend on imports from other countries, and sometimes countries with which relations are tense in the best of times.

“The period from 1960 to the oil crisis of late 1973 was one of rapid economic growth and burgeoning oil demand. National wealth in OECD countries grew by 90% during the period, energy demand by a similar amount and oil demand by

³⁵ The first, and most common error, is to refer to the 1973 situation as the OPEC embargo, when it was only the Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries that imposed the embargo, while OPEC as such only raised the prices.

120%. Transport demand boomed and oil cut deep into coal's markets as a furnace fuel. In the world as a whole, oil demand rose from somewhat more than 20 million barrels per day (mb/d) to approach 60 mb/d, of which OECD demand accounted for two-thirds. Many OECD countries produced little primary energy or had static or declining production. They became heavily dependent on oil imports, mostly from OPEC countries, and especially from the Middle East.”³⁶

Between 1965 and 1973 alone, the EU 12 countries dependence on imported oil rose from 91.4 percent to 99.7 percent. The share of oil in total energy consumption rose from 42.1 percent to 54.7 percent during the same time, which meant that 54.5 percent of all European energy was imported – mostly from the Middle East.

“The oil price shock resulting from the 1973 crisis, reinforced by the Iran/Iraq crisis of the late 1970s, had profoundly damaging effects. It abruptly ended the period of rapid growth. OECD countries and the world were stricken by high inflation, trade and payments imbalances, high unemployment and weak business and consumer confidence.”³⁷

Christopher Dows wrote in 2000 that “the recession of 1973–5 was the first occasion since the war when total output fell absolutely. ... Each of these two recessions coincided with one of the vast jumps in the world price of oil ... I will argue that these played a large role in their genesis; and though in each case there were other causes also, the two recessions will be referred to here as the OPEC recessions.”³⁸

³⁶ IEA, 2000, p. 13

³⁷ BP Statistical Review of World Energy, 2007 (no data prior to 1965 included). Unless otherwise stated, all quantitative energy data, including energy prices, throughout this paper are taken from the BP database.

³⁸ Dows, Christopher “Major recessions”, p. 274

The economic mechanism that translates an energy price increase into diminished economic growth is a straight-forward application of fundamental micro-economic principles. Higher prices for any factor of input increase overall costs. The production of each unit of output becomes more expensive, as a result of which demand for the product will be reduced, resulting in reduced production. Since almost all goods require fuel as a factor of production at some stage, any increase in fuel prices is going to increase the costs of production of almost all products.

“It does not matter whether the cost of energy rises because it is imported and a cartel raises its monopoly price or because depletion of potential and proved reserves makes domestic energy sources more difficult to tap. Nor does it matter whether the price increase occurs slowly or rapidly. In each case the higher the cost of energy will mean a lower real national income – that is, a loss of real purchasing power.”³⁹

Much of the impact depends on so-called price elasticity – the degree to which consumption of a particular product, in this case oil, can be curtailed and/or replaced by a substitute. Judging by the energy consumption data for the EU 12, at least the short-term elasticity for oil seems to have been quite low. Even though prices for energy more than doubled within a year, consumption declined only marginally: while oil prices increased 3.17 times from 1973 to 1974, consumption dropped by only 0.72 percent. This is mostly because “energy usage is closely tied to the stock of energy using equipment, which cannot be redesigned and replaced over night.”⁴⁰ Consumers have to balance the benefit of replacing a gas inefficient car for a gas efficient one against the cost of a new car versus the market price of the old, while operators of electricity generating plants have to consider the costs of replacing their current equipment.

³⁹ Pindyck, Robert S. And Julio J. Rotenberg, “Energy Shocks and the Macroeconomy”, in “Oil Shock”, 1982, p. 98

⁴⁰ Griffin and Steele, p. 20 - 21

In the short run, however, energy consumption is relatively inelastic vis-a-vis energy prices, which means that an increase in energy prices would result at least temporarily in higher energy expenditure. This was indeed the case in Europe. In 1972, the EU12 total expenditure on oil (in 2000 \$)⁴¹ was \$49.26 billion. By the end of 1975, this had risen to \$168.75 billion, and at its peak in 1980, it had reached \$365.72 billion – 7.42 times more than 8 years before.

Figure 1 – EU15 Oil Expenditure 1965 – 1990⁴²

In the long run, price elasticity can be quite high: by the mid-1983, oil consumption in the EU declined by 24.9 percent relative to 1973, while oil prices were about four times higher than they had been in 1973. Even more importantly, the share of oil in the general energy balance had dropped from 54.7 percent in 1973 to 42.9 percent. Overall energy consumption, however, had declined by only 4.2 percent.

⁴¹ While I have tried to use 2006 currency equivalents consistently, I needed to use 2000 equivalent currency here, since the GDP data I am using was denominated in 2000 currency.

⁴² Data from BP, 2006 – calculations by author.

If we combine these raw data with the basic concept that increases in factor prices affect GDP, the following graph showing a very strong relationship between the increase in oil prices and GDP growth should not be surprising:

Figure 2 – EU15 Oil Price – GDP Growth trends 1970 – 1982⁴³

There seems to be a strong correlation between the movements of the two trends: as oil prices go up, GDP growth goes down, becoming even negative in 1975. GDP rebounds with steady oil prices, but when oil prices rise again, GDP growth slows. It is this relationship that has prompted many writers to conclude “most evidence shows that the energy shocks [of the 1970s] contributed significantly to the stagflation of the 1980s.”⁴⁴ And as recently as 2006, one study came to the conclusion that “rising oil prices seem to retard economic activity.”⁴⁵

The media immediately picked up on the theme that the OPEC had triggered the end of post-war prosperity. An Economist article from 1979 declared that “the quadrupling of oil prices in 1973-74, as a result of the Yom Kippur war, was the greatest shock to hit the world economy since

⁴³ BP, 2007; U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2007; calculations by author.

⁴⁴ Griffin and Steele, p. 21

⁴⁵ Lardic and Mignon, “The impact of oil prices on GDP in European countries: an empirical investigation based on asymmetric cointegration”, Energy Policy, 34, (2006)

1945.”⁴⁶ Following an increase in oil prices in late July 1979, the Washington Post reported that “the oil Petroleum Exporting Countries virtually assure that the U.S. economy will slip into a recession accompanied by higher inflation and increased unemployment, according to economic forecasters.”⁴⁷ As early as December 25, 1973, the New York Times reported that

“Doubling of oil prices announced by 6 Persian Gulf nations on Dec 23 is expected to accelerate recessionary forces in both indus [sic] and developing countries and add to their cost of living; for practically all Indus [sic] nations, with possible exception of US; effect of higher oil prices is likely to be trade deficit, or deeper trade deficits; it is also feared that nations may compete against each other in destructive fashion to try to protect their trading position in narrow, nationalistic terms, a development that could unleash generalized internatl [sic] recession and extensive unemployment”⁴⁸

The role of the energy crisis in the decline of the West’s economic fortune was also underlined by then U.S. Energy Secretary James Schlesinger, who was quoted as saying that “if we have inflation and unemployment as a result of the energy crisis, it will shake the foundations in the 1980s of the industrial democracies in a manner that has not been seen since the great Depression of the 1930s.”⁴⁹

Considering the significant damage the oil crisis seemed to inflict on the West, European and North American governments decided to deal with the situation in a coordinated and mutually supportive manner. The creation of the International Energy Agency, initiated by Henry Kissinger, was the most important of these initiatives, and is today one of the integral elements of the EU

⁴⁶ The Economist, “Suddenly, everything was different”, December 29, 1979, pg. 39

⁴⁷ Berry, John M. “The Opec Decision – Recession in the U.S. seen after Opec price hike.”, the Washington Post, June 29, 1979

⁴⁸ The New York Times, December 25, 1973. The spelling errors are likely not from the original, but were made when the article was entered into the LexisNexis database.

⁴⁹ “IEA agrees to action to cut demand for oil”, The Globe and Mail, May 23, 1979

energy security system. Its goal is to “co-ordinate measures in times of oil supply emergencies”⁵⁰ by setting up the “IEA emergency response mechanism.”⁵¹

“The embargo highlighted three main issues. First, it exposed a need for increased energy policy collaboration among European countries and between Europe and the energy producing world. Second, it became clear that institutional mechanisms for increased coordination in the event of future supply disruptions were essential. Third, consensus emerged that Europe should prepare strategies to prevent it from becoming the victim of future attempts by exporting nations to use energy as a political or economic weapon.”⁵²

The members of the OECD began to focus on three strategies meant to limit the ability of oil supplying countries to put political pressure on OECD nations: Demand management, Strategic Reserves, and Diversification of supplies. In the following, the effectiveness of each of these strategies will be analysed in some detail.

“The 1974 creation of the International Energy Agency (IEA), which has become Europe’s primary instrument for monitoring and analyzing world energy markets, was one response to the embargo. In addition, European countries sought to develop strategies to diversify energy supply.” These measures require “IEA member countries to hold oil stocks equivalent to at least 90 days of net oil imports and – in the event of a major oil supply disruption – to release stocks, restrain demand, switch to other fuels, increase domestic production or share available oil, if necessary.”⁵³

⁵⁰ IEA webpage

⁵¹ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 3

⁵² CRS Report to Congress, May 7, 2007, p. 3

⁵³ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 3

These “collective response actions are designed to mitigate the negative impacts of sudden oil supply shortages”.⁵⁴

The graph below provides an effective overview of the measures envisioned under the IEA system, some of which will be addressed in the discussion below.

Figure 3 – IEA Emergency Measures System⁵⁵

3.1.1. Demand Management

The focus of the IEA system was and is oil, for a number of reasons: not only was the purpose of the IEA system to explicitly deal with the problem of oil supply insecurity, but oil remains the single most important energy source in the European Union:

⁵⁴ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 3

⁵⁵ IEA, 2007

Figure 4 – EU27 Energy Mix 2006⁵⁶

Oil in turn is predominantly used by the transportation sector – and since the transportation sector is primarily fuelled by oil, it “is extremely vulnerable to short-term supply disruptions (...)”⁵⁷ Consequently, the focus of IEA demand restraint policies is focussed on reducing the utilization of transport.

“Demand restraint refers to short-term oil savings which can be achieved during the period of a crisis. The measures to achieve demand restraint fall into three main classes – persuasion and public information, administrative and compulsory measures, and allocation and rationing.”⁵⁸ “The initial emphasis is often on light-handed, voluntary measures, instigated through public persuasion campaigns. These can be particularly effective in a crisis, when consumers are more receptive to the need of saving oil.”⁵⁹ But such 'light-handed' measures are not the end of it. If necessary

⁵⁶ Data BP, 2007 Calculations by author

⁵⁷ Noland, Cowart, and Fulton, “Travel demand policies for saving oil during supply emergencies.”, *Energy Policy*, 34 (2006), p. 2994 - 3005

⁵⁸ IEA, “Oil Supply Security – The emergency response potential of IEA countries in 2000”, p. 18

⁵⁹ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 10

“compulsory measures can range from medium-handed restrictions such as speed reductions, to more heavy-handed policies such as fuel rationing.”⁶⁰

In a 2006 study financed by the IEA, it was argued that each of these policies may indeed be effective in reducing demand for oil, though it is unclear to what degree.⁶¹

Total estimated fuel savings for various policies

	Total all IEA regions (barrels saved per day)	Percent road transport fuel savings (%)	Policy context to achieve savings
Policies to increase public transport usage	280,000	1.4	50% reduction in current public transport fares
	563,000	2.8	Free public transport
	188,000	0.9	Increase off-peak public transport service
	232,000	1.2	Increase peak and off-peak public transport service
	17,000	0.1	Allow existing bus and carpool lanes to operate 24 h
	34,000	0.2	Add additional lanes for buses with 24 h usage
Policies to increase carpooling	2,240,000	6.2	Build carpool lanes along all motorways, comprehensive programmes to match riders, public information
	170,000	0.9	Small programme to match riders, public information
Increasing telecommuting	730,000	3.7	Public information to employers on benefits of telecommuting, minor investment to facilitate
Compressed 4/40 work week	520,000	2.6	Public information to employers on benefits of compressed work weeks
Driving ban	4,100,000	21	Odd/even driving ban. Provide police enforcement, appropriate information and signage
Speed limit reduction	570,000	2.9	Reduce speeds to 90 km/h. Provide police enforcement or speed cameras, appropriate information and signage
Maintain proper tyre pressures	370,000	1.9	Provide public information

Figure 5 – IEA Demand Management Effectiveness Projections⁶²

To assess the effectiveness to which the use of public transport could be increased, the authors studied, “three main approaches for increasing public transport use on an emergency basis during a petroleum crisis”⁶³: fare reductions, service frequency increases, and bus line prioritization enhancements. The most significant increase was expected from reducing or entirely eliminating public transport fees. However, “percent reductions [of total petroleum consumption] are relatively

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ Noland, Cowart, and Fulton

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ Ibid.

small for all the public transport policies.”⁶⁴ A closer look at the study also reveals that these numbers are based on assumptions which can be questioned and may overstate the effectiveness of fare reductions on increased ridership:

“According to a fact sheet from the Commission for Integrated Transport (2002), in the United Kingdom since the 1990s, local bus fares have increased by 24% and local bus use declined by 11%, which would imply an elasticity of -0.46.”⁶⁵ But this conclusion assumes that the decline in bus use is merely a function of price alone, and does not appear to consider other factors, such as attitudes towards public transport resulting from perceptions of convenience, safety, or prestige. Most of the studies cited by Noland et. al. are based on data from probably less than representative samples, such as a study that measured price elasticity in a small Australian town. Noland et. al. therefore caution that “these estimates usually reflect a stand-alone ceteris paribus fare change” and therefore may be of limited value in predicting the actual effects of policies promoting public transport during a fuel crisis.⁶⁶

Most effective, the study found, were the reductions that could be achieved by increased carpooling: these could result in up to 6.2 percent decreased consumptions for the entire OECD region.⁶⁷ However, these depend to a significant extent on the existence of special infrastructures, such as High-Occupancy Vehicle lanes on major motorways, created “either by simply restricting lanes or by major investment in dedicated facilities.”⁶⁸ But as before, these data are based on assumptions that may or may not be correct, such as that “public appeals to carpool, perhaps

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Ibid.

combined with preferential treatment of carpoolers would lead to some increase.”⁶⁹ It would require a serious crisis to determine whether this assumption holds true.

Telecommuting would also have a significant impact on the usage of fuel, up to 3.7 percent overall, though the impact would be much lower in Europe, where the IEA’s own estimates put the potential impact at only marginally above 1 percent. The basis of this estimate, however, is even more speculative than that for public transport price elasticity: the authors determined that roughly 60 percent of all workers in OECD countries could telecommute at least some of the time based on a “data set listing over 25,000 job titles by industry category, and total employment for each” from the Bureau of Labour Statistics. The only real-life data on the willingness/ability of workers to telecommute came from observations during the British fuel crisis of 2000, where it was reported that “a significant percentage rise in telecommuting” had taken place, “although the absolute numbers were small.”⁷⁰

Demand reduction policies are not new, and were practiced during the 1956 crisis as well as 1973-74 and 1979-80. On November 21, 1973, the New York Times reported that a ban on ‘non-essential driving on Sundays’ might be introduced. In Business Week article from February 10, 1975, Anthony J. Parisi and Stephen J. Shepard summarize the sometimes almost absurd attempts by the US administration to deal with the situation: “There are those who favour high energy taxes as the way to reduce imports 1-million bbl. a day by yearend and those who would rather have rationing”⁷¹ - when energy prices were already higher than in 1973. According to Parisi and Shepard, the proposed increase on oil and gas prices would have resulted in “draining \$30-billion from the

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Parisi, Anthony J. And Stephen J. Shepard “The Case against energy taxes and rationing”, Business Week, February 10, 1975

economy”⁷², and the Ford administration itself admitted that “the consumer price index would rise two points as higher energy prices ripple through the economy.”⁷³

3.1.2. Strategic Reserve Stocks

Demand management alone, however, is not believed to be enough: “In accordance with the International Energy Program (I.E.P.), each IEA member country has an obligation to have oil stock levels that equate to no less than 90 days of net imports.”⁷⁴ These stocks are held by the various IEA member governments, the IEA itself, as well as by industry. “Most member governments require certain companies ... to hold a minimum number of days of stocks. Generally, the required amount is based on a percentage of the previous year’s sales, consumption or imports.”⁷⁵

The following table provides an overview of the stocks held by IEA member states in 2006:

⁷² Ibid.

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ IEA, “Oil supply security – emergency response of IEA countries, 2007”, p. 32

⁷⁵ Ibid., p. 33

Current Stockholding Systems of IEA Member Countries

	IEA Membership	EU Membership	Structure of Stockholding Responsibility
Australia	1979	-	-
Austria	1974	1995	Agency/Industry
Belgium	1974	1957	Agency/Industry
Canada	1974	-	-
Czech Republic	2001	2004	Government
Denmark	1974	1973	Agency/Industry
Finland	1992	1995	Agency/Industry
France	1992	1957	Agency/Industry
Germany	1974	1957	Agency
Greece	1977	1981	Industry
Hungary	1997	2004	Agency
Ireland	1974	1973	Industry/Government
Italy	1974	1957	Industry
Japan	1974	-	Industry/Government
Korea, Republic of	2002	-	Industry/Government
Luxembourg	1974	1957	Industry
Netherlands	1974	1957	Agency/Industry
New Zealand	1977	-	Government
Norway	1975	-	Industry
Poland	Accession country	2004	Industry/Government
Portugal	1981	1986	Agency/Industry
Slovak Republic	Accession country	2004	Government
Spain	1974	1986	Agency/Industry
Sweden	1974	1995	Industry
Switzerland	1974	-	Agency/Industry
Turkey	1974	-	Industry
United Kingdom	1974	1973	Industry
United States	1974	-	Government

"-" Not EU member/No stockholding obligation

Figure 6 – Current Stockholding Systems of IEA Member Countries⁷⁶

The ratio of public stocks to industry stocks for the IEA as a whole is as follows:

⁷⁶ IEA, 2007

Figure 7 – Public Stocks as share of total IEA Stocks⁷⁷

While in some countries, particularly the U.S., public stocks are significantly larger than private stocks, in others government stocks constitute only a minor share of total stocks held by the IEA system. In 2006, only 17 out of the 26 member states held public stocks at all.

A significant share of the industry stock is what is generally described as “operational stock”, that is those volumes of oil that is in en route in tanker ships, pipelines, rail cars, and held on site for immediate processing. This “makes it difficult to distinguish between operational and obligatory stocks, and to monitor the stockholding obligation.”⁷⁸

Stocks are further divided into crude and oil product stocks. The latter include anything from diesel to gasoline, kerosene, and other necessary oil products. In 2006, the share of crude and oil products was as follows:

⁷⁷ IEA, 2007

⁷⁸ IEA, 2007, p. 36

Figure 8 – Total IEA Oil Stocks by Product and Crude, December 2006⁷⁹

The advantage of oil products is that in case of a serious supply crisis combined with a shortfall of refining capacity, they are of immediate use to industry and government. Their disadvantage is that oil products are significantly more expensive to store than crude. Crude, however, offers greater flexibility in terms of use when refining capacity is not significantly restricted. Few oil products can be converted into other oil products, and if there is a shortage of gasoline, for example, diesel supplies will be of only marginal utility.

In case of a significant supply disruption, or threat thereof, the IEA can decide to initiate the release of these emergency stocks. “Each country’s share in the action is then based on its share in total IEA oil consumption.”⁸⁰ The exact mechanism of stock releases are of only marginal interest

⁷⁹ IEA, 2007

⁸⁰ IEA, 2007, p. 42

here, but they involve a combination of different approaches, including auctioning into the free market, allocation of rations to priority consumers, or similar systems.

“Since its creation, the IEA has acted on two occasions to bring additional oil to the market through co-ordinated actions: in response to the 1991 Gulf War and the hurricanes in the Gulf of Mexico in 2005.”⁸¹ According to the IEA data, a total of 60 million barrels were made available by the IEA countries to offset the production loss from the 2005 hurricane season, 48% of which had come from public stockpiles – 28.8 million barrels, and 39% from industry stocks.

To put this into perspective, 60 million barrels are equivalent to less than 2 days of OECD oil consumption. Furthermore, the problem during the 2005 Hurricane season was not a shortage of oil, but the fact that the hurricanes had devastated the energy system of the American South-East as a whole – with the destruction of the electricity network having been the most damaging aspect. During a hearing on energy security at the US Congress, Daniel Yergin referred to the devastation wrought by Hurricane Katrina as the “first integrated energy shock” in history. It was simply impossible to supply oil to refineries since the pipelines required electricity to operate. The benefit of the IEA measures are not only an immediate relief of local needs, but also psychological and meant to calm the energy market, as well as give the impression that the government was doing something to address the crisis.

3.1.3. Diversification

One of the critical elements of energy security that is mentioned time and again in the literature is diversification. Diversification can mean a number of things, but most commonly it refers to the diversification of geographic regions from which energy resources are imported. The underlying

⁸¹ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 11

logic of this is that while it is impossible for most industrialised countries to fully rely on their own energy resources in an economically efficient manner – energy autarky – it is necessary to reduce the risk of energy supply disruptions by importing energy resources from as many countries as possible. “Churchill’s maxim of ninety years ago continues to hold true,” writes Daniel Yergin, “diversification of supply is one of the main guarantors of security, and, indeed, is the starting point for energy security.”⁸²

However, prior to the OPEC crisis, few policy makers made diversification of energy supplies a priority. By 1973, Europe depended for on the Middle East for the bulk of its oil supplies. In response to the crisis, it was decided that the diversification of energy resources would have to be a priority goal for the long-term management of energy security in Europe. This included not only encouraging imports from other regions than the Middle East, but also systematically developing indigenous oil resources, particularly in the North Sea.

Energy diversification also means expanding the range of primary energy sources, particularly in the area of electricity generation. While it is difficult to replace oil and oil products in the transportation sector, the generation of electricity does not necessitate any particular fuel. Electricity is a secondary energy source that can be generated by burning of primary fuels, such as coal, oil, or natural gas, by employing mechanical energy, such as windmills and water turbines, by photovoltaic means, such as solar cells, or by nuclear reaction generating heat, such as nuclear fission, and possibly fusion.

Energy supply security in natural gas is therefore closely linked not only to the physical availability of supplies from exporting countries, but also to the macro-economic policy environment, which can significantly impact the ability of importing countries to deal with eventual

⁸² Yergin, Daniel, “Energy Security and Markets”, in “Energy & Security – Toward a New Foreign Policy Strategy”

energy crises. But before it is possible to provide an analysis of current European Union economic policies relating to natural gas supply security, it will be necessary to deal to some extent with general economic theory, particularly the theory of market failure and monopoly.

3.2. An Excursion into Economic Theory

In this section, I will provide a detailed examination of the economic argument in favour of government intervention into the economy. Starting with a description of the ‘perfect competition’ model, I will discuss the concept of ‘market failure’, particularly the problem of ‘natural monopoly’, which is generally agreed by most economists to require government intervention.

“Since the days of Adam Smith, British and American economists have generally touted the virtues of the ‘invisible hand’ of market organization,⁸³” writes Richard Nelson. While Smith only mentions the term ‘invisible hand’ once, he succeeded in stating the case for the market dramatically and memorably:

“As every individual, therefore, endeavours as much as he can, both to employ his capital in the support of domestic industry, and so to direct that industry that its produce maybe of the greatest value; every individual necessarily labours to render the annual revenue of the society as great as he can. He generally, indeed, neither intends to promote the public interest, nor knows how much he is promoting it. By preferring the support of domestic to that of foreign industry, he intends only his own security; and by directing that industry in such a manner as its produce may be of the greatest value, he intends only his own gain; and he is in this, as in many other cases, led by an invisible hand to promote an end which was no part of his intention. Nor is it always the worse for the society that it was no part of it. By pursuing his own interest, he frequently promotes that of the society more effectually than when he really intends to promote it. I have never known much good done by those

⁸³ Richard R. Nelson, “The Limits of Market Organization”, 2005, p. 7

who affected to trade for the public good. It is an affectation, indeed, not very common among merchants, and very few words need be employed in dissuading them from it”.⁸⁴

Few economists today dispute Smith’s basic idea, in principle, but only under conditions of ‘perfect competition’.

“under competitive conditions, producers will be prepared to supply larger quantities at higher prices, combining inputs to minimize costs. Consumers, seeking to maximize their welfare, will purchase less at higher prizes. The producer and consumer and consumer meet in the marketplace, where their conflicting objectives are brought into equilibrium. If the quantity demanded exceeds the quantity supplied at the prevailing price, the price automatically rises, squeezing out some demand and evoking a larger supply until all those willing to buy and all those willing to sell at the prevailing price can do so. At this point, and equilibrium price is established, the market clears, and there is no tendency to depart from the equilibrium unless it is disrupted by some exogenous change.”⁸⁵

However, this harmonious situation can only prevail if the following conditions are met:

“1. **Economies of scale** *are small relative to the size of the market.* This means that average costs will rise rapidly if a firm increases output beyond a relatively small amount. Consequently, in a perfectly competitive industry there will be a large number of sellers. We also assume that there are many buyers, each of whom demands only a small percentage of total demand.

2. *Output is* **homogeneous.** That is, consumers cannot distinguish between products produced by different firms.

⁸⁴ Adam Smith, any edition

⁸⁵ Paul R. Gregory and Robert C. Stuart, “Comparative Economic Systems”, 1999, p. 96

3. *Information is perfect.* All firms are fully informed about their production possibilities and consumers are fully aware of their alternatives.

4. *There are no entry or exit barriers.* This means that the number of firms in the industry adjusts over time so that all firms earn zero economic profits or a competitive rate of return. Why? Because positive and negative economic profits create incentives for the number of firms in the industry to change. If economic profits are positive then the revenue of a firm exceeds the *opportunity cost* of its factors of production—the value of the inputs in their next best alternative use. Without entry barriers, entrepreneurs have an incentive to enter by transferring factors of production from other industries or activities. And without exit barriers, negative economic profits mean that firms will exit since their factors of production can, and will, be profitably transferred to other industries.”⁸⁶

An alternative and arguably more concise definition is the following:

- “1. Consumers are perfectly informed about all goods, all of which are private goods.
2. Producers have production functions that rule out increasing returns to scale and technological change.
3. Consumers maximize their preferences given budget constraints; producers maximize profits given their production functions
4. All agents are price takers, and externalities among agents are ruled out.

⁸⁶ Jeffrey Church and Roger Ware, “Industrial Organization: A Strategic Approach”, 2000, p. 21

5. A competitive equilibrium, that is a set of prices such that all markets clear, is then determined.”⁸⁷

In the presence of all these conditions, markets are working perfectly and the outcome of the total of market interactions is supposed to be Pareto optimal. Pareto optimality, or Pareto efficiency – named after Italian economist Vilfredo F. D. Pareto – is given when “it is not possible to make one person better off without making another worse off”⁸⁸.

The question that naturally arises is: worse off according to whom or what? Standard economic theory answers this question by referring to the concept of marginal utility, or the usefulness of an additional unit of a particular good relative to other goods from the perspective of the consumer. This is also referred to as the “willingness-to-pay,”⁸⁹ which, if aggregated for all consumers, yields the so-called demand curve of the standard demand-and-supply diagram, such as the one below. The ‘willingness-to-pay’ is different for each and every consumer, with some being willing to pay a lot for a particular good, and others willing to pay little for it. Since the natural tendency of people is to purchase less of a good as it increases in price, the demand curve is ‘downward sloping’ – the higher the price, the smaller the quantity sold.

On the other side of the market is the supplier, who is willing to sell as much as he can at as high a price as possible – to which one could refer as the ‘willingness-to-sell’. The aggregate of this is the supply curve, which is ‘upward sloping’, since more suppliers are willing to sell at a higher price than at a lower price.

The ‘market price’ is where the average willingness-to-pay coincides with the average willingness-to-sell.

⁸⁷ Viscusi, Vernon, and Harrington, “Economics of Regulation and Antitrust”, 2000, p. 75

⁸⁸ Church and Ware, p. 28

⁸⁹ Viscusi et. al, p. 77

Figure 9 - Supply-Demand Price Model⁹⁰

For the purpose of this discussion it is crucial to understand what determines the *supply curve*. According to mainstream economic analysis, the supply curve is determined by the marginal cost of the supplier, that is: the expense the supplier (producer) incurs to supply one additional unit of a particular good.

Under perfectly competitive conditions, no single supplier can sell at a price above that of others, that is: if his production costs for any unit is higher than that of other producers, he would have to sell at a higher price – but since other suppliers can provide the same good at a lower price, consumers will prefer the cheaper good. The higher cost producer cannot sell at this lower price without making a loss. Consequently, he will be forced to match the price of other suppliers by lowering his costs to the market clearing price. A supplier who can produce at a lower cost than D, however, will increase his production and supply more goods since in this manner he will be able to make more profit. He could also try to increase his price, but this would not be sustainable, since other producers would offer their goods at a lower price – and given that consumers have perfect knowledge of all goods and prices, they would chose to buy the cheaper good.

⁹⁰ Lerner, 1934

Eventually, this interplay of forces reaches Pareto optimality, also known as the competitive equilibrium, or the “social optimum relative to any distribution of resources (or income) between different individuals,”⁹¹ which is

“reached only if the resources which are to be devoted to satisfying the wants of each individual are so allocated between the different things he wants, that his total satisfaction would not be increased by any transference of resources from the provision of any one of the things he gets to any other things he wants.”⁹²

When the European Commission writes that free competition is “not an end in itself – it is a means to an end,”⁹³ it is referring to the idea of a Pareto optimal outcome resulting from the interplay of demand and supply under conditions of perfect conditions:

“[w]hen we strive to get markets working better, it is because competitive markets provide citizen with better goods and better services, at better prices. Competitive markets provide the right conditions for companies to innovate and prosper, and to increase overall European wealth. More wealth means more money for governments to use to sustain the fabric of our societies and a high-quality environment for generations to come.”⁹⁴

It should be noted, however, that Adam Smith did not use an argument akin to Pareto optimality when he made the case for the free market. It is historically inaccurate to argue, as Church & Ware do that

“Adam Smith first conjectured that competitive markets were desirable because the outcomes associated with them were socially optimal. It was as if an “invisible hand” was at work guiding the

⁹¹ Lerner, 1934

⁹² Lerner, 1934

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

interaction between firms and consumers such that the socially optimal amount of output is produced at minimum resource cost and this output is distributed to those who value it the most.”⁹⁵ More correct would be to say that “Adam Smith’s description of the market was incomplete,”⁹⁶ and Smith paid insufficient attention to the phenomenon of ‘market failure’ – when the conditions of perfect competition are not met.

There are no generally agreed clear definitions of market failure, but most economists would probably agree with the following list by Griffin and Steele⁹⁷:

1. Externalities
2. Public Goods
3. Monopoly and Oligopoly
4. Decreasing costs of production (natural monopoly)

I will briefly outline each of these types of market failure, but then focus particularly on the ‘natural monopoly’ case, because this is most relevant to the discussion of energy security.

An externality is “a cost or benefit arising from any activity which does not accrue to the person or organization carrying on the activity.”⁹⁸ Externalities are also referred to as ‘social costs’ or ‘social benefits’, depending on whether they are ‘negative’ or ‘positive’, that is: whether those who are exposed to these externalities would rather not have them, or feel they benefit from them. In his by now classic discussion of “social cost”, Coase offers the “standard example ... of a factory the smoke from which has harmful effects on those occupying neighbouring property,” and that of the “case of

⁹⁵ Church & Ware, p. 25

⁹⁶ Gregory & Stuart, p. 96

⁹⁷ Griffin & Steele, pp. 40 - 44

⁹⁸ Oxford Dictionary of Economics

straying cattle which destroy crops growing on neighbouring land.”⁹⁹ The factory owner or cattle rancher may benefit from these situations, but the neighbours (a cloth dying enterprise or grain farmer¹⁰⁰, for example) do not. The price at which the factory owner or cattle farmer offer their goods to the market reflect only the costs they themselves incurred, but not the costs inflicted on the others. The cloth dyer and grain farmer, however, have to include the costs from the damage to their goods into the price of their goods, even though they themselves have not produced more, and could have produced more at no extra cost if the damage had not been done to them.

The economic problem arises from the fact that it is difficult to deal with this situation from a macro-economic perspective, namely: would society benefit if the cattle farmer was allowed to damage the crops of the grain farmer without compensation, or would society benefit if the grain farmer were compensated?

It is at this point of only marginal interest to discuss the solution tentatively proposed by Coase (to treat factors of productions as rights, and that harmful effects are also factors of production), what matters is to recognise that the price of a particular good may not always represent the total costs to society – including the costs of those who were involuntarily harmed by the production of the good without directly benefiting from it.

Current economic theory holds that goods with negative externalities are overproduced, that is: since the producer does not bear the full cost of their production, he will supply more of the good than he would if he had to bear the full cost of production. This, however, is socially not beneficial, since the cost is now borne by somebody else, whose cost of production have been raised by the

⁹⁹ R. H. Coase, “The Problem of Social Cost”, *The Journal of Law and Economics*, v. 3 (October 1960), pp. 1 - 44

¹⁰⁰ Coase, *ibid.*

actions of the former. If the former had to compensate the latter, the production of his goods would decrease, while the production of the latter's goods would increase.¹⁰¹

A classic example for a positive externality would be that of a beekeeper whose insects pollinate the blossoms of an orchard, thereby increasing the harvest and profit of the farmer. Since the beekeeper is not rewarded for the accidental benefit his bees bestow on the farmer, he has no incentive to keep more bees than he needs to satisfy his emotional want for bees. For the economist, the case is now the inverse from the case of negative externalities: the orchard farmer can sell his fruits at a cost below what it would be if he had to run his own beekeeping operation, while the beekeeper is not rewarded for the service he provides.

Apples in this case are overproduced, while bees are under-produced. If only the apple farmer would pay the beekeeper for stocking a few more bees, he would be able to harvest far more apples – but at a cost that takes into consideration the costs of the beekeeper.¹⁰²

Public goods are effectively a derivation of the idea of positive externalities, and are defined as “goods or services which, if they are provided at all, are open to use by all members of society.”¹⁰³

The reason they cannot be offered for private profit is “A public good is a good that exhibits “jointness” in consumption: one person's consumption does not reduce the amount of the good available for consumption by others. ... It is impossible to set up ordinary markets for public

¹⁰¹ The obvious logical conundrum of this argument is inherent in the Pareto analysis, which does not consider the problem of property rights, but only concerns itself with welfare.

¹⁰² Again, the obvious absurdity of this argument is inherent in the premise. This is, however, the logic of current economic regulation.

¹⁰³ Oxford Dictionary of Economics

goods—even if one could exclude consumers who hadn't paid, the market has no tendency to set efficient prices in the way that markets do for private goods.”¹⁰⁴

As a result, “if public goods are purchased individually, their production will either be zero or very small compared to the optimal level where marginal social benefits equal the marginal social cost of production.”¹⁰⁵

Classical examples of public goods are “defence, law and order, and public parks and monuments. As nobody can be excluded from using them, public goods cannot be provided for private profit.”¹⁰⁶ In the context of the larger discussion of this paper it should also be pointed out that energy security is frequently referred to as a public good.

While it would go beyond the framework of this paper, it should be noted that a number of theorists have questioned the validity of the public goods concept, among them Demsetz who in 1970 argued that “there is nothing in the public good concept that disallows the ability to exclude” and that therefore a wide range of goods and services commonly defined as ‘public goods’ can be provided privately, even though “the private production of collective goods, for which the cost of excluding nonpurchasers is great, does not seem to be practical.”¹⁰⁷

The most prominent and politically relevant concept of market failure is monopoly. The simplest definition of monopoly is “a market situation with only one seller.”¹⁰⁸ If there is only one seller in the market, he faces by definition no competition from other sellers, and can therefore deal with the market in a radically different manner. Rather than having to match the prices of others, the

¹⁰⁴ Church & Ware, p. 588

¹⁰⁵ Griffin and Steele, p. 42

¹⁰⁶ Oxford Dictionary of Economics

¹⁰⁷ Harold Demsetz, “The Private Production of Public Goods”, *Journal of Law and Economics*, 1970, Vol. 13, No. 2, pp. 293 - 306

¹⁰⁸ Oxford Dictionary of Economics

monopolist has to take into consideration only two factors: the willingness of consumers to pay and his own cost function. While in a perfectly competitive market a producer has no influence on prices and can increase his revenues only by expanding output, the monopolist can achieve the same goal by reducing output and increasing prices.

The effect of this is most easily demonstrated graphically:

Figure 10 - Simple Monopoly Price Model¹⁰⁹

“The output is OF, and the price is OA under monopoly, compared with the competitive output, OG, and price, OC. The extent of misallocation is the value of the resources that must be brought into the industry for the price to fall to the competitive level. This value is the competitive price times the difference between competitive and monopolistic outputs, OC times FG, or the rectangle DEFG.”¹¹⁰

In the absence of competition, producers can set a price above marginal cost – no competitor exists who would bid at a lower price. At the higher price, fewer consumers will be willing to buy,

¹⁰⁹ Schwartzman, 1960; This presentation can justifiably be called the ‘text-book’ definition; see for example Skeath et. al, “Consistent Comparisons between Monopoly and Perfect Competition”, in *The Journal of Economic Education*, 23, 3, 1992 pp. 255 - 261

¹¹⁰ Schwartzman, 1960

but each unit sold provides the supplier with a higher profit than if he would sell at the competitive price. In the stylized form of this diagram, the monopolist will set the price at which he sells at a level where he can maximize his profit, which becomes a simple problem of geometry, namely how to maximize the area of the rectangle titled “monopoly profit”: as the monopoly price A increases, the monopoly quantity F decreases, changing the size of the rectangle $ABCD$, determining the area of the rectangle.

From an economic point of view, the outcome is disadvantageous since “consumers who continue to purchase the sellers’ product at the new, higher price suffer a loss ... exactly offset by the additional revenue that the seller obtains at the higher price. Those who stop buying the product suffer a loss not offset by any gain to the seller,”¹¹¹ which is also known as the ‘deadweight loss’ – the area of BDE in the diagram above.

But while “[t]his monopoly revenue constitutes a levy upon the consumers that the monopolist is able to appropriate for himself purely by virtue of his restrictive powers qua monopolist,” writes Lerner, by itself this levy “cannot be said to be harmful from a social point of view.”¹¹² However, “the levy is not mere transference. The method of raising it, namely, by increasing the price of the monopolised commodity, causes buyers to divert their expenditure to other, less satisfactory, purchases.”¹¹³ Most importantly, “this constitutes a loss to the consumer which is not balanced by any gain reaped by the monopolist, so that there is a **net social loss**.”¹¹⁴ Less of a desired good has been produced than could have been.

¹¹¹ Posner, “The Social Costs of Monopoly and Regulation,” *The journal of political economy*; 1975 vol:83 iss:4 pg:807 -27

¹¹² Lerner, 1934

¹¹³ Lerner, 1934

¹¹⁴ Lerner, 1934

However, as Lerner points out, the social loss does **not** result from a seller's effective control over a particular good: "control by a single firm of 100 per cent. of the supply of a commodity for which the demand is infinitely elastic is absolutely unimportant and has no economic significance."¹¹⁵ The dictionary definition provided earlier fails to recognize the essential nature of monopoly by focussing on the physical properties of the good in question, and ridiculed by Rothbard:

"One [definition of monopoly] is derived from its linguistic roots: monos (only) and polein (to sell), i.e. *the only seller of any given good* ... This is certainly a legitimate definition, but it is an extraordinarily broad one. It means that, whenever there is any differentiation at all among individual products, the individual producer and seller is a 'monopolist.' John Jones, lawyer, is a 'monopolist' over the legal services of John Jones; Tom Williams, doctor, is a 'monopolist' over his unique medical services, etc. The owner of the Empire State Building is a 'monopolist' over the rental services in his building. This definition, therefore, labels all consumer distinctions between individual products as establishing 'monopolies'."¹¹⁶

Rothbard echoes Lerner's basic argument that "if any quantity or complex of goods and services can be substituted at the margin for any other quantity of goods and services (and therefore have the same market value), then they are both equal quantities of the same commodity."¹¹⁷ In practice, this means

"if one pound of coal gives me the same heating power as four pounds of wood, that both of these items cost the same on the market, and I am indifferent as to which I have, the one pound of coal and four pounds of wood represent the same number of units of the same commodity. It means, further, that if I am indifferent to whether I have one hundredweight of coal every week

¹¹⁵ Lerner, 1934

¹¹⁶ Murray Rothbard, MES, p. 590

¹¹⁷ Lerner, 1934

during the winter, or an overcoat to keep me warm, then a winter's coal and an overcoat are equal quantities of the same commodity"¹¹⁸

What matters is not the physical property of a substance, but the utility of it. According to Lerner "it is only because we have not yet completely freed ourselves from the crudely materialistic conception of goods with which the Physiocrats and Adam Smith were the first to wrestle", that we fail to analyse economic goods and services from the point of view of utility rather than their 'essential' nature. He therefore suggests that instead of speaking of commodities, it would be better to speak of "units of accommodation"¹¹⁹ – or the 'utils' of some introductory economic text books.

For monopoly theory, this point is absolutely essential. If goods of radically different physical properties are interchangeable in terms of their utility, it becomes all but impossible to determine whether or not a market is working under monopolistic competition if one looks exclusively at the number of suppliers of a particular good. Lerner's example of fuel is quit apropos to the topic of this discussion: if, for example, private dwellings are generally heated by stoves, a coal merchant with exclusive access to coal will not be able to extract a monopoly rent from those in need of fuel *if* there is a large number of suppliers of wood or peat.

But for Lerner, this difficulty is not a problem at all, but rather "clears the way to a better understanding:"¹²⁰

"For what we want in the measure of monopoly is not the amount of tribute individuals can obtain for themselves from the rest of the community, by being in an advantageous monopolistic

¹¹⁸ Lerner, 1934

¹¹⁹ Lerner

¹²⁰ Lerner

[that is: single supplier of a particular physical good or specific service] position, but **the divergence of the system from the social optimum that is reached in perfect competition.**¹²¹

The measure for this, according to Lerner, is given by the classic representation of monopoly pricing already provided above, where the monopolist can charge a price above the level that would be expected under perfect competition, that is: the monopolist can charge a price above marginal cost of production. Under perfectly competitive conditions it is by definition not possible to charge above the marginal costs of production since every producer and customer has access information – not only do customers know all the prices of the market, but all producers work under the same technological conditions and therefore face the same marginal cost curve. If, therefore, a supplier is able to charge a price above marginal cost, he is working in a market that is not perfectly competitive. The degree of monopoly is therefore defined by Lerner as $\frac{Price - Cost}{Price}$,¹²² the divergence between the price that could be expected under perfectly competitive conditions, and that in fact successfully charged by the supplier(s) in question. The higher the index, the greater the monopoly power. This formula has become known as the Lerner Index.

It should be pointed out, however, that the Lerner Index has practical limitations: according to Pindyck, “in a dynamic market ... when price and output are determined intertemporally, the Lerner index ... will [not] necessarily provide a meaningful measure of monopoly power.”¹²³ The reason for this is that the Lerner index as such applies only to an instant of time, while the impact of monopoly power always applies to some interval of time.”¹²⁴ Pindyck illustrates this by pointing out that in the case of an exhaustible resource, the Lerner index can overstate monopoly power because the current

¹²¹ Lerner

¹²² Lerner

¹²³ Pindyck, 1985

¹²⁴ Ibid.

cost of extraction may be low but will increase over time.¹²⁵ The Lerner index can also understate monopoly power in the case of a company using new technology, since the current lower experience with the technology can result in higher current costs, while in the future they may in fact be lower.¹²⁶ However, Pindyck is not arguing against the basic idea of Lerner's index. What he sets out to do is to show "how the Lerner index can be generalized to provide an instantaneous measure of monopoly power that properly accounts for intertemporal constraints on production and price"¹²⁷

This definition of market power is currently in use by most regulatory agencies, including the European Commission, according to which "An economy is allocatively efficient when it produces the quantity of goods that maximise total welfare. This generally implies that prices equal marginal costs of production ... Market power can be measured by the margin between price and the marginal cost of production."¹²⁸

Pindyck's solution is to alter the formula thus:

$$\frac{P_t - FMC_t}{P_t} = 1 - \frac{FMC_t}{P_t}$$

Where "FMC_t is the full marginal cost at time t, evaluate at the monopoly output level ... [and] includes any "user costs" that result from the intertemporal nature of the firm's optimization."¹²⁹

Pindyck's formula has since been adapted to a more sophisticated form which is currently used by most economists evaluating market power:

$$\frac{P}{P - MC} = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} = \frac{S}{\varepsilon + (1 - S)f} = L_2$$

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

¹²⁷ Ibid.

¹²⁸ European Competitiveness Report 2006, p. 34

¹²⁹ Ibid.

The parameters in the Modified Lerner Index are:¹³⁰

- The firm's price (P),
- The firm's marginal or incremental cost (MC),
- The firm's market share (S),
- The market price elasticity of demand ($\bar{\epsilon}^M$). This measures the countervailing power of consumers — their willingness to do without the product or service if the price increases,
 - The firm price elasticity of demand (ϵ). This measures consumers' willingness to substitute products from other suppliers, as well as doing without the product entirely, when the firm increases the price, and
 - The supply elasticity of the competitive fringe (f). This measures the change in the amount supplied by existing or new competitors due to a change in the dominant firm's price.

Yet, the more simplistic market-share criteria which Lerner so systematically criticized is also still in use. In its “guidelines on the assessment of horizontal mergers”,¹³¹ the European Commission explicitly refers to the Herfindahl-Hirschmann Index, “which is calculated on the basis of the market shares of all firms in the market [...],”¹³² as a means to determine whether the merger of two companies would lead to an excessive concentration of market power.

The harm of monopoly, at least according to the standard theory that is the basis of current regulatory approaches to its control, is not limited to the dead-weight loss that results from the inefficient allocation of prices being set above marginal costs.

In his 1967 landmark paper *The Welfare Costs of Tariffs, Monopolies, and Theft*, Gordon Tullock argues that the standard model for measuring the social cost of monopoly understates the problem, because “there are a considerable number of costs that are ignored by this procedure [measuring the deadweight loss].”¹³³ Treating the economic costs of tariffs, monopolies, and theft as analogous, he argues that in the case of calculating the cost of a tariff by simple reference to the

¹³⁰ Practice Note – Quantitative Tests for Market Power; by the International Telecommunication Union; <http://www.ictregulationtoolkit.org/en/PracticeNote.aspx?id=2880>; accessed March 20, 2008

¹³¹ <http://europa.eu/scadplus/leg/en/lvb/l26107.htm>; accessed March 20, 2008

¹³² *Ibid.*

¹³³ Tullock, 1967

dead-weight loss created by the higher price it is ignored that the “collection of tariff involves expenditure on customs inspectors, etc. who do the actual collection and coast guards who prevent smuggling.”¹³⁴

He then continues to argue that the social cost of theft is equally much higher than the simple loss of property that is suffered as a result of the direct theft. Since most people do not want to become the victims of theft, but would rather protect their property, they will invest in protective measures, such as locks and other anti-theft devices. These, however, serve no larger economic purpose than the prevention of theft, and are therefore a reduction in social welfare.¹³⁵ The thief in turn will invest time and money into acquiring better tools and skills to overcome these security devices – further reducing social welfare. So the cost of theft is not only the theft itself, but includes the expenditure aimed at preventing it *and* the expenditure of the prospective thief into the ways and means that would allow him to become a better thief.¹³⁶

Finally, Tullock applies this line of reasoning to the problem of monopoly: considering the potential size of the monopoly profit, the “potential monopolist would be willing to invest large resources in the activity of monopolizing. In fact the investment that could be profitably made in forming a monopoly would be larger than this rectangle, since it represents merely the income transfer. The capital value, properly discounted for risk, would be worth much more. Entrepreneurs should be willing to invest resources in attempts to form a monopoly until the marginal costs equals the properly discounted return.”¹³⁷ These activities, Tullock argues, are not aimed at creating any positive economic value, but merely at securing monopoly – which, as we have already seen – is a loss to the economy. Added to these cost are then the costs involved in trying to prevent the

¹³⁴ Ibid.

¹³⁵ This line of reasoning has very important implications for the measure of economic welfare in general, since in current econometric measures, these expenditures would be counted as positive contributions to GDP.

¹³⁶ Tullock, 1967

¹³⁷ Ibid.

monopoly from being successful – antitrust regulation and enforcement require potentially significant resources, while the entrepreneurs attempting to create a monopoly would in turn invest into resources aimed at defending themselves from these preventative attacks, such as lawyers,¹³⁸ “investment in excessive production capacity, excessive accumulation of advertising goodwill stocks, and excessive product differentiation through R and D.”¹³⁹

It should be noted that Tullock made the argument at least partially in response to studies which at the time found that the actual welfare loss from monopoly power is rather small and may not be sizeable enough to warrant anti-trust activities by the government.¹⁴⁰ Curiously enough, the kind of low estimates that drove Tullock to argue almost angrily “the Department of Justice is not dealing with a minuscule problem in its attack on monopoly”¹⁴¹ were the results of studies done by, among others, the creator of the standard welfare loss model from monopoly, A. C. Harberger¹⁴².

But these estimates still underestimate the welfare loss by changing the cost curve of the firms either pursuing, or already in possession of, monopoly power “to the extent that these expenditures enter reported costs [...]”¹⁴³ since the measure of monopoly power is the difference between price and marginal costs, the added costs of monopoly profit capture increase marginal costs above what they would be without these expenses, and hence the difference between price and marginal costs is lower than it would be otherwise.¹⁴⁴ And this is still not the end of the social cost of monopoly, “if the link with the distribution of political power were considered.”¹⁴⁵ In the final analysis, Cowling and Mueller cite a study by Baran and Sweezy according to which the total social cost of monopoly

¹³⁸ Ibid.

¹³⁹ Cowling & Mueller, 1978

¹⁴⁰ Tullock, 1967

¹⁴¹ Ibid.

¹⁴² Ibid.

¹⁴³ Cowling and Mueller

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

¹⁴⁵ Ibid.

in the U.S. might be as high as 50 percent of GNP.¹⁴⁶ Before this background, it seems almost secondary that at least one study found the damage of monopoly impacting low income groups significantly more than high income groups.¹⁴⁷

None of these problems are, of course, novel discoveries and I will leave the last word on the definition of the problem of monopoly to Adam Smith whose description in light of the above appears as clear and modern as anything written today:

“The price of monopoly is upon every occasion the highest which can be got. The natural price, or the price of free competition, on the contrary, is the lowest which can be taken, not upon every occasion indeed, but for any considerable time together. The one is upon every occasion the highest which can be squeezed out of the buyers, or which it is supposed they will consent to give; the other is the lowest which the sellers can commonly afford to take, and at the same time continue their business.”¹⁴⁸

What this discussion has so far not addressed is the origin of monopoly – how is it possible that a market can fail to the point of such apparently serious damage to the general wellbeing of society? When Adam Smith discusses monopoly, he almost exclusively addresses what contemporary economic theory would refer to as ‘statutory monopoly’ – by government decree, only a particular individual, company, or group of companies is allowed to provide a particular range of goods or services. For everybody else, it was illegal to compete in these markets even if they could do so at a lower price. Much of Smith’s economic analysis can be seen as an argument against this type of monopoly. The solution to this particular kind of monopoly problem is apparent: repeal of the exclusive license.

¹⁴⁶ Ibid.

¹⁴⁷ Creedy & Dixon, 1998

¹⁴⁸ Adam Smith

The reason for this is that according to Stigler and others, “every industry or occupation that has enough political power to utilize the state will seek to control entry,”¹⁴⁹ since this will reduce the pressure of competition and allow firms to charge above marginal costs. While it could be interesting to investigate the origins of this political power that would allow the advancement of narrow interest at the expense of society as a whole, this is not strictly an economic question but rather a political one and will not be address at this point.

There is, however, a second source of monopoly that is far more interesting to the economist: so-called ‘natural monopoly’. Adam Smith never used the term ‘natural monopoly’, but he provided what could be considered a rudimentary approximation of the modern concept when he argues that

“Some natural productions require such a singularity of soil and situation, that all the land in a great country, which is fit for producing them, may not be sufficient to supply the effectual demand.”¹⁵⁰

This, however, says little more than that some factors of production are scarce. If somebody owned the only patch of land that would be suitable for the supply of a particular commodity, he would have a monopoly over this product, and this would certainly be a natural monopoly, but this is not quite what is meant by natural monopoly today.

Arguably, it was John Stuart Mill who first provided the first conceptual definition of natural monopoly as “created by circumstances, and not by law,”¹⁵¹ a definition that is – at least in principle – still used today. While a legal entity can at least in principle be abolished almost as easily as it can be created – namely by decree, natural phenomena are by definition autonomous of human action.

¹⁴⁹ Stigler, 1971

¹⁵⁰ Adam Smith, I.7.24

¹⁵¹ John Stuart Mill

However, the modern definition of natural monopoly includes more than simply a market where competition is not possible – in also includes markets where competition is not desirable:

“It is important to distinguish between using natural monopoly in the **positive** sense—a prediction that there will be only a single firm in the industry—and using it in the **normative** sense. When used normatively, a natural monopoly refers to an industry where industry average cost of production is minimized when there is a single producer. The two uses of the term natural monopoly are related, but not necessarily overlapping. It is quite possible that a natural monopoly in a normative sense, if unregulated, would be an oligopoly, not a monopoly.”¹⁵²

Leaving aside, for the time being, the issue of oligopoly, the term natural monopoly implies that in the long run it is not profitable for two firms to co-exist in the same market due to a phenomenon generally referred to as “subadditivity”. Subadditivity describes “an industry in which the economies of scale – that is, the tendency for average costs to decrease the larger the producing firm – are continuous up to the point that one company supplies the entire demand.”¹⁵³ Or to put it the other way round: “A market or industry is a natural monopoly if costs are minimized by concentrating production in a single firm. Natural monopoly exists if, over the relevant range of output, the cost function is subadditive.”¹⁵⁴ In such a market, “one firm can displace other small competitors by simply increasing production and at the same time lowering price and average costs.”¹⁵⁵

Subadditivity is generally described as the result of economies of scale and scope. The following is a concise explanation of economies of scale:

¹⁵² Church & Ware, p. 752

¹⁵³ Berg & Tschirhart, p. 21, quoting Kahn (1971)

¹⁵⁴ Church & Ware, p. 754

¹⁵⁵ Griffin & Steele, p. 44

“Suppose a particular technology that produces a well-defined product or service requires a high fixed cost and a small constant variable cost; when all demand is satisfied at a price equal to marginal cost, the average cost per unit is still falling with output and is above marginal cost. Several firms competing in this situation will drive price equal to marginal cost, so all will lose money. The high fixed cost makes large-scale operation more economical. Indeed, with this technology one producer obviously is the lowest cost form of market organization, but with only one firm there might appear to be no competition.”¹⁵⁶

Economies of scope are given when “a given quantity of each of two or more goods can be produced by one firm at a lower total cost than if each good were produced separately by different firms,” generally as the result of different goods being produced by the same machinery.¹⁵⁷

Other elements of natural monopoly are barriers to entry and exit. While natural monopolies can exist without barriers to entry, but in general, they are considered an integral element of natural monopoly. As defined above, barriers to entry are given when entry into a market requires significant investments that cannot be recouped upon exit from the market. If these barriers are significantly high, there will be little or no entry into a given market and the pressure of competition will be rather low. Barriers to entry, therefore, reduce competition and enable monopoly. But as Viscusi et. al. point out, “there is perhaps no subject that has created more controversy among industrial organization economists than that of barriers to entry,”¹⁵⁸ as they are notoriously difficult to define. The following definition by Church and Ware is not so much a definition of barriers to entry, as it is a description of their effects:

¹⁵⁶ Sherman, p. 5

¹⁵⁷ Train, p. 8

¹⁵⁸ Viscusi et. al., p. 156

“We define an **entry barrier** as a structural characteristic of a market that protects the market power of incumbents by making entry unprofitable.”¹⁵⁹

As we will see below, the problem of entry barriers is a critical element of natural gas market regulation in the European Union, as it is elsewhere.

Having established that a particular industry is a natural monopoly, the question arises what to do about it. Since left to itself, the monopolist will likely produce at a reduced level, ways and means have to be found to either induce the monopolist to produce at a higher level or else to deprive him of his monopoly profit and distribute it.

There are, however, a number of complexities involved that derive from the fact that in a natural monopoly the average costs can be either below or above marginal costs.

¹⁵⁹ Church & Ware, p. 487

Figure 11 - Natural Monopoly and Marginal Cost Pricing Model¹⁶⁰

In the latter case, if the state forces the company to produce at the level of marginal costs, the company will lose money and unless it is subsidised, will eventually go bankrupt. The problem for the regulator then is to choose between increased output and the cost of subsidization and decreased output without subsidization. While subsidization does not solve the problem of overall welfare loss, it allows governments to engage in redistribution policies that are politically expedient.

In the former case, forcing the company to price at marginal costs will not drive the company into bankruptcy but create an almost paradoxical situation. Seeing that the current monopolist is making an economic profit, other companies may be enticed to enter the market. However, since the market is a natural monopoly, the increased production by the new entrant would create losses

¹⁶⁰ Church & Ware, p. 489

for the incumbent, while the new entrant would not be able to expand output enough to break even. The result would be what has been called ‘ruinous competition’, in which two companies would try to gain control over a market only one can serve efficiently. The resources spent by the defeated company would more often than not be wasted – a phenomenon already outlined when discussing the costs associated with companies trying to achieve monopoly power. In this situation, in order to prevent decreased social welfare, the government might be forced into the paradoxical situation of protecting the incumbent against new entrants.¹⁶¹

The latter approach, paradoxical though it may appear, has been the most common approach by governments to the regulation of those natural monopolies that provide so-called public goods, such as electricity, water and sewage services, and natural gas, which are generally referred to as ‘public utilities’. Since society is said to be better off with them rather than without them, it is preferable to allow a monopoly, however regulated, to provide them rather than risk not having them at all.

¹⁶¹ Berg & Tschirhart, p. 31

4. Overview of the Current Energy Supply Security Situation in the European Union

4.1. The Structure of Energy Demand in the European Union

Assessing the success of Europe's energy diversification strategy is difficult, and depends on the analytical parameters one chooses to apply. In regards to import dependency as such, the situation today is much less favourably than it has been 30 years ago. While the EU12 depended on imported energy to just over 50 percent, it now imports more than 60 percent of its total energy consumption.

Figure 12 – EU12 Net Import Dependency 1981 – 2006¹⁶²

If one were to compare the energy dependency profile of the EU27 countries today relative to their import profile in the 1970s, the situation is even worse: in 1982, the EU27 countries as a group were almost entirely energy self-sufficient, while today, they import just under 50 percent of their energy.

¹⁶² Data BP 2007, calculations by author.

Figure 13 – EU27 Net Import Dependency 1981 - 2006¹⁶³

However, such macro comparison ignores that many of the EU27 countries were part of the Soviet zone in 1982, and that their economies were much less reliant on oil and gas than they are today. Poland, for example, supplied almost all its own energy needs from the coal mines of Silesia and was simultaneously a major coal exporter – as it is still today. Towards the end of the 1980s, many East European economies began to increasingly use oil and natural gas as primary fuels. But since few of them have any indigenous production of these resources, they became also more dependent on imports.

As a result, the European Union today is more dependent on imported fuels as it has been since the end of the energy crisis in the mid 1980s, if not more so. The European Union today spends more money on energy imports than it has since the end of the energy crisis:

¹⁶³ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

Figure 14 – Share of EU27 GDP spent on Imported Oil and Gas 1985 – 2005¹⁶⁴

But looking at the energy balance of the European Union as a whole is misleading, since it ignores the considerable regional differences of import dependence. Some countries of the EU depend far more than the average on energy imports, while others are (currently) at (near) autarky levels. Levels of dependency also depend on fuel type – different countries have very different fuel consumption profiles, and their dependencies are accordingly quite different than the EU average.

¹⁶⁴ Expenditure data approximate, do not include expenditure on coal imports. Calculations by author based on BP 2006 energy data and GDP Data from US Department of Agriculture. Numbers adjusted for 2005 constant \$ values.

Figure 15 – EU25 Import Dependency by country in 2004 ¹⁶⁵

Denmark, for example, is fully self-sufficient for fossil fuels, importing only coal. Thanks to its relatively small size and its large North Sea oil and gas reserves, it in fact exports substantial volumes of oil and gas – mostly to other European Union countries. Of the large EU countries, the UK and Poland are the least energy dependent, while Germany, France, Italy and Spain all depend to 50 percent or more on imported energy.

This becomes even more apparent when one compares the energy consumption profile of the EU as a whole to that of different EU member states.

Energy consumption in the EU27 as a whole has been by 11.2 percent since 1994. The most important fuel for the EU is and remains oil, with a share of close to 40.5 percent in 2006, while natural gas is the second most important fuel at 24.6 percent. Coal, which in 1983 provided 50.8 percent of all primary energy consumption, has declined to currently 18 percent. The contribution of

¹⁶⁵ Data supplied by the European Union DG of Energy and Transportation.

nuclear power has remained largely stable since the early 1990s, and is currently at 12.6 percent, while hydro-electric power contributes 4.3 percent, slightly less than its 1983 level of 4.7 percent.

Figure 16 – EU27 Primary Energy Profile 1983 - 2006¹⁶⁶

But this profile is very different from that of Poland. Unlike the EU, Polish energy consumption has declined since the early 1990s as a result of the Communist collapse and the subsequent economic crisis and reforms. Only since about 2002, as the economy began to grow, did consumption stabilize and begin to increase. Unlike most EU member state, and unique among the large countries, Poland's main fuel is coal, providing 61.8 percent of the country's energy needs.

¹⁶⁶ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

Figure 17 – Polish Primary Energy Profile 1983 – 2006¹⁶⁷

Gas, on the other hand, plays only a minor role at 13 percent. Even oil, the dominant fuel throughout the EU, supplies only 24.4 percent of all Polish energy needs. The main reason for this is that Polish energy generation and household heating still relies predominantly on coal, while in the EU as a whole, coal has been almost abandoned for household heating, and electricity is predominantly generating by burning oil and gas, as well as nuclear power. Supply disruptions of oil and/or gas would therefore have a relatively small impact on the Polish economy, which finds itself in a relatively favourable energy supply situation.

Germany has been successful at decreasing its energy consumption levels since the late 1980s, and even relative to 2000, despite good GDP growth over the same period. However, with a share of 37.6 percent, oil remains its by far most important energy source, ahead of natural gas at 23.9 percent and coal at 25.1 percent. Nuclear power supplies 11.5 percent of total energy consumption, while hydro power is at 1.9 percent almost unchanged over the last decade. At the same time, Germany produces no significant amounts of domestic oil, and only 18 percent of its natural gas

¹⁶⁷ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

needs. Disruptions in the supply of natural gas or oil would therefore have a significant impact on the German economy.

Figure 18 - German Primary Energy Profile 1983 - 2006¹⁶⁸

The energy supply security situation of the EU27 is further marked by a steadily increasing reliance on imported fuels. Immediately following the oil crisis, domestic production of oil in the

Figure 19 - EU12 Proven Oil Reserves 1983 - 2006

EU increased dramatically from 1.6 mtoe in 1965 to 133 mtoe in 1986, but declined rapidly until it fell to 101.8 mtoe in 1989. Production then recovered, and by 1999 peaked at 157 mtoe annually. Since then, however, European production faced a dramatic decline to 99 mtoe in 2006 – only slightly more than in 1981. At the same time, despite rising oil prices, EU reserves have been steadily falling as well, being as low as 5.8 billion barrels in 2006 – (by comparison, those of the Middle East are currently estimated at 742.7 billion). It is estimated, that at current production levels, EU reserves will only last for less than a decade. This means that even Denmark’s currently favourable energy balance will become negative for oil as well.

Figure 20 – EU12 Oil Production 1965 - 2006¹⁶⁹

So while European governments had decided in the wake of the energy crises to become less dependent on imported oil, this has been only partially successful, and in the future the EU will likely return to import dependency levels similar to that of the early 1980s.

¹⁶⁹ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

Figure 21 – EU27 Oil Dependency 1983 – 2006¹⁷⁰

On the other hand, the EU has had some success in diversifying the geographic regions from which it imports energy. The Middle East is no longer the dominant source of oil, and by 2000 increased imports from the (former) Soviet Union, Norway, and other regions – particularly Nigeria – had not replaced, but substantially displaced, the Middle East as the major exporter to the EU.

Figure 22 – EU27 Oil Imports by Region of Origin in 2000¹⁷¹

¹⁷⁰ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

¹⁷¹ Data by European Commission, 2006

At the same time, however, the EU has become increasingly dependent on oil from the Former USSR, most of which is either from Russia or transits Russia on its way to Europe. While in 2000, its share was 23 percent of all oil imported into the EU, this proportion had increased to 36 percent. So while dependency on the Middle East continues to fall, dependency on the Former Soviet Union, in particular Russia is increasing.

Figure 23 – EU 27 Oil Imports by Region of Origin in 2005¹⁷²

However, relative to the 1970s and the early 1980s, this is certainly an improvement of the general situation. Furthermore, since the oil market is considerably integrated globally, the ability of any particular country to unilaterally influence the price of oil is limited. Furthermore, considering the difficulty – if not impossibility – of the relatively unified political position among Arab states in the 1970s to effectively reduce exports to countries they were trying to pressure politically, the far more diffused structure of the current oil market will make it even more difficult for any exporting nation or group of nations to effectively employ oil as a political weapon.

But while the EU may be relatively safe from an outright embargo, there is little it can do to protect itself against rapidly rising energy prices and their effect on its economy. Since the oil market

¹⁷² Data by European Commission, 2006

is global, a global increase in oil prices will always affect the EU as well, and it will have to spend more money not only on imported oil, but also on that which is drilled domestically.

The situation for natural gas is both similar and different. Originally, natural gas was meant to counterbalance the high dependence on imported oil, particularly from the Middle East. In this function, natural gas has largely failed – the EU, as we have already seen, is as dependent on oil today as it has ever been. The partial improvements to the oil supply security situation were achieved through increased domestic production and the diversification of source regions, not the reduction in the reliance on oil as such. Arguably, the increasing role of natural gas has created a new and quite unique energy security challenge for the European Union. The demand for natural gas is driven primarily by the electricity generation industry.

While coal remains the most important fuel for electricity generation in the European Union – approximately 29.5 percent of all electricity was generated by burning coal in 2005 – the role of natural gas has increased from almost nothing in the 1970s to 20 percent in 2005¹⁷³, and its role is generally expected to increase considerably over the next decades. Oil, by comparison, is used to generate only 4.5 percent of all European electricity¹⁷⁴, with declining tendency. The use of coal in energy production is likely to decline as well in the near future, as coal is still considered a ‘dirty’ fuel, particular in the context of the global climate change debate and the desire by the EU governments at all levels to reduce CO₂ emissions. But even if the EU governments were interested in using more coal in order to diversify their energy resources, this likely would not decrease energy dependency since an increasing share of the coal used in the EU is imported.

¹⁷³ European Union DG Energy and Transportation data, 2007

¹⁷⁴ European Union DG Energy and Transportation data, 2007

Figure 24 – EU27 Coal Import Dependency 1981 - 2006¹⁷⁵

Natural gas poses a number of energy security challenges. First, and most importantly, the European Union has very little domestic gas production. While the EU27 represented 17 percent of the global gas demand in 2006, it produced only 7.1 percent of the global gas supply. The EU27 also has only about 1.3 percent of global gas reserves, and a Reserve/Production ration of 12.8 years. While these numbers compare favourably with those for oil (.6 percent of global reserves, R/P ratio of 8.1 years), they do not change the basic fact that the EU27 depends heavily on imported natural gas: it currently imports 58.4 percent of its annual consumption.

¹⁷⁵ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

Figure 25 – EU27 Natural Gas Import Dependency 1970 - 2006¹⁷⁶

A further problem for energy supply security is that the largest natural gas reserves are found outside the EU27: 63 percent of currently proved reserves are located in the Russian Federation, Iran, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates; and the Russian Federation, Iran, and Qatar control 55.7 percent of global reserves. The largest producing country in the EU, the Netherlands, has only .7 percent of global reserves, followed by the United Kingdom with .3 percent. The picture looks only slightly more reassuring when it is kept in mind that Norway controls at least 1.6 percent of global reserves.

Reserve distributions are not, however, an indicator of current production capacities. If countries are ranked according to their production surpluses, then the situation looks somewhat differently:

¹⁷⁶ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

Figure 26 – Share of Global Gas Exports by Region¹⁷⁷

The largest exporters are the Russian Federation and Canada, followed by Norway and Algeria. For political and economic reasons, Iran and Saudi Arabia currently export almost no gas at all, while Qatar is still only a minor exporter. Like oil, therefore, the distribution of gas resources is quite uneven around the world, and consequently, the EU27 depends on only a very small number of supply countries for the bulk of its gas imports.

Figure 27 – EU27 Gas Imports by Region of Origin in 2005¹⁷⁸

¹⁷⁷ Data by BP, 2007; calculations by author.

¹⁷⁸ Data supplied by EU Commission

The by far largest share of gas comes from the Russian Federation, closely followed by Norway. However, the European Union has been rather successful in reducing – at least for the time being – its reliance on Russian gas and diversifying the regions from which it imports natural gas.

Figure 28 – EU Gas Imports by Region of Origin 2000 - 2005¹⁷⁹

What are not obvious from these numbers are the tremendous challenges for any policy aimed at diversifying natural gas sources. To better appreciate these difficulties, it is necessary to understand some of the specific features of the natural gas industry.

4.2. The Economics of Natural Gas

The natural gas industry is generally considered to be almost a text-book example of a natural monopoly.¹⁸⁰

While it was possible to develop the oil industry through an almost anarchic system of wild-cat oil drilling, combined with improvised transportation methods and small scale refining, the development of natural gas requires a highly organized and integrated system of planning and development on a scale that almost defies imagination.

¹⁷⁹ Data by European Commission, 2006

¹⁸⁰ In almost every textbook on the topic, it is included in the list of common natural monopolies.

Gas is in many ways an ideal energy resource (easy to utilize by the final consumer, environmentally clean), but “the difficulties in making productive use out of it have given gas the reputation of being an energy source of low economic value.”¹⁸¹ Natural gas is difficult to exploit because it is a gas, and as such difficult to transport. Traditionally, “natural gas is usually transported through a pipeline or transmission system (a grid) from the gas field to the users,”¹⁸² or converted into Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) that can be transported by large ocean-going vessels. While the new Gas-to-Liquid technology may add a third option, I will focus primarily on natural gas and LNG.

“The first obstacle to rapid gas development is its structure of costs. Large, up-front investments are needed in pipelines and distribution systems before the gas can begin to be used. In this respect, gas is similar to electric power, water supply and other public utilities. It is difficult to start with small investments, even though initial demand will be small. This creates financial problems for the producer just at the time he is needing to expand his investment to meet future demand,”¹⁸³ and the development of gas resources therefore “requires the coordination of an integrated gas industry involving three technically distinct phases: production, transmission, and distribution.”¹⁸⁴

Natural gas developments are easily among the most expensive industrial undertakings. Cost estimates regularly range in the billions. The Shtokman gas field in the Barents Sea is currently estimated to require at least \$20 billion to develop,¹⁸⁵ while a liquefaction plant to be build by

¹⁸¹ Estrada et. al., “Natural Gas in Europe – Markets, Organisation and Politics”, p. 1

¹⁸² Golombek, Hoel, and Vislie, “Natural Gas Markets and Contracts: An Introduction”, in “Natural Gas Markets and Contracts”, p. 1

¹⁸³ DeAnne Julius and Afsaneh Mashayekhi, “The Economics of Natural Gas: Pricing, Planning and Policy”, p. 2

¹⁸⁴ Estrada et. al. p. 1

¹⁸⁵ Robin Pagnamenta, “Shell puts ‘hundreds of billions’ price tag on Siberian Arctic gas”, *The Times*, November 22, 2007

ExxonMobil in Papua New Guinea is projected to cost \$9.5 billion¹⁸⁶. Pipeline construction costs are extra, so to say: To amortize such investments, the planning horizon of natural gas companies is not years, but decades.

The production of gas, once found, is relatively easy: since it is a gas under pressure it requires little more than tapping it with a pipe and it will begin to flow. But from then on, the physical properties of natural gas become a liability. “It is more expensive to transport gas by pipeline than to move oil in a pipeline,¹⁸⁷” writes Ferdinand E. Banks. At almost any distance, the per unit cost of oil transportation is only a fraction of that of gas. Most importantly, since it is very economic to transport oil by sea, oil is generally not transported by pipeline over the distances as gas: “when gas is to be shipped by sea, it must first be liquefied, and later reliquefied, while crude oil and oil products can be pumped directly into a tanker. The capital investment for gas liquefaction and reliquefaction facilities can run in the billions of dollars, while no analogous outlay is required for shipping oil (...).”¹⁸⁸ When Banks wrote these lines in 1983, the relative costs of transporting natural gas by pipeline compared to transport by LNG tanker ships was as follows:

¹⁸⁶ Gomez, Brian “ExxonMobile PNG project to cost \$9.5 billion; oil search earmarks \$190 million for exploration in 2007, Platts Oilgram News, May 7, 1007

¹⁸⁷ Ferdinand E. Banks, “The Political Economy of Natural Gas”, p. 44

¹⁸⁸ Banks, p. 44

Figure 29 - Relative Cost of Gas Transport Options in 1983¹⁸⁹

Transporting gas by LNG was only economical if the distance was more than 6,000 km, and as a result, gas is typically shipped by tankers between Qatar and the Far East, and the Caribbean's and North America (the current shipments of Qatari gas to Spain are not motivated by economics, but are subsidized by the Spanish government in the name of energy supply security). Recent technological developments have changed the relative cost of the LNG option, which currently is economical for distances of just more than about 3,000 miles (4,800 km).¹⁹⁰

¹⁸⁹ Banks, p. 47

¹⁹⁰ James T. Jensen "The LNG Option for Middle East Gas Trade", a presentation to the Sixth Meeting of Experts from Energy Exporting and Importing Countries, sponsored by the International Energy Agency and the Gulf Cooperation Council Abu Dhabi, January 29, 2002

Figure 30 - Relative Cost of Gas Import Options in 2002¹⁹¹

However, it is unlikely that in the near future the cost disadvantage of LNG will be reduced much more, particularly since new pipeline technology may dramatically reduce the cost of long-distance over-land gas pipelines¹⁹². The following diagram shows the relative costs of the different transportation options of gas compared to oil in 2002. Unless there are going to be dramatic changes in the relative cost structure of LNG relative to pipelines, most natural gas will be transported by pipelines for the foreseeable future.

The high cost of transporting natural gas has an additional effect, not immediately obvious from this discussion: with current technology and at current prices, it is uneconomical to develop small gas fields and those located in remote land-locked regions. However, this may change in the future as a promising new technology, called Gas-to-Liquid, may change this. This process allows it to transform natural gas into so-called ‘middle distillates’ – primarily diesel and gasoline – and some

¹⁹¹ Jensen, 2002

¹⁹² Alexander A. Bolonkin, “A Low-Cost Natural Gas/Freshwater Aerial Pipeline”, <http://arxiv.org/abs/physics/0701061>; accessed March 20, 2008

believe that in the future these may compete with middle distillates derived from oil, and thus create a new dynamic in the fossil fuel sector.

But for the time being, the cost of connecting natural gas fields to consumers is tremendous. A pipeline project in Europe, the ‘Nabucco’, connecting Middle Eastern and Central Asian gas fields to European customers would cost at the very least \$7.3 billion.¹⁹³ The following diagram shows the cost of a fairly representative pipeline project in North America¹⁹⁴.

Figure 31 - Cost Profile of Typical Natural Gas Project

The high cost of natural gas transportation also has implications for security of supplies that go beyond the simple fact that exploitable natural gas resources are located in only a few regions: since most of global oil trade is done by tanker ships, the global oil trade is very flexible and responsive to demand changes. Not only can ships simply be redirected en route to new destinations, the oil stored in their hulls represents and supply reserve that is available even when supply countries decide to shut down production.

¹⁹³ Dempsey, Judy: “Russian gas will flow through EU pipeline”, International Herald Tribune, February 8, 2008

¹⁹⁴ BP, ExxonMobil, and ConocoPhillips, “Alaska Producer Pipeline Update” (May 2002), Slide 15, web site www.arcticgaspipeline.com/Reference/Documents&Presentations/ProducerInformation/5-02AlaskaProducerUpdate.ppt ; accessed March 20, 2008

4.3. Challenges to diversification

The risk of physical supply disruptions in the international oil market is, despite the experience of the 1970s, relatively low. With few exceptions, oil is predominantly transported internationally by tanker ships. Should supplies from any country be disrupted, it is generally possible to cushion the impact by the immediate rerouting of ships to ports of affected importing countries. This flexibility can even mitigate the impact of situations like the 2005 hurricane season in the U.S.. If it hadn't been for this inherent flexibility of the oil market, the OPEC embargo of 1973 would likely have been far more disruptive than it was.

The international gas trade, by comparison, is very inflexible: pipelines cannot simply change direction, and LNG can only be unloaded where there are regasification facilities, since ships with on-board regasification capabilities are currently both uncommon and very expensive. The amount of gas 'stored' inside pipelines – also known as 'diurnal' storage – is much smaller than the amount of oil 'stored' in tanker ships. If therefore a supplier 'turns off the tap', the reduction in supplies is almost immediately felt throughout the supply chain – as Western Europe learned so painfully during the 2006 Russo-Ukrainian gas crisis.

Depending on pipelines for the supply of gas therefore creates a security challenge of its own for importing countries: once the pipelines are built, and once the gas infrastructure is in place, the customers are at least in the short-run committed to the existing system and have almost no ability to substitute supplies. If the U.S. had received most of its oil in 1973 via pipelines from the Middle East, and had there been no significant fleet of tankers, the oil embargo would have been far more effective than it was. This risk was one of the reasons the U.S. strongly opposed the decision by European governments to import significant volumes of Soviet gas during the 1980s: the fear was that in case of a political crisis, the Soviets would simply turn off the tap and thereby dramatically affect the ability of Western countries to function normally.

An additional limitation on gas development is the necessity for considerable storage facilities – not to ensure security of supplies during crisis situations, but to ensure stable supplies under normal conditions: The usage of natural gas – just like that of coal and oil – fluctuates by season. More is needed in winter than in summer (or in warm countries, more is needed in summer than in winter). Ideally, there would be less production of gas during periods of low usage than during periods of high usage. However, reducing the production of gas upstream is difficult since natural gas is not produced in the same manner as oil. While the latter is being forced out of the ground by pumping, gas flows by itself once the gas field is tapped. Manipulating the flow rate at the well head is technically difficult, since it affects the pressure of the entire gas infrastructure system. It is generally preferred to keep the flow rate stable, and since the sheer volume of gas makes it impossible to store it cost effectively in tanks, storage is limited to depleted gas fields, salt caverns, or aquifers. But these geological formations are not equally available everywhere, and hence the flexibility of gas infrastructure development is limited.

The best storage facilities are depleted gas reservoirs. Having already held gas for several million years previously, they pose little risk of leakage. They also already contain what is called ‘base gas’: since gas is not extracted like oil by mechanical means, but pressed out of the reserves by the pressure differential between the atmosphere and the reservoir, a considerable amount of gas cannot be extracted once the pressure between the atmosphere and the reservoir is equalized. Any storage facility therefore needs to be filled with a certain amount of ‘base gas’. Depleted gas fields already contain this, while artificial facilities – such as salt cavities – must be filled first (and this gas can never be recovered). From an engineering point of view, depleted reservoirs are therefore ideal – except that they can only be found in (formerly) gas producing region, which limits their availability to regions that currently produce, or have produced, natural gas.

Injecting and withdrawing gas from a facility are not symmetric processes. It generally takes much longer filling a storage facility than it takes withdrawing gas from it, as illustrated in figure 32 that shows the data for the UK. In the case of the depleted fields, it takes only about 2 month to deplete the reserves, but 190 days to refill them. This has to be taken into consideration when looking at the storage-to-consumption ration's in the EU27. It also has to be taken into account that withdrawal is fastest at the beginning, and slows down as the pressure in the facility declines.

The UK's Storage Facilities and their Characteristics						
Facility	Space		Withdrawal		Duration in days	Refill Time from Empty Duration in Days
	GWh	%	GWh/day	%		
Depleted Field						190
Rough	30,344	76.2%	455	21.6%	67	
Hatfield Moor	1,260	3.2%	55	2.60%	23	
Salt Cavity						
hornsea	3,495	8.8%	195	9.3%	18	
Hole House	300	0.8%	30	1.4%	10	
Five LNG Sites	3,846	9.7%	769	36.5%	5	192
Diurnal Storage	600	1.5%	600	28.5%	1	
Total	39,845	100%	2,104	100%		

Figure 32 - UK Gas Storage Facilities

Current storage capacity in the EU27 is sufficient for 58 days, though this number is merely an average. Since the European gas network is not fully integrated, the geographic distribution of the gas storage facilities matters as much, if not more, as their actual volume.

Figure 33 - EU27 Gas Storage Capacity in days of average consumption in 2005¹⁹⁵

Italy, for example, receives its Russian gas through a different pipeline than Germany, and the two countries' pipeline systems are not significantly connected. Should therefore gas supplies through Belarus be disrupted, reducing the gas needed in northern Germany, it will be of little consolation to the Oldenburg based EWE that Italy has 13.25bcm gas in storage. And if supplies across the Ormen Lange pipeline between Norway and Scotland should ever fail, the UK will not at all benefit from the 19.4 bcm stored in Germany: since both Germany and Britain receive gas from the Netherlands, the Dutch gas pipeline network is not be able to transport gas from Germany to Britain.

¹⁹⁵ IEA, Natural Gas Information, 2007; BP Data 2006 ; calculations by author

Figure 34 EU27 Gas Storage Capacity in Billion Cubic Meters in 2005¹⁹⁶

From a supply security point of view, the current necessity to transport most natural gas by pipeline is probably one of the greatest challenges. Even if one is not worried about the possibility of governments in supply countries to cut supplies for political reasons, many of the threats to energy security do not entirely depend on the deliberate acts of governments: terrorist attacks on gas producing and transmission facilities are probably the risk that springs to mind most easily in the post-9/11 environment. But one can also not discount the risk from political unrest in either producing or transit countries. One of the most ambitious current pipeline projects in the European Union – Nabucco – would involve building pipelines through some of the most restless regions of Eurasia. Rebel movements could see the regular destruction of feeder pipelines as an effective means of exerting pressure on European and other governments. No less attention should be given to the risk of earthquakes, or the risk of floods and mudslides in mountainous territory.

Security of natural gas supplies in the long run depends on expanding the existing gas infrastructure significantly to meet rising demand and giving it enough flexibility to cushion the system against local supply shocks. Since every single stage of the gas sector involves investments in the billions of dollars, creating supply diversity is by necessity very much a question of money.

¹⁹⁶ IEA, Natural Gas Information, 2007; BP Data 2006 ; calculations by author

Additions to the infrastructure cannot easily be made incrementally, at least not as long as the economic calculus of natural gas remains as constraining as it is today. But infrastructure expansion is exactly what is needed to increase the security of supply in the European Union. This will require substantial investments into every segment of the natural gas infrastructure, from increased exploration, building more supply lines and developing better technologies.

The need to expand European natural gas pipeline import capacities both by building more pipelines and increasing the capacity for LNG was identified as far back as 1980, shortly after the Iranian crisis.¹⁹⁷ But while considerable efforts and resources have since then been devoted to building pipelines from the (former) Soviet Union and North Africa, supply has been barely able to keep up with demand. In 1994, the OECD estimated that approximately \$200 billion needed to be invested until 2014¹⁹⁸. The pipeline connection between Algeria and Italy was identified as particularly important, and it was suggested that it be expanded from then 12bcm import capacity to 30bcm/annually.¹⁹⁹ Currently, 27 bcm are exported through that particular pipeline, and Italy's ENI agreed to expand it by an additional 6.5bcm/annually by 2012.²⁰⁰ Over the coming years, about 14,300 km of pipelines are slated to be built throughout Europe, of which about 12,200 will be large-diameter long-distance pipelines.²⁰¹

But pipelines alone are not enough to ensure the energy security of Europe. Liquefied natural gas will play an increasingly important role in the future²⁰², since this would allow for the creation of a far more flexible and resilient natural gas infrastructure system than one based on long-distance

¹⁹⁷ Gianpaolo Bonfiglioli "Economics of gas imports to Europe from Oapec", Oil & Gas Journal, August 7, 1980.

¹⁹⁸ Thomas Land "Spotlight falls on gas transport: two studies look at the challenging facing industrialized countries in pumping investment into infrastructure – the industrialised world must invest heavily in energy transport infrastructure." Lloyd's List, July 4, 1994

¹⁹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰⁰ "Tunisia; Italian Gas And Oil Company ENI Plans Major Investments", Africa News, January 5, 2008

²⁰¹ Christopher Smith and Leena Koottungal, "Global pipeline plans expand", Oil & Gas Journal, February 18, 2008

²⁰² John A. Sullivan "Bodman: LNG plays Key Role in Nation's Future Energy Security", Natural Gas Weekly, February 19, 2007

pipelines alone²⁰³. The European Union aims at increasing the share of LNG imports rapidly, so that by 2013 LNG imports will be as large as natural gas imported by pipeline.²⁰⁴ But as already pointed out, LNG is not a cheap option and its development depends significantly on relatively high energy prices at the consumer level²⁰⁵.

But investing more into the already existing gas infrastructure systems will not be enough, and “meeting global energy demand will require unprecedented advances in technology.”²⁰⁶ The commercialization of “resources that are considered uneconomic or technically not feasible to develop using more traditional forms of production or transportation”²⁰⁷ is of particular importance here, particularly so-called ‘stranded gas’. In 2007, a Dutch-Norwegian cooperation project to “develop the world’s first LNG floating production, storage and offloading (FPSO) vessel”²⁰⁸ with a volume of 230,000 cubic meters was announced²⁰⁹. It is expected that this type of vessel could “have a nominal liquefaction capacity of 335 million cubic feet [10 million cubic meters] per day” and allow. If successful, this technology could significantly increase the amount of natural gas that can be brought to market, since “a considerable portion of the world natural gas reserves fall into the category termed as ‘stranded’ where conventional means of transportation via pipeline is not practical or economical. ‘Stranded’ gas reserves are either located remotely from consumers or are in the region where the demand for gas is limited.”²¹⁰ But it is necessary to put the capacity of these

²⁰³ “Politics focuses on threat to energy supplies”, Lloyd’s List, April 19, 2006

²⁰⁴ “EU ministers agree to more EC contribution to cross-border energy infrastructure projects”, Platts Global Power Report, July 27, 2006

²⁰⁵ Ed Crooks, “Flexibility to go where price rises the highest”, Financial Times, March 10, 2008

²⁰⁶ Warren R. True, “WGC: reversing natural gas misperceptions a must,” Oil & Gas Journal, June 26, 2006

²⁰⁷ James Batty, “Race is on to Build Vessel with Onboard Liquefaction Capability,” Natural Gas Weekly, October 1, 2007

²⁰⁸ James Batty, “Race is on to Build Vessel with Onboard Liquefaction Capability,” Natural Gas Weekly, October 1, 2007

²⁰⁹ One million cubic meter of LNG is approximately equivalent to 460,000 tonnes of gas.

²¹⁰ Bipin Patel, “Gas Monetisation: a techno-economic comparison of gas-to-liquid and LNG”, presented at the 7th World Congress of Chemical Engineering, Glasgow, 2005; available at

vessels into proportion: to supply the 2006 EU27 gas imports of 236 billion cubic meters, 2450 trips by such a vessel would have been required.

To ensure the long-term supply security of natural gas, it is therefore not only necessary to invest significantly into the supply infrastructure, but also to limit the stress increasing demand puts onto the system. If demand grows at a faster rate than the supply system can reliably handle, a gas supply crisis similar to that of the oil supply crisis of the 1970s may be a real possibility.

4.4. Monopoly and the European Gas Market

This has already been discussed to some extent above, but to fully appreciate some of the currently ongoing changes to the natural gas system in the European Union, it is helpful to look at the natural gas system in some more detail:

Figure 35 - Gas Market Structure²¹¹

It is quite common to refer to the natural gas sector as consisting of an upstream and downstream segment. The upstream segment encompasses “exploration for reserves and production of the gas itself”, while the downstream sector consists of “the transportation of natural gas over long distances, and the subsequent distribution on a local basis to end users ... via the gas marketing sector.”²¹²

As already discussed above, the physical delivery of natural gas to the final customer depends mostly on pipelines.

²¹¹ Barnett, p. 7

²¹² Bennet, p. 2

“Pipelines have long been considered to be natural monopolies ... based on certain core beliefs: that there are economies of scale in pipeline size and output, that duplicating pipelines would be wasteful, and that there is a need to plan the installation of pipelines and coordinate their operation to achieve the economies that are inherent in a network.”²¹³

Pipeline economies of scale result from simple geometry:

“The volume of a cylinder of length L with radius r is $\pi r^2 L$. The surface area of the same cylinder is $2\pi r L$. Doubling the radius increases the volume by a factor of four, but only doubles the surface area. Larger pipelines have less surface area per unit of volume than smaller pipelines.”²¹⁴ The costs of pipeline development are certainly more complex than this simple problem of geometry, and also involve the extra cost of stronger materials required to deal with the greater pressures of higher-volume pipelines. But this simple geometric principle is one of the key factors determining the costs of pipelines.

A second reason why pipelines are a natural monopoly has to do with the fact that gas pipelines are a network industry, which

“could fail to realize the economies of coordination if each pipeline segment is independently owned and operated. Competition ... could not achieve the coordination needed to operate efficiently the network because each firm controls only a small part of it and cannot internalize the gains of coordination over the portion of the network where they occur. Full coordination might require that all the segments be owned and operated by a single firm, so that the externalities are internalized inside the firm.”²¹⁵

²¹³ Vancy and Walls, p. 15

²¹⁴ Church & Ware, p. 54

²¹⁵ Vany and Walls, p. 16

In addition to this inherent monopoly nature of the natural gas sector, much of the European gas industry “has historically been organised around state owned monopolies ... responsible for ensuring gas supplies to the consumers of each country [because of] European governments’ concern over supply security.”²¹⁶

After the oil crisis of the 1970s, many European governments decided that natural gas should be given a greater role in the economy to counterbalance the importance of oil. This was done primarily by relying on the already existing energy supply structures dominated by state corporations and other government sanctioned monopolies.

Gas companies in most European countries, with the exception of Germany, “were created either as extensions of existing state-owned gas companies, or from a mixture of (private) gas producers and state-owned companies and also (in the case of the Netherlands) a direct government shareholding.”²¹⁷ Known as ‘transmission companies’, they were responsible for importing gas into their respective national markets (and/or to deliver it from the gas fields in the case of the Netherlands, Britain, and other natural gas producing countries).

But nevertheless, this situation has led to a number of systematic problems, including gas prices and price patterns throughout the EU that seemed to bear little relationship to the marginal cost of supplying gas to customers, and were in general higher than in North America.²¹⁸ Furthermore, and from the perspective of energy supply security most worrisome, was the general lack of interconnection between the different national natural gas systems. While so far this had not

²¹⁶ Anthony Bennet, “Natural Gas in Europe,” 1995, p. 3

²¹⁷ Stern, *Competition and Liberalization in European Gas Markets*, p. 12

²¹⁸ European Commission, “Opening up to Choice – Launching the Single European gas market,” 2000, p. 4

led to any acute problems, it was and is widely considered to be a serious threat to the general energy security situation in the European Union.²¹⁹

The existence of monopoly structures in the energy sector was seen as contradictory to the spirit of the Treaty of Rome and the goal of European institutions to create an integrated market for all goods and services throughout the continent. Regardless of how necessary the creation of these national monopolies had been to create the natural gas supply infrastructure of the European Union, there was a growing belief that “monopoly power had been exploited to allow inefficiencies.”²²⁰ To reduce these inefficiencies, the European Commission began to work towards a systematic restructuring of the European gas industry that would in the long run allow for competition and improve both efficiency and supply security.

Of critical importance was a systematic change to the way the natural gas sector was being re-conceptualized. Rather than considering the entire gas supply chain as a unified whole, regulators began to approach each element individually. It was soon realized that while the sector did contain elements that were naturally monopolistic, the industry as a whole was structurally capable of being organized in a far more competitive manner than it had traditionally been the case.

While most analysts agree that the lower end of the supply chain is a natural monopoly, there is considerable debate whether this is the case for long-distance pipelines as well. For the time being

²¹⁹ See, among others, “Communication from the European Commission to the European Parliament and the Council – the internal market in energy: coordinated measures on the security of energy supplies, 2002: “of major importance for the functioning of internal markets is the interlinking of networks since it plays a fundamental role in the flexibility of supplies. The lack of network infrastructure ... could hinder integration of national markets and thus restrict security of supplies.

²²⁰ Bennt, p. 3

regulators in the EU continue to recognise that pipeline infrastructures are in fact natural monopolies.²²¹ LNG infrastructures and gas storage, too, are generally seen as natural monopolies.

However, European regulators decided that one could differentiate that the transportation of natural gas can be organized independently from the marketing of natural gas to final consumers. Traditionally, local distribution companies had not only been responsible for physically delivering natural gas to households and industry, but also for selling it. These two activities, however, do not necessarily have to be conducted by the same company.

A common analogy to this is railways. It is conceivable that the operation of railway tracks is seen as a service to companies operating railroad cars, who in turn provide a service to those companies that need to deliver goods via railways. Even the running of trains can be divided into the locomotion business and the business of operating rail cars. Owners of train engines can come to an agreement with the operators of tracks to make the track available to them at a particular time over a particular distance, while offering their pulling service to the owners of railway cars, who in turn offer their cars to businesses in need of transportation.

While each of these operations constitutes a natural monopoly – there is likely only one track connecting different locations, while each segment of this track can accommodate only one train at any time, and each locomotion can only pull a maximum number of tonnage, and each rail car can only accommodate a given tonnage or volume – there can be competition between engine operators for track access, competition for rail car owners for access to locomotives, and competition among customers for haulage space.

²²¹ Christian von Hirschhausen, “Reform der Erdgaswirtschaft in der EU und Deutschland: Wie viel Regulierung braucht der Wettbewerb?“, *Perspektive der Wirtschaftspolitik*, 2007 7(1), 89- 103; author’s translation

The entire railway system can only be financed from the revenues that come from selling tickets to passengers and providing haulage capacity to individuals and companies. If the track operator were to control the entire rail system up to the rail cars, he would have an incentive to act as a monopolist and reduce the supply of passenger and haulage capacity the point where he maximizes his monopoly profit. By splitting the railway system into its component parts, and by operating each system element as an independent business unit, the dynamic is changed fundamentally: car operators have to compete for passengers and freight revenues with each other, while different engine operators have to compete for car haulage revenues.

The regulatory term for separating the various aspect of the railway or natural gas business, or any other business that has similar properties, is called 'unbundling'. It is now no longer possible to earn a monopoly profit by limiting the amount of passenger and freight hauling capacity, since there is more than one supplier of these services competing with each other. It is also not possible anymore to earn a monopoly profit by limiting the amount of locomotion capacity, since there is more than one locomotion operator.

The same logic applies to the natural gas system. The ultimate source of revenue in the natural gas business is to sell it to final consumers. As long as the operators of pipelines can control the supply to customers, they will have the ability to earn a monopoly profit by reducing the supply of natural gas and increasing prices. If, however, the business of selling gas to customers is separated from the business of delivering the gas, the dynamic changes analogous to the change brought about by separating the passenger and freight haul business from the track operation business. Different gas merchants are now competing with each other for gas consumers and are no longer able to earn a monopoly profit.

However, unbundling alone does not solve the monopoly problem entirely. For railways, it is still possible to earn a monopoly profit by limiting the amount of tracks available to locomotion operators, while the pipeline operator is still able to earn a monopoly profit, even though reduced, by limiting the amount of pipeline capacity that he makes available to merchants. The size of the monopoly profit may be reduced, but it still exists.

Furthermore, it may still be legal for the track or pipeline operating company to be involved at the other levels of the business. Since in Europe, the marketing of natural gas used to be the responsibility of the LDC, many of these still have the right to market the gas they transport. This, however, creates an incentive – or at least temptation – to give priority to their own subsidiaries when it comes to allocating pipeline volume. Unbundling therefore means more than “accounting separation, functional separation, operational separation, and divesture,”²²² of the different levels of business, but its goal is always “to ensure that a vertically-integrated transport company does not discriminate in favour of its own gas supply business.”²²³

To make this possible, regulators have developed the concept of ‘essential facilities’, and While there is no universal definition of essential facilities, in the context of natural gas, they generally encompass “pipelines, compressors, gas storage, gas treatment and LNG terminals,”²²⁴ just like tracks are essential facilities for the railway business. Since it is generally “not feasible to duplicate them,”²²⁵ regulators have developed the principle of Third Party Access (TPA), according to which “competing gas suppliers need to be allowed fair access to these facilities to enable them to compete.”²²⁶

²²² OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, date?, p. 16

²²³ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, date?, p. 16

²²⁴ DEPARTMENT OF TRADE AND INDUSTRY, Conditions for Truly Competitive Gas Markets in the EU, volume I, p. 32

²²⁵ Ibid.

²²⁶ Ibid., p. 32

Starting in the late 1990s, the European Commission issued a number of so-called Gas Directives, which systematically aimed at changing this:

“The first gas Directive required unbundling in the form of accounting separation only. The second Directive goes further in requiring legal separation but not separation at the level of ownership. This means that transportation and supply businesses may be held in separate subsidiaries but can be owned by the same parent company.”²²⁷

But while “[t]he unbundling requirements do not prevent the operation of a combined transmission, LNG, storage and distribution system operator provided it is legally independent from other activities, including the supply business,”²²⁸

these different business units have to act as if they were not affiliated to each other but were in fact separate companies without a common financial interest. Most importantly, however, infrastructures – particularly pipelines and storage facilities, but also LNG facilities – have to be made accessible to third parties under so-called Third Party Access regimes.

The key step towards this was the Gas Directive of 1998, which mandated the “non-discriminatory rights to build new gas infrastructure facilities, non-discriminatory access to the gas system and unbundling of the internal accounts of vertically integrated companies.”²²⁹

The provision of ‘non-discriminatory rights to build new gas infrastructure facilities’ meant simply (but not unimportantly) that henceforth anybody had the legal right to build any type of gas infrastructure element, including local pipelines, transmission pipelines, gas storage facilities, LNG facilities, etc. No special privileges could be given by regulators to incumbent or state companies.

²²⁷ *Ibid.*, p. 77

²²⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 77

²²⁹ *Ibid.*

This aspect of the directive was relatively uncontroversial. The other two provisions, non-discriminatory access and unbundling, however, continue to be highly controversial to this day, and will be examined in some detail below.

By forcing the owners of pipelines to provide transportation capacity to gas trading companies, a major obstacle to the creation of a competitive market on the consumer level was removed, at least in principle. Without Third Party Access,

“whoever needs gas has seldom had any choice other than buying from the owner of the pipeline to which he is connected. The end user has been bound to his local distribution company, which, in turn, has been forced to buy gas from the connected transmission company. Similarly, gas producers have had limited opportunity for selling gas other than to transmission companies.”²³⁰

²³⁰ Ketil Boe Moen, “The Gas Directive: third party transportation rights – but to what pipeline volumes?”, 2003 *Journal of Energy and Natural Resources Law*, Volume 21-1. Accessed at <http://www.dundee.ac.uk/cepmlp/journal/html/Vol13/vol13-1.html> on March 20, 2008

5. Critical Discussion of the European Union approach to Energy Supply Security

For both historical and political reasons, the impact of energy market dynamics on the general economy tends to be systematically overestimated. While fossil fuels are indeed of vital importance for a modern economy today, this does not mean that even significant fluctuations in the price of energy will always translate into significant macro-economic disruptions. As the analysis in this chapter will show, the impression that the OPEC crisis of 1973 triggered a global recession is probably incorrect. Significant and sustained increases in energy prices may in fact damage the economy as a whole, but short-term fluctuations even at the scale of the 1973 price hike have little, if any demonstrable impact. Energy policies designed to deal with short-term fluctuations in the supply and price of energy are probably unnecessary, and likely counterproductive.

Still, the risk of significant supply disruptions is real and can have dramatic impacts on the welfare of individual consumers and businesses, even if the economy as a whole is far more resilient than generally assumed. Energy policies should therefore be focussed on creating the conditions for a reliable and flexible energy infrastructure that can absorb even significant supply shocks by distributing the impact more evenly throughout the economy.

Unfortunately, current European energy policies designed to achieve this goal are likely to achieve the opposite as they are predicated on a short-term and simplistic understanding of the role of monopoly in the economy. Failing to differentiate between statutory monopolies that can persist indefinitely under the protection of government and monopolies that exist temporarily as the result of a functioning market economy, the European Union is undermining the ability of the European energy industry to invest significantly into the infrastructures necessary for the provision of a stable and reliable energy supply.

5.1. A Reassessment of the OPEC Crisis and the Threat of Oil Shocks

In its 2001 Green Paper on Energy Supply Security, the European Commission claims that “today, petrol is vital for the functioning of the economy, *like bread*. Any disruption of supply is likely to lead to social demands, if not social conflict. The situation *is similar to that created by a bread shortage two hundred years ago*.”²³¹ This comparison does not stand up to close scrutiny, but it certainly makes for good political rhetoric. After all, the French Revolution was not only the result of widespread agricultural mishaps, but also the persistent decade-long political and economic mismanagement of the state by the ancient regime.

Equally curious is the claim by the EU Commission, namely that “we must not forget that the first two oil crises helped put an end to full employment.”²³² At first glance, the statement seems to imply that the oil crises put an end to full employment, and that energy dependency is therefore a serious threat to the economic welfare of the people of Europe. But, one should also note the word ‘helped’ – a qualifier that can mean anything from ‘the oil crises accelerated a process that was happening independently’ to ‘the oil crises caused the chain of events that have led to the regrettable result of the 1973 stagflation.’ In the context of the Green Paper it is unlikely that the first meaning was implied – after all, what it would not be necessary to specifically deal with a problem if all it does is simply make an already bad situation worse. Since Green Papers are political documents with political purposes, it should be clear that the writers deliberately implied the second meaning, while hedging their empirical bets in safe language.

²³¹ EU Commission 2001 Green Paper, p. 65; it is strange – and not without humour – that an EU Commission document would portray the EU to be in a situation similar to that of France during the last years of the Ancien Regime...

²³² EU Commission 2001 Green Paper, p. 65

It is even more critical to note that while the Commission argues that “the strike in autumn 2000 by those particularly affected by the rise of oil prices, notably truck drivers, is an example”²³³ of the kind of disruptions an energy crisis can cause, it conveniently ignores that “the protests of consumers were focused at least as much on the levels of national taxation of oil products as the initial OPEC charges [that led to the rise in price]”²³⁴. The recent history of energy security in Europe is as much a history of the real risks associated with importing energy from distant regions as it is a history of government mismanagement of the economy and the energy sector.

Most importantly, there are good reasons to believe that the original energy crisis of 1973-74 which gave rise to the current system of energy security management was far less significant than generally assumed. While unquestionably contributing to the subsequent economic crisis, the stagflation of the 1970s was largely caused by long-term monetary expansion that created an unsustainable period of rapid economic growth. If the energy crisis of the 1970s did not cause the economic crisis of the 1970s, an argument which I hope to have made convincingly, then energy security policies that are based on the assumption that it did are inherently flawed and should be rethought.

However, there are good reasons to question this received wisdom – without putting into doubt the fundamental economic principle that increased factor costs decrease production. First of all, it has to be noted that the overall share of energy in the total GDP of industrialized nations is rather small. The 1972 GDP of the EU15 in 1972 was \$4.1 trillion (in constant 2000 \$), while total expenditure on oil, as already mentioned, was \$49.27 billion, or 1.2 percent. By 1975, GDP was

²³³ EU 2001 Green paper, p. 65

²³⁴ Barton et. Al, p. 4

\$4.38 billion, and expenditure on oil the equivalent of 3.48 percent of total GDP. In 1979, the European countries spend the largest amount of their GDP on oil, 7.65 percent. By comparison, in 2006, the EU15 spent 3.22 percent of total GDP on oil. The importance of oil in the national economies of Europe is therefore relatively small, compared to the total GDP. But still, it may just be that this is enough to send an economy spinning in the short run.

More important than the relative size of the expenditure on oil relative to GDP is the fact that the relationship between this expenditure and GDP growth is less clear than the data above implies. When a longer period of time is taken into consideration, the relationship between oil prices and GDP growth becomes rather weak. The same study already quoted that concluded that rising oil prices seem to negatively impact GDP growth also found that they do so “by more than falling oil prices seems to stimulate it.”²³⁵ A careful study of the GDP and energy price data for the period from 1971 – 2001 reveals that the relationship between oil prices and economic development seems to be inconsistent. While the link is striking in 1973-74, there seems to be no relationship between energy prices and GDP development for the subsequent years to 1981. Subsequently, however, the link becomes much weaker, until in 1999 – 2001, increasing energy prices coincide with a growing economy. Clearly, except for the OAPEC embargo and the Iranian crisis, the link between energy prices and GDP is at best weak.

²³⁵ Lardic and Mignon, “The impact of oil prices on GDP in European countries: an empirical investigation based on asymmetric cointegration”, *Energy Policy*, 34, (2006)

Figure 36 – EU15 GDP – Oil Price Trends 1971 - 2001²³⁶

This is, of course, an interesting observation and it is difficult to see how this corresponds to the simple dynamic used to explain falling GDP growth as the result of rising energy prices. This weakening relationship has not gone unnoticed by policy makers, either, and the 2001 EU Commission Green Paper states “While industrialised countries were at a breaking point following the two oil crises (1973 and 1979), this is no longer the case today.”²³⁷ However, the Green Paper also provides an explanation for this: “Energy diversification, the almost general exclusion of oil products from the production of electricity, and structural changes in Europe’s economy which has changed from being an industrial society to a service society, have lessened the impact of erratic fluctuations in the price of oil.”²³⁸ This explanation is not, however, particularly convincing: the price of gas, for example, is indexed on oil: when oil prices rise, so do gas prices – albeit with a lag of sometimes several months. Also, the European economies rely far more on road transport today

²³⁶ BP, 2006; US Department of Agriculture, 2006; calculations by author

²³⁷ 2001 Green Paper, p. 38 - 39

²³⁸ 2001 Green Paper, p. 39

than during the 1970s. An increase in the price of oil therefore always increases the price of transportation and with it the price of goods that are transported by road.

In a 1996 study, researchers examined “the existence and direction of causality between oil prices, oil consumption, real output, and several other macroeconomic policy variables”²³⁹ and concluded that “oil price shocks are not a major cause of U.S. business cycles. Moreover, our findings also suggest that both oil prices and real output cause significant changes in oil consumption without feedback.”²⁴⁰ This in lay terms means that the economy affects oil consumption levels, but not vice versa. This seems to correspond to the trend lines of long-term GDP growth rates and oil prices above.

With hindsight, however, it becomes clear that the link between the oil crisis and the recession was probably a lot weaker than generally believed.²⁴¹ Since the explanation for the impact of oil on GDP growth is that it increases the factor costs, there should be a relationship between the expenditures on oil as share of total GDP and the growth rates of GDP.

Yet the impact on GDP during this time is less clear than expected:

²³⁹ Ali F. Darrat, Otis W. Gilley, and Don J. Meyer, “US Oil Consumption, Oil prices, and the Macroeconomy”, *Empirical Economics* (1996), p. 317-334

²⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

²⁴¹ Throughout this discussion, it should be kept in mind that this analysis relies significantly on data that was not available at the time. It would be unfair to blame decision of the 1970s for not knowing what is known 30 years later. Current decision makers, however, should know better – but still tend to act on the basis of three decades old concepts.

Figure 37 – EU15 Oil as Share of GDP/GDP-Growth 1969 - 2003²⁴²

While during the 1970s, there seems to be a fairly close relationship between the share of GDP spent on oil and the rate of GDP growth, this relationship appears to weaken as we enter the 1980s and particularly the 1990s. Between 1988 and 1993, for example, GDP growth is steadily slowing down even though the share of oil expenditure is declining or remaining stable.

To identify whether or not a reliable correlation exists between these two factors, I ran several correlation analyses. If the text-book link between GDP growth and the role of oil in the economy is in fact correct, than one would expect to see a more or less stable relationship between the two measures. If the link is not stable, or does not follow any identifiable pattern, the case for explaining the economic crisis of the 1970s and 1980s with the supply shock thesis becomes weak.

In the years between 1970 and 2004, no significant correlations were found between expenditure on oil as share of GDP and GDP growth. The low, but significant, correlation between the price of oil and GDP growth is not relevant to this discussion since the price of a commodity can only impact the economy if it translates into a significant expenditure as share of the economy overall.

²⁴² BP, 2006; US Department of Agriculture, 2006; calculations by author

Correlations

		growth rate of GDP	oil expenditure as share of gdp	GDP in 2000\$	Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	oilprice	chance in oil prices
growth rate of GDP	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	1 35	-.243 .160 35	-.232 .181 35	-.315 .065 35	.155 .374 35	-.350* .039 35	.110 .528 35
oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.243 .160 35	1 .160 35	-.445** .007 35	.968** .000 35	.257 .137 35	.958** .000 35	.287 .095 35
GDP in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.232 .181 35	-.445** .007 35	1 .007 35	-.218 .208 35	-.138 .429 35	-.237 .170 35	-.132 .449 35
Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.315 .065 35	.968** .000 35	-.218 .208 35	1 .193 35	.226 .193 35	.989** .000 35	.258 .135 35
change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.155 .374 35	.257 .137 35	-.138 .429 35	.226 .193 35	1 .358 35	.160 .358 35	.996** .000 35
oilprice	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	-.350* .039 35	.958** .000 35	-.237 .170 35	.989** .000 35	.160 .358 35	1 .358 35	.198 .255 35
chance in oil prices	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.110 .528 35	.287 .095 35	-.132 .449 35	.258 .135 35	.996** .000 35	.198 .255 35	1 35

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 38 - Correlation between Oil Price, Expenditure on Oil, and GDP in the EU 1970 - 2004²⁴³

When the same analysis is run for the time from 1970 – 1987 (the year with the highest GDP growth after the 1979 crisis), the correlation between GDP growth rates and the share of oil expenditure in GDP becomes significant and is negative. At least for the period from 1970 to 1987, the text-book model seems to be correct.

²⁴³ BP, 2006; US Department of Agriculture, 2006; calculations by author.

Correlations

		growth rate of GDP	oil expenditure as share of gdp	GDP in 2000\$	Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	Oil Price	Change in oil prices
growth rate of GDP	Pearson Correlation	1	-.509*	-.322	-.512*	.122	-.579*	.052
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.031	.192	.030	.630	.012	.836
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation	-.509*	1	.328	.991**	.217	.966**	.255
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.031		.184	.000	.388	.000	.308
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
GDP in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation	-.322	.328	1	.431	-.272	.505*	-.230
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.192	.184		.074	.274	.032	.359
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation	-.512*	.991**	.431	1	.152	.987**	.192
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.030	.000	.074		.547	.000	.447
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation	.122	.217	-.272	.152	1	.073	.996**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.630	.388	.274	.547		.773	.000
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
Oil Price	Pearson Correlation	-.579*	.966**	.505*	.987**	.073	1	.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	.000	.032	.000	.773		.636
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
Change in oil prices	Pearson Correlation	.052	.255	-.230	.192	.996**	.120	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.836	.308	.359	.447	.000	.636	
	N	18	18	18	18	18	18	18

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 39- Correlation between Oil Price, Expenditure on Oil, and GDP in the EU 1970 - 1987²⁴⁴

But when only data since 1988 is taken into account, the correlation between GDP growth, oil prices, and share of total oil expenditure as share of GDP disappears.

²⁴⁴ BP, 2006; US Department of Agriculture, 2006; calculations by author.

		Correlations						
		growth rate of GDP	oil expenditure as share of gdp	GDP in 2000\$	Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	Oil Price	Change in oil prices
growth rate of GDP	Pearson Correlation	1	-.060	-.112	-.108	.214	-.072	.252
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.820	.668	.680	.408	.784	.329
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation	-.060	1	-.088	.847**	.493*	.933**	.473
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.820		.737	.000	.044	.000	.055
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
GDP in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation	-.112	-.088	1	.450	.342	.269	.345
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.668	.737		.070	.179	.296	.175
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
Expenditure on Oil in 2000\$	Pearson Correlation	-.108	.847**	.450	1	.620**	.980**	.605*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.680	.000	.070		.008	.000	.010
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
change in oil expenditure as share of gdp	Pearson Correlation	.214	.493*	.342	.620**	1	.594*	.998**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.408	.044	.179	.008		.012	.000
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
Oil Price	Pearson Correlation	-.072	.933**	.269	.980**	.594*	1	.578*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.784	.000	.296	.000	.012		.015
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17
Change in oil prices	Pearson Correlation	.252	.473	.345	.605*	.998**	.578*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.329	.055	.175	.010	.000	.015	
	N	17	17	17	17	17	17	17

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 40 - Correlation between Oil Price, Expenditure on Oil, and GDP in the EU 1980 - 2004²⁴⁵

If the theory that the factor prices of oil have a direct impact on GDP were correct, one would have expected to find a much clearer link between the amount of GDP dedicated to oil and the growth of GDP. However, this link only exists in the period up to 1988, and becomes weaker as one moves away from the first oil crisis in 1973.

This data does not show that there is no link between factor prices and GDP growth – economic theory makes it clear that the link exists in principle – but it clearly shows that the economic crisis of the 1970s and 1980s was *not caused* by the change in oil prices. Oil prices likely played a role, but – as Barsky and Killian argue – oil prices were not decisive.

But if falling oil prices do not automatically lead to an increase in economic activity, then the simple model relating the price of oil to the economy by means of factor price increases cannot be

²⁴⁵ BP, 2006; US Department of Agriculture, 2006; calculations by author.

correct. If all things were equal and oil prices were the only changing variable, the relationship should hold, but the real economy is more complex, and the asymmetry between rising and falling oil prices requires an explanation.

A team of American researchers may have found just this explanation. In a 2000 paper, they “provide a model that can explain the bulk of stagflation by monetary expansion and contractions without reference to supply shocks.”²⁴⁶ They based their arguments on the monetary theory of inflation, according to which inflation is the result of an increased money supply and/or an increased velocity of money. While an increase in factor prices can decrease economic growth, it cannot trigger inflation. If oil becomes more expensive, more resources have to be devoted to oil and as a result, fewer resources are devoted to other goods. The price of oil goes up, but the price of other goods must go down, relative to oil. This would decrease economic growth for those goods that require energy for their production, but does not lead to an increase in the volume of money. Since the economic crisis of the 1970s was not only a case of decreased economic growth, but also of high inflation, Barsky and Killian saw the root of the economic crisis in the rapid expansion of the global money supply that began in the late 1960s, as a result of which inflationary pressure began to increase long before the OAPEC oil price increase in late 1973:

²⁴⁶ Barsky, Robert B. and Kilian, Lutz, "A Monetary Explanation of the Great Stagflation of the 1970s" (February 2000). NBER Working Paper No. W7547. Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=214990>

Figure 41 – Money Growth and Inflation: Ten Industrial Countries 1960 - 1990²⁴⁷

This rapid expansion created a fast, if short-lived, economic boom with rapidly rising demand for commodities of all kinds, as evident in the steep increase of commodity prices:

²⁴⁷ Barsky & Killian

**Figure 4: Monthly Price Indices for
Crude Oil and for Non-Oil, Non-Agricultural Commodities
1948.1-1997.5**

Figure 42 - Monthly Price Indices for Crude Oil and Non-Agricultural Commodities 1948 - 1997²⁴⁸

Oil prices, however, remained comparatively stable.²⁴⁹

Figure 43 - Global Oil Balances 1965 – 1973²⁵⁰

²⁴⁸ Barsky & Killian

²⁴⁹ Barsky & Kilian, 2000

What is particularly striking is that between 1965 and 1973, global oil consumption had increased by 61%, while prices had remained almost completely stable. One could argue that prices remained stable because consumption had increased at the same rate as production, but there are a number of problems with this. Most significantly, nominal prices from 1961 to 1969 had remained unchanged at \$1.80/barrel, while real prices were declining.

The reason for these strange price levels that until the early 1970s, the Western oil companies – collectively known as the “Seven Sisters” effectively controlled the entire oil market outside the Communist zone. Paying the governments of producing countries royalties based on the official price of oil, it was in their interest to keep official oil prices as low as possible. Their traditional position in these countries gave these companies tremendous political and economic power and they were able to keep the price of crude oil far below market prices, and even lower than at will. A company like Exxon “did not negotiate with oil-exporting nations; it simply announced the price cuts”²⁵¹ that best fit its own business interest. By keeping oil prices as low as possible, oil companies maximized their own profits and partially subsidized the Western post-war boom at the expense of the oil exporting countries.

The power of the oil majors was so significant they were able to effectively nullify the policies of entire countries when these went against the interest of the Western oil companies.

“In 1951, the Iranians, led by Prime Minister Mosaddegh, nationalized British Petroleum’s Iranian properties in an attempt to wrest effective control of their oil industry away from the British. The ‘seven majors, controlling 98 percent of the world oil market responded by instituting a boycott of Iranian oil, and they easily

²⁵⁰ BP, 2007; calculations by author

²⁵¹ Stobaugh & Yergin, p. 23

supplied the world markets by increasing production in the other Middle East nations – primarily Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Iraq.”²⁵²

But with oil prices set far below market clearing level, demand increased rapidly – far more rapidly than investment into new production capacities, and by the 1970s the power relationship between oil producing nations and the oil majors had changed: “not only had U.S. production reached its limits, but also a number of oil-exporting nations, such as Libya, Algeria, and Kuwait, were approaching production peaks.”²⁵³ There was little spare production capacity left in the oil market that would allow the oil majors to outmanoeuvre individual countries in their attempt to raise oil prices, and in 1971, a 50 cent/barrel increase was conceded to the oil producing nations which by then had banded together into the OPEC.

But the pressure on the oil market was to increase in 1971, when the US government lifted the tariff on imported oil. Until then, it had been US policy to encourage domestic production, but with demand for oil continuously rising, the tariff was seen as a drain on the economy. After the tariff was removed, US production dropped off, since US oil was no longer as profitable as under the previous condition of artificially increased domestic prices. Instead, cheap oil began to flood the US market and within two years US imports had more than doubled.

²⁵² Stobaugh & Yergin, p. 21

²⁵³ Stobaugh & Yergin, p. 23

Figure 44 - US Oil Production 1945 – 2005²⁵⁴

Figure 45 - U.S. Oil Imports 1970 - 2007²⁵⁵

For Europe, the situation was similar. Oil imports had been steadily rising since the end of the war, and by 1973, the EU15 alone imported almost 600 million tonnes annually, while domestic production was almost nonexistent.

²⁵⁴ U.S. Energy Information Agency, data accessed in March 2008

²⁵⁵ Ibid.

Figure 46 – EU 15 Oil Imports 1965 - 2006²⁵⁶

To understand the events of 1973, it is necessary to visualize the dynamics of the oil market that was developing beneath the surface of rising demand at stable prices:

Figure 47 - Shadow Price Model²⁵⁷

“In period 1 [before 1973], starting from the equilibrium point A, a shift in demand for oil as a result of expansionary monetary policy raises the shadow price for oil. The new market clearing price at point B, however, is never realized, because the price of oil is effectively fixed by long-term contracts [due to the market power

²⁵⁶ BP, 2007

²⁵⁷ Barsky & Killian

of the Western oil majors]. Instead, we move from A to C, corresponding to an increase in the quantity of oil supplied at the old price.”²⁵⁸

But the politics of the time would soon bring an end to this unsustainable situation: Israel and the Arab countries had gone to war three times already, in 1948, in 1956 and in 1967. Each time, much to the frustration of the Arab states, the Western powers had supported Israel. But with the rising importance of oil in the economies of the West, the Arab states began to consider the possibility of using energy as a weapon. However, while in both the 1956 and 1967 war Arab governments had considered an oil embargo against the West, they proved incapable of enforcing it.

However, oil supplies were briefly interrupted by military actions and direct sabotage during the 1956 war, resulting in short-term disruptions of oil supplies through the Suez Canal as well as the sabotage of the Iraq Petroleum Company pipeline, while the Saudis closed a major pipeline supplying the refineries in Bahrain.²⁵⁹ These interruptions “forced most Western European countries to ration petroleum,”²⁶⁰ as supplies were reduced by almost 2 million barrels/day – equivalent to almost two-thirds of total European imports. Curiously, the impact on the European Economies was minimal, barely affecting GDP and having almost no impact on inflation.

The loss of the Suez Canal also reduced the flow of non-petroleum trade, since the Suez route linked the European economies with that of the Far East²⁶¹. However, “In the end the repercussions of the Suez Oil Crisis were less drastic than they were at the time expected to be,”²⁶² and most European policy makers quickly stopped worrying about the importance of the Middle East for Europe’s economies.

²⁵⁸ Brasky & Kilian

²⁵⁹ Daoudi & Dajani, p. 19; ironically, the pipeline was supposed to have been empty since the Arab-Israeli war of 1948.

²⁶⁰ *Ibid.* p. 19;

²⁶¹ *Ibid.*, p. 24

²⁶² *Ibid.*, p. 24, quoting P. H. Frankel

The 1967 war triggered another round of Arab leaders discussing an oil embargo against the West, but its impact was arguably even weaker than in 1956. Western oil companies, in response to the 1956 crisis, had invested heavily in additional tanker capacity that made it possible to transport additional oil from other regions to Europe, while avoiding the Suez Canal²⁶³. The Canal itself had also become less important as a major seaway, and other countries – particularly the Soviet Union and non-Arab OPEC members – were able of making up for the decline of Middle Eastern production.²⁶⁴ And finally, solidarity among Arab countries was very weak – the heated rhetoric failed to translate into effective long-term policy.

But in addition to the political reasons that led to the failure of the attempted 1967 embargo, the macro-economic situation was considerably different from that only six years later, when the Yom Kippur war resulted in the third – and finally successful – attempt by Arab countries to punish the West by reducing production and increasing prices. In 1967, the global price inflation that would finally cumulate in the stagflation of the 1970s was just in its earliest phase. The difference between prices for non-oil commodities and oil was relatively small, and while demand had been rising dramatically since the 1950s, the ability of oil producing countries to manipulate the market was still small, thanks to the still existing extensive supply flexibility of other producers.

But by 1973, the situation was dramatically different: global inflation had reached levels far above any level reached previously throughout the post-war period, commodity prices had shot up to record levels, and demand had pushed the production capacity of the global oil industry to its limits. Finally, the Arab countries – and not OPEC – were able to break the grip-lock Western oil companies have had on them since the beginning of the petroleum era.

“In period 2, OPEC reneges on the contractual price, and raises the oil price to

²⁶³ *Ibid.*, p. 48

²⁶⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 48

the market clearing level $D=B$ while reducing the quantity supplied (which is no longer needed at the new price). The price and quantity movements have the appearance of an oil supply shock, yet the supply curve never shifts; we are witnessing the correction of a disequilibrium resulting from the earlier demand shift.”²⁶⁵

Soon after, the global economy began to enter a recession. Since the onset of the recession followed almost immediately after the oil embargo and price increase for oil, most analysts and politicians became convinced that the oil crisis was the reason – with serious implications for subsequent energy policies.

This analysis of the 1973-74 and 1979-80 crisis indicate that the conventional narrative of the oil crisis and subsequent economic downturn is probably incorrect. The inability of the Arab nations to institute an effective embargo and increase prices for oil in 1956 and 1967 – should not only be attributed to political factors, but must be seen in the grander context of global economics. Franz Wirl argues that at least “some of the past oil price jumps that are typically linked to political events ... only coincide with them but have been driven ultimately by economic considerations (such as in 1973).”²⁶⁶

Paul Segal concludes that

“the most important route through which oil prices affect output is monetary policy: when oil prices pass through to core inflation, monetary authorities raise interest rates, slowing growth. ... [T]he direct effect of high oil prices on output is

²⁶⁵ Brasky & Kilian

²⁶⁶ Wirl, Franz “Why do oil prices jump (or fall)?, *Energy Policy*, 36 (2008), p. 1029 - 1043

relatively small and ... the microeconomic mechanisms proposed in the literature are insufficient to explain the historical impact of oil prices.”²⁶⁷

and:

“[H]igh oil prices have had no perceptible impact on the macro economy over the last few years, and ... in the data oil prices already stopped having an impact sometime in the 1980s.”²⁶⁸

Based on my own analysis of the data, I have to agree with Segal that “the microeconomic mechanisms, while plausible in their own right, probably were not able to explain the magnitude of the estimated impact of the oil prices on the macro economy through the 1970s and early 1980s, and that monetary policy was the more promising explanation.”²⁶⁹

The question whether or not the high oil prices had a significant impact on the economy of the 1970s and 1980s is not simply an interesting theoretical issue. Whether or not supply shocks and/or high oil prices *by themselves* are capable of negatively impacting the economic well-being of the affected countries has very important policy implications. The current debate about energy security is very much informed by the conventional wisdom of the supply-shock induced economic crises of the 1970s and 1980s, and as we will see in the discussion below, most – if not all – energy security policies are based on the implications of this probably erroneous assumption. What is regularly ignored by policy makers is the critical fact that both the energy crises of the 1970s and the subsequent economic crises were the result of long-term government policy mismanagement. It may be politically convenient to portray the West as the victim of sinister political forces outside its control, but it would be by far more constructive to recognise and deal with the importance of monetary policy on the long-term health of the economy.

²⁶⁷ Segal, Paul “Why do oil price shocks no longer shock?”, 2007, p. 1

²⁶⁸ Segal, Paul, p. 22

²⁶⁹ Segal, Paul, p. 22

5.2. Demand management

At the same time that the US was trying to deal with the crisis through rationing, price controls, import taxes, and other heavy handed measures, European countries adopted very different approaches. A Newsweek article of February 17, 1975 reported that

“the Bonn government is really not doing anything to conserve energy – and this approach seems to be working. Actually, Germany decided early in the game to rely on the law of supply and demand to cut fuel consumption. Sure enough, when the prizes of gas and oil began soaring, demand dropped. As a result, German energy consumption last year fell 10 percent, while gasoline and heating oil – now in plentiful supply in Germany – remain the lowest-price in Europe.”²⁷⁰

The article goes on to quote Dr. Dieter Schmidt of the Energy Institute in Cologne as saying “I don't think there can be much argument about the meaning of these statistics ... In general, it's best to let the market take its course.”²⁷¹

Unlike the US, Germany did not experience gasoline shortages – consumers with less urgent need for gasoline consumed less, while those with greater need consumed the same amount as before at a higher price. Still, the economies of both countries – and of all other economies dependent on imported oil – suffered from the crisis. It is simply not possible to eliminate the impact of a supply shock on the economy – regardless whether it is through increased prices or an actual physical reduction in supplies. In either case, prices increase, consumption decreases, and the economy suffers through reduced productivity and reduced output.

²⁷⁰ Milton R. Benjamin and Malcolm MacPherson, Newsweek, February 17, 1975 “Energy: what other nations are doing”, p. 28

²⁷¹ Benjamin and MacPherson, *ibid.*

A few days later, the Economist published an article, in which it derided as “tactless” the American plan to impose “up to \$3 a barrel ... duties on imported oil at the very moment when they are demanding that oil producers cut their prices by – coincidentally – a very similar amount, on the grounds that high energy prices are ruining the American and other industrialised economies.”²⁷²

According to the Administration's own calculations, the measure would have “cut auto sales 35%, reduce[d] GNP by \$13 billion a year and add[ed] 'several hundred thousand' unemployed. And because of the high prices on the white market, energy planners predict[ed] that the CPI would [have soared] 2.5 percentage points.”²⁷³ The irony – if one may call it that – is that each of these measures might have been appropriate in a situation where the supply of oil was entirely cut off. Rationing during war, for example, can be sensible when fuel is needed for the front and consumers simply have to do without, since the alternative is tanks and troop transports running out of fuel, resulting in the country eventually being overrun by the enemy. But the US – or Europe – did not face any mortal danger during the embargo: the Arab countries had not, after all, stopped producing oil. They had increased prices and embargoed the US, but they were unable to stop reselling oil to the US by other customers – and were utterly powerless to stop increasing production by other countries.

However, there is good evidence that they actually worsened rather than mitigate the effects of the crises. In the first place, as Montgomery, Baron, and Weiskopf point out, the OPEC “embargo did not deprive the United States of supplies.”²⁷⁴ As can be seen in the graph above, supplies did not decline until 1975 – largely because demand had declined. What happened in 1973 was that the OPEC cartel succeeded in increasing the price of oil – without significantly reducing the rate of

²⁷² “Kissinger's Wedge”, *The Economist*, February 15, 1975, p. 82

²⁷³ Parisi and Shepard, *ibid.*

²⁷⁴ Montgomery, Baron, and Weiskopf, 2007

production – and simultaneously attempted to stop supplies to the United States. However, OPEC had no technical or legal means to stop anybody from selling oil to the United States. The gasoline supply shortages were therefore strictly the result of price and allocation controls that “created chaos” and “gasoline lines formed in many areas while others were oversupplied with fuel.”²⁷⁵

Had there been no price controls or other government interferences in the market, many of the negative effects of the oil crises in 1973-74 and 1979-1980 could have been avoided:

A competitive market responds to a supply interruption by allocating the limited available supplies to their most highly valued uses through price increases. In an open competitive market, users for whom the scarce supply has the highest value are willing to pay the most. The market price is bid up until consumers who place a lower value on using gasoline than the market price drop out, and prices rise until demand is driven down to a level equal to available supply. The market price then will equal the lowest valued use that can be satisfied with the quantity of supply available. Those who value it less buy none. All consumers who place a higher value on continued use of the product pay the market price, and gain a “consumer’s surplus” equal to the difference between the value they put on the product and its market price.²⁷⁶

This understanding differs sharply from the official policy of the IEA, which argues that “although supply shortages may bring about rising prices ... these [rising prices] can be caused by other factors”²⁷⁷ - a statement that makes little if any economic sense. Prices, as we have seen, reflect the relationship between supply and demand for a particular product. Economically there is no

²⁷⁵ Ibid.

²⁷⁶ Ibid.

²⁷⁷ IEA booklet, 2007, p. 3

difference between an increase in demand at stable supply, and a decrease in supply at stable demand. In either case, more people are willing to pay a higher price for the same volume of goods than before. Which is no different from saying that some people will not be able to buy the same volume of product with the same amount of money as before? From the consumers' point of view there is no difference between a reduction in supply and an increase in demand. It therefore makes little economic sense for the IEA to argue that “the goal of the response action is to offset an actual physical shortage, not react to price movements.”²⁷⁸

It is quite reasonable to assume that the IEA measures – particularly the strategic stockpiles – are likely to aggravate any supply shock crises: when the supply crisis begins, prices for fuel will increase – automatically reducing demand, that is: consumption. The IEA notes correctly that “the transportation sector accounts for roughly 55% of total consumption [of oil] in IEA member countries”²⁷⁹, and that consumption in this sector is the easiest to reduce. But the measures the IEA proposes require a significant degree of voluntary action on behalf of the population, motivated not by a desire to save money – as it would be if the price of oil was allowed to increase rapidly – but by a desire to help the economy as a whole.²⁸⁰

Each of these measures have a significant impact on the economy: making public transport available for free would likely increase ridership, but it would also reduce the amount of public transport available to each individual: the more people use a bus, train, or subway, the longer it takes to board and unboard, the less room is available on the system – particularly during peak hours – which would result in significant delays and other inconveniences for passengers. It is also questionable that many drivers would voluntarily switch to public transport simply because it is free.

²⁷⁸ Ibid.

²⁷⁹ Ibid.

²⁸⁰ There is a certain absurdity to this idea, and it clearly contradicts one of the key ideas of current economic thinking, namely that ‘public goods’ cannot be provided by private citizens due to the ‘free rider’ problem.

It is also hard to imagine how car-pooling could become a rapid response to oil shortages in the absence of a significant rise in prices for gasoline. Public transit and car-pooling tends to be much cheaper than private transportation under normal circumstances – but using either is in many cases a lifestyle choice for those who have the financial resources to choose between private transport, carpooling, and public transit. Similar questions can be asked about telecommuting – which requires employers and employees to have already established the procedures necessary for working from home – as well as the 'compressed four-day work week' – which would probably result in serious disruptions of services and business in general.

What seems to elude the designers of the IEA program is that there is effectively no difference between consumers not having access to fuel and consumers acting as if they had no access to fuel. By asking consumers and industry to not use fuel that is in fact available, the economy will be affected to the same degree as if the fuel was not available. If the goal of energy security is to ensure “the uninterrupted physical availability of energy products on the market, at a price which is affordable for all consumers (private and industrial),”²⁸¹ then each of the programs proposed by the IEA during an energy *supply shock* seems to be designed to further *reduce* energy security by limiting the supply of energy even more, and increasing the price level above what is necessary.

Demand management, as practiced by the US and France and now part of the EIA emergency response system, may succeed in reducing demand, but it cannot cushion the economic impact of the supply shock. If less money is spend on fuel, more money will be spend on other goods and services, which in turn will increase the demand for the resources – including energy – necessary to produce these goods and services. If the manufacturers and service providers of the alternative goods and services could be persuaded to reduce their demands for energy as well, the supply of

²⁸¹ European Commission 2001 Green Paper on Energy Supply Security

goods to the economy as a whole would be reduced, which in turn would lead to a price increase throughout the economy. It is therefore not possible to avoid the economic problems associated with a supply shock in the short run. One way or the other, if the supply shock is serious enough, it will result in reduced consumption while simultaneously decreasing production and increasing prices for fuel.

Economic theory – and the practical example of Germany during the energy crisis – shows that demand management is not capable of achieving a better outcome than the market mechanism if the goal is to minimize the economic repercussions of a supply shock. Of course, if the goal is to reallocate supplies from what sector of society to another regardless of economic costs – as, for example, under conditions of war – then the market mechanism will prove inadequate and administrative steps must necessarily be taken. However, for this it would not be necessary to create the IEA – imposing a state of emergency and martial law would accomplish the same goal much more effectively.

5.3. Strategic Petroleum Reserves/Emergency Stocks

Ironically, the crisis of 1973-74 and 1979-80 had not, in fact, been a crisis of supply, but of price.²⁸² The local shortages of gasoline may have created a different impression on the general public, but as already discussed – the shortages were the result of misguided and dysfunctional government policies, particularly in the U.S. The stockpiles, therefore, were created to address a problem that did not at that time exist – and has not, throughout the history of the oil age, ever existed for any country not engaged in large-scale warfare. It may therefore be rather interesting to calculate the amount of money the IEA system costs taxpayers every year to deal with a problem that, while possible, is not very likely to exist during peace time.

²⁸² Stobaugh & Yergin, p. 27

In 2006, the US public stocks alone contained approximately 688,605,000 barrels ²⁸³of crude. Since the average price of oil in 2006 had been \$65.14,²⁸⁴ the value of the U.S. SPRs can be estimated at \$44.8 billion. The 60 million barrels made available by the entire IEA system during the Katrina crisis represented about 8.7 percent of the total volume of US public stock. Since in April 2006, total OECD stocks were the equivalent of 1.005 billion barrels²⁸⁵, the total draw on IEA stocks was 6 percent of the total reserves.

In the U.S, this was only the fifth time that significant amount of oil had been drawn from the public stocks, while it was only the second time that the IEA system as a whole had been put into use. However, since its creation in 1977, the U.S. stocks contained on average 481.6 million barrels of oil, with an average annual value of \$17 billion. To appreciate the total cost of these stocks over time, one can estimate the opportunity cost of their maintenance by calculating how much interest could have been earned if instead of using money to fill the stocks, the same amount would have been invested. For the purpose of this calculation, I have taken the interest rate of 2-year US treasury bills as benchmark.²⁸⁶

To calculate the so-called ‘management’ costs, I have calculated for each year since 1977 how much money the government would have earned if instead of buying oil stocks it had instead invested the money at the rate of each year’s 2-year t-bill rate. In years the government drew on the stocks, I have calculated how much it would have cost the government if instead of taking its own stock, it would have borrowed money at the rate of 2-year t-bills in order to buy oil supplies on the

²⁸³ Data from EIA website

²⁸⁴ BP Statistical Review of World Energy, 2007

²⁸⁵ AFX News Agency, June 13, 2006.

²⁸⁶ Thanks to Dr. Robert P. Murphy for suggesting T-Bills.

open market.²⁸⁷ These calculations do not include the cost of building and maintaining the stocks – merely the management cost.

Graphically, the result of this calculation can be presented in the following manner:

Figure 48 – U.S. SPR Management Costs ²⁸⁸

The total opportunity cost to the U.S. economy from the public stocks since 1977 was therefore \$123.787 billion. Or to put it differently: only if oil prices had risen to \$246/barrel in 2006 would the value of 2006 strategic reserves have been equivalent to the value of the fictitious investment portfolio based on 2-year T-bill rates since 1977.

²⁸⁷ Since 1977, there was at no time a shortage of actual supplies – the largest decline in production was in 1991, when as a result of the Gulf War, there was a .28 percent in global production, while there was no global production reduction at all in 2005. On the other hand, in 1982 and 1983, global production fell by 3.76 percent and 1.22 percent respectively, with little notice by the global economy which was still stuck in the recession, as energy prices fell from \$79.93/bbl in 1980 to \$59.99/bbl in 1982 and global consumption declining as well.

²⁸⁸ Source: BP, 2006; EIA, 2008; FED, 2008; calculations by author.

The few times stocks have been drawn to supply the economy with additional sources, there had not in fact been any significant global production shortages of crude. Since the purpose of supplying oil to the economy is to prevent a price increase throughout the economy as a result of reduced supplies, it has to be considered whether the expenditure on the stockpiles has been commensurate with their economic benefit. If instead of the strategic stockpiles, OECD governments would maintain a strategic energy fund in which they invested annually at a steady rate, it could be argued that this would possibly achieve the same benefit for the economy as the strategic stockpiles.

In a situation in which the world would in fact face a dramatic and sustained reduction of energy supplies, the benefit of the strategic stockpiles is going to be marginal. A study conducted by the Clingendael International Energy Program in 2004 found that

“[i]n a situation of turmoil in the Persian Gulf region most policy tools will be ineffective. Security of oil supply is very seriously threatened in such a situation and the supply gap will most likely be very large and acute. Depending on the duration of a Persian Gulf supply disruption, more radical instruments in energy policy are required, because strategic stocks only give short term relief and the ability to fill the supply gap with oil from elsewhere will be limited on short notice.”²⁸⁹

During periods of local disruptions, the world energy market has shown time and again to be very resilient and capable of supplying large quantities of crude and petroleum products to affected markets – at a premium, of course.²⁹⁰

²⁸⁹ Clingendael Report, p. 57

²⁹⁰ Robert Bradley & Thomas Tanton, “U.S. Petroleum: Let the Market Function”, Dec 19, 2005

Since the stocks held by the private US oil industry alone would have been sufficient to meet the needs of the 2005 IEA measures, the IEA government reserves arguably contributed little to the energy security of the IEA member countries in physical terms. If the costs of the reserves are taken into consideration, it can legitimately be argued that the IEA reserves reduce the economic welfare of IEA countries.

It is therefore far from clear whether the IEA system does actually contribute to the ability of the IEA member countries to mitigate the negative economic impact from a supply shock. If reduction of consumption is the main goal, then a sharp increase in prices for oil and oil products is the probably most effective means of achieving this. If the IEA system is meant to reduce the negative economic impact of a supply shock, it is not clear how it can achieve this.

Based on both theoretical and empirical consideration, I argue that during peace time, governments should not worry about the disruptive effects of a supply crisis. More often than not, markets have proven to be capable of addressing short-term, localized disruptions by redirecting energy flows to where they are needed at making them available at a price that satisfies all demand. Intervention into the market is likely to make bad situations worse, not better.

So far, I have argued that neither demand management nor strategic stocks of fuel are adequate strategies to deal with the problem of energy security. Demand management and strategic stocks are at best short-term solutions to very short-term and local problems – and it is debatable if the costs associated with these measures are worth their benefits. The management of demand during times of supply insecurity can be effectively accomplished via the market mechanism, which would price fuel in such a way that its consumption would be reduced appropriately. Since governments and business are both equally likely to properly assess the duration of an energy crisis – and are both equally likely to fail in doing so correctly – there is little reason to believe that the government is

going to adopt measures that would restructure demand more effectively than it could be achieved through the market mechanism. However, neither government nor industry will be able to reduce the economic impact of an actual physical supply crisis on the economy. Government may be able to direct the costs of an energy crisis in a politically beneficial manner, but this does not reduce damage, merely distributes it differently. However, as experience during the energy crises of the 1970s and 1980s, as well as 2005, have shown, government intervention to reassign economic damage by instituting price controls, quotas, driving bans, and other interventionist measures are likely to aggravate the economic damage from supply crises.

In the long run, diversity of energy supplies – both in terms of geographic sources and types of fuel – are the only way to achieve the goal of reducing as much as possible to cost of energy to the economy as a whole, and limiting the impact of supply disruptions. Even though the energy crisis of the 1970s did not cause the subsequent economic crisis, the rapid increase in energy prices was an economic cost that both consumers and industry would have preferred not to bear. From an economic point of view, low prices for factors of production are preferable over high prices, and predictable prices are preferable over unpredictable prices. Energy supply security should be geared towards achieving a reduction of energy prices in the long run, while limiting the risk of supply disruptions.

The need to diversify energy supplies has been addressed numerous times by different levels of government in Europe since the energy crisis of 1973. It is in fact one of the key elements of the IEA strategy, while in a 1995 White Paper on general energy policy, the European Commission

listed diversification of energy supplies as one of the key strategies to ensure the security of energy supplies.²⁹¹

4.5 Competition Policy and of Energy Supply Security

The idea that unbundling and third party access will increase energy supply security has become a core policy of the European Commission. In accordance with the standard economic theory, Nelli Kroes, the current EU Commissioner for competition, argues that it will “deliver more investment; protect the EU against any potential dominance from external suppliers; and improve security of supply [and] lead to more competitive prices.”²⁹² Judging by the documents prepared by the Commission, there is no question about positive relationship between competition, unbundling, third party access, and energy security.

However, this may not entirely be the case. In its 1995 White Paper, the Commission indicated that competitiveness and energy security may in fact be contradictory goals: “... energy policy must pursue aims that reconcile competitiveness, security of supplies ... while bearing in mind that the Union’s central concerns are ... job creation and the quest for greater efficiency...”²⁹³

A number of industry analysts and researchers have also argued that that TPA and energy supply security may be contradictory goals: “Which network operator would voluntarily invest in networks and facilities if he can expect that he must divest them (under duress) in the near future? The EU Commission has so far not answered the question which advantages are to be expected from splitting the network.”²⁹⁴ And while German energy analyst, Claudia Kemfert, “praises that the

²⁹¹ White Paper, p. 23

²⁹² Neelie Kroes; “More competition and greater energy security in the Single European Market for electricity and gas”, speech on 30 March 2007 in Berlin, accessed at <http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/07/212&format=DOC&aged=1&language=EN&guiLanguage=en>; accessed on March 20, 2007

²⁹³ As implied by the 1995 Commission White Paper “An Energy Policy for the European Union”, p. 3

²⁹⁴ Harry Roels, “Der Mythos Entflechtung,” Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung, February 24, 2008

EU wants to create more competition in the energy market... [she] doubts that it is the right way to take the networks away from the [energy] concerns. ... Unbundling is not a cure-all for more competition – it can even result in the opposite.”²⁹⁵

In its 2000 study on energy market reform in the European Union, the IEA cautions that while the “starting point for reform is third party access to the transport network ... it also needs to be organized so as not to deter potential investment in new supply projects and infrastructure.”²⁹⁶ Rather than mandating TPA in all cases, the study suggests that “the choice between negotiated and regulated TPA is a matter of finding the best balance between competition and security of supply,”²⁹⁷ and continues that “the advantage of negotiated TPA is that it leaves gas companies with more scope for commercial strategic use of their infrastructures and with some autonomy vis-a-vis large producers.”²⁹⁸

The important point is not that negotiated TPA would benefit the owners of infrastructure – this is in accordance with the general economic principles outlined above – but that the IEA sees this as an advantage. It should give pause that an organization dedicated exclusively to the maintenance of energy supply security should consider the ability to exercise market power as beneficial for energy supply security when the EU Commission insists that only TPA can ensure long-term energy supply security.

This apparent contradiction becomes even more notable when the IEA explains the advantages of voluntary TPA in the short run. According to the IEA, negotiated TPA – that is, TPA that

²⁹⁵ Wissenschaftler streiten über Königsweg: die Vorschläge der EU zur Entflechtung der Energiewirtschaft stoßen auf ein geteiltes Echo,” Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung, September 20, 2007

²⁹⁶ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 14

²⁹⁷ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 14

²⁹⁸ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 14

network operators grant voluntarily because it meets their own commercial objectives – has the additional advantage that

“The supply situation is likely to remain more transparent. There will come more scope for supply diversification, the building and use of additional interconnections and the contracting of back-up agreements in case of a supply failure by a given party. This may be important in order to maintain a European industry willing and able to maintain a high level of short-term reliability and to invest in further development.”²⁹⁹

Curiously, in the 2000 EU Green Paper on energy supply security, the European Commission explicitly states that in terms of supply disruptions it “is only concerned with temporary disruptions insofar as they are a sign of structural supply difficulties on a Community scale.”³⁰⁰ At the same time, the Commission advocates unbundling and TPA as means for addressing exactly these structural difficulties.

However, the argument of the IEA that voluntary can be better for supply security than mandated TPA addresses the same time frame: the earlier discussed disadvantages of monopolies – such as the creation of over-capacity – may actually be good for energy supply security because they provide the energy supply system with the necessary security margin.

The IEA goes even further and argues that mandatory TPA access – the preferred option of the EU – “may **undermine** security of supply. If price becomes the overriding factor in the consumer’s choice of a supplier, consumers may not be prepared for more expensive gas in a diversified supply portfolio.”³⁰¹ In 2007, however, European competition commissioner Neelie Kroes argued the exact opposite by saying that “the absence of ownership unbundling had ‘suppressed investment in

²⁹⁹ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 14

³⁰⁰ Green Paper, p. 65

³⁰¹ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 14 - 15

interconnection capacity and in network capacity, threatening both competition and security of supply.”³⁰²

Certainly, the IEA does not argue that under regulated TPA, supply security cannot be addressed at all, but it points out that this would require “imposing responsibilities on transport providers and gas suppliers. ... Guarantees relative to supply could be required, including reserve stocks in storage, back-up contracts or a diversified gas portfolio.”³⁰³ However, “too many onerous conditions on gas suppliers could deter the entry of new players and the development of sizeable hubs and spot markets and short-term commodity and capacity trade (key to a competitive and liquid market) could be slow to develop.”³⁰⁴

And to complicate matters even more, the European Commission has even adopted rules that seem to acknowledge the contradiction the Commission's focus on unbundling and mandatory TPA and its policy goal of creating secure energy supplies. In 2004 the Commission created a set of rules that can exempt some facilities from mandatory TPA, particularly those that are considered “major high risk” infrastructures, such as LNG terminals, but also others. Criteria for such exemptions are that, among others,

“the investment must enhance competition in electricity (gas) supply and enhance security of supply (gas only); the level of investment is such that the investment would not take place unless the exemption is granted...”³⁰⁵

What this amounts to is the admission that monopolistic competition is not always bad for the consumer. By granting exemptions to TPA rules, the European Commission admits that there may

³⁰² “Energy: Back unbundling, Kroes tells users”, Utility Week, July 6, 2007

³⁰³ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 15

³⁰⁴ OECD/IEA “Regulatory Reform: European Gas, 2000, p. 15

³⁰⁵ Note of DG Energy & Transport on Directives 2003/45-55 and Regulation 1228\03 in the Electricity and Gas Internal Market – Exemptions from certain provisions of the third party access regime”

be advantages to monopoly in the energy sector – very much in contradiction of the standard economic theory on which much of contemporary regulation in the EU and elsewhere is based.

Based on these contradictory positions on what is necessary to ensure energy security, it is not surprising that many analysts have come to the conclusion that energy supply security and free competition are indeed conflicting policy goals, particularly since energy security is often defined as a ‘public good’ that can by definition not be provided by the free market.

However, I will try to argue that the apparent contradiction between energy supply security and the ‘free market’ is based on a misunderstanding – in particular a misunderstanding about the nature of competition and monopoly. Much of this misunderstanding can be traced back to the standard economic theory of competition and monopoly outlined earlier in this paper, particularly the model of ‘perfect competition’.

The most striking short-coming of the model appears to be its set of highly unrealistic assumptions, particularly that of ‘perfect knowledge’. It is simply inconceivable how anybody could have perfect knowledge of all aspects of the market at any given time. The human condition is more often marked by ignorance than knowledge, and to therefore build a model on an assumption that can never be met should strike anybody as questionable at best. If everybody has perfect knowledge of the market, than everybody would know the best way of doing whatever needs to be done, would be fully aware of all possible gains of trade, and also know exactly what everybody else is doing.

As a result, “perfect competition denotes ... the situation in which every market participant does exactly what everyone else is doing, in which it is utterly pointless to try something in any way better than what is already being done by others, and in which, in fact, it is not necessary to keep one’s eyes

open to what others are doing at all. It is the state ‘of placid acceptance of the market’s verdict concerning price.’³⁰⁶

This, however, appears to be in considerable contrast to what Kirzner describes as the ‘layman’s’ understanding of competition, which is “the notion of men vigorously competing with another, each striving to deliver a performance that outdistances his rivals. The essence of the idea is the awareness of what one’s rivals are doing and the conscious effort to do something different and better.”³⁰⁷

But to do something differently and better requires that not everything is known, and that there remain better ways of doing business yet undiscovered – which would satisfy commonsense, but does contradict the model of perfect competition.

But while the standard model would treat this ignorance as a problem, Kirzner sees it as the necessary element of market competition. If all market participants really did have perfect knowledge, “the market process must immediately cease. Without autonomous change in tastes, or in technological possibilities, or in the availability of resources, no one can have any interest in altering his plans for the succeeding periods. The market is in equilibrium; the pattern of market activity will continue without change period after period.”³⁰⁸

Clearly, however, this is not the case. The world is in a continuous state of change, each aspect of which affects the state of the economy: weather patterns, human relationships, technology, tastes. There are random events, some disastrous, others beneficial. Diseases kill people well in advance of their natural life span. Most people have very little knowledge of each of these events, even if they happen in their immediate proximity - and even fewer are able to always correctly anticipate their

³⁰⁶ Kirzner, p. 90

³⁰⁷ Kirzner, p. 89

³⁰⁸ Kirzner, p. 11

consequences. However, the idea of perfect competition is explicitly build on the assumption of no change. In short, the assumption of perfect knowledge in the standard economic model is not just ideal – it is impossible. Consequently, on these grounds alone, there can be no perfect competition, and hence, there can be no equilibrium.

Kirzner therefore argues that “the market process ... is set in motion by the results of initial market-ignorance by participants,”³⁰⁹ who constantly have to readjust their behaviour in light of new information from either their failure or successes. “Even without changes in the basic data of the market (i.e. consumer tastes, technological possibilities, and resource availabilities), the decisions in one period of time, this series of systematic changes in the interconnected network of market decisions constitute the market process.”³¹⁰

Ignorance and change rather than perfect knowledge and optimal outcome are what define the market, and for this reason alone – the assumption of perfect knowledge – the standard perfect competition model has to be considered unrealistic.

Another assumption of the perfect competition model is that products are homogenous. To some degree, the argument by Lerner on the issue of substitution already addressed this – products are not purchased for their physical properties, but for the function they fulfil. To seek homogeneity in physical properties creates definitional problems that are impossible to solve: “What constitutes a homogeneous commodity” (i.e., an industry)—neckties, bow ties, bow ties with polka dots, etc., or bow ties made by Jones?”³¹¹ asks Rothbard, and provides the answer that “Only consumers will decide, and they, as different consumers, will be likely to decide differently in each concrete case.”³¹²

³⁰⁹ Kirzner, p. 10

³¹⁰ Kirzner, p. 10

³¹¹ Rothbard, p. 667

³¹² Ibid.

The point may appear trivial, but in the context of this discussion, it is far from trivial: if the range of attributes that make up the homogeneity of a product cannot be rationally decided, then it makes little if any sense to include this criterion in the definition of perfect competition. If there are no homogeneous products, than if perfect competition rests on their existence, perfect competition can logically not exist.

This also has important implications for the idea of economies of scale: if perfect competition rests on the assumption that economies to scale are small relative to the size of the market, then it is possible to define almost any market sufficiently small to prove that it exhibits significant economies of scale. What matters is only a sufficiently narrow definition of the product one wishes to discuss. Again, I refer to the discussion of Lerner above which indicates that defining products by their physical attributes provides little, if any, analytical value.

But according to Walter Block, the most significant problem of the perfect equilibrium model is not only that it is unrealistic, but that it gives rise to the concept of imperfect competition or market failure.³¹³ Since the real world economy does not, and cannot, correspond to the idealized model of the perfect competition model, economists wrongly conclude that they are dealing with market failure where there is in reality only a normal, continuous market process.

“The argument, shorn of all technicalities, goes something like this,” writes Block: “the free market is imperfect; it misallocates resources ... on the assumption that the proper allocation of resources is the goal ... government involvement in the economy ... is called for,”³¹⁴ which is almost verbatim what Church & Ware argue when they say that “markets, left to themselves, do not exhaust all of the gains from trade and total surplus is not maximized. As a result, potential Pareto

³¹³ Walter Block, “Value Freedom in Economics”

³¹⁴ Walter Block.

improvements are possible: the winners from regulatory intervention could compensate the losers and still be winners.”³¹⁵

But this, according to Block, is not a technical but an ethical argument: “[T]he ease with which it [the argument for regulation] can be attacked on logical grounds gives evidence ... that what is really lurking behind this supposed economic argument is ... an ethical predisposition.”³¹⁶ The ethical predisposition Block is referring to can be understood as confusion between what the market does and what the market should do, and which is reflected in a common interpretation of Adam Smith according to which Smith “conjectured that competitive markets were desirable because the outcomes associated with them were socially optimal.”³¹⁷ But it should be pointed out that Smith’s argument was subtly different: the welfare of society was the unintended outcome of individually selfish behaviour free from any government interference.

Smith based his argument for leaving the market alone on his realization that the government is incapable of managing the economy properly, not that the market is perfect or that the market will bring about an ideal situation:

“What is the species of domestic industry which his capital can employ, and of which the produce is likely to be of the greatest value, every individual, it is evident, can in his local situation judge much better than any statesman or lawgiver can do for him. The statesman, who should attempt to direct private people in what manner they ought to employ their capitals, would not only load himself with a most unnecessary attention, but assume an authority which could safely be trusted, not only to no single person, but to no council or senate whatever, and

³¹⁵ Church & Ware, p. 750

³¹⁶ Block

³¹⁷ Church & Ware, p. 25

which would nowhere be so dangerous as in the hands of a man who had folly and presumption enough to fancy himself fit to exercise it.”

Though current market theories and policies are based on the assumption that markets require the interference of the government because they fail to do achieve efficiency on their own, and often experience market failure, “it is not at all difficult to condemn any real-world markets, monopoly or otherwise, that necessarily emerges in an imperfect world to solve pressing real-world problems, if the criterion is perfection.”³¹⁸ It is probably just as reasonable to argue that while markets may in fact be inefficient there is no guarantee that the intervention of the government will necessarily make them work any better. In fact, it can be argued that whatever inefficiencies there may exist in the unregulated market, government intervention is more likely to add to the problem rather than solve it: after all, the original argument by Adam Smith in favour of the market was based on the realization that government management of the economy will always result in an outcome that is worse than the market.

The standard perfect competition model and its use in assessing whether or not a particular market has failed and requires the intervention of the government to be corrected suffers from more than simply unrealistic assumptions that will always result in the diagnosis of market failure: its analytical value is critically undermined by the fact that it fails to take into consideration the factor of time.

In his classic work “Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy,” Schumpeter argues that “since we are dealing with a process whose every element takes considerable time in revealing its true features and ultimate effects, there is no point in appraising the performance of that process *ex visu* of a given point in time; we must judge its performance over time, as it unfolds through decades or

³¹⁸ McKenzie & Lee, p. 25

centuries.”³¹⁹ Even Pindyck’s refinement of Lerner’s original measure of market power discussed above hardly seems fit to deal with these kinds of timeframes, and it is indeed difficult to see any evidence that any current anti-trust regulation applies standards that take into consideration timeframes beyond a few years – if at all.

But Schumpeter is not content with arguing that it is difficult to properly assess the importance of particular market inefficiency. Contrary to what is implied by the perfect competition model, he argues that inefficiencies are in fact not only unavoidable but desirable: “A system ... that at every given point of time fully utilizes its possibilities to the best advantage may yet in the long run be inferior to a system that does so at no given point of time, because the latter’s failure to do so may be a condition for the level or speed of long-run performance.”³²⁰

We have already encountered this argument in a similar form above when Kirzner argued that a perfectly competitive economic system would be static and undergo no endogenous change. In a perfectly competitive system, there would be no need for the type of individual mentioned already in this paper: the entrepreneur.

“The pure entrepreneur,” argues Kirzner,

“proceeds by his alertness to discover and exploit situations in which he is able to sell for high prices that which he can buy for low prices. Pure entrepreneurial profit is the difference between two sets of price. It is not yielded by exchanging something the entrepreneur values less for something he values more highly. It comes from discovering sellers and buyers of something for

³¹⁹ Schumpeter, p. 83

³²⁰ Schumpeter, p. 83

which the latter will pay more than the former demand. The discovery of a profit opportunity means the discovery of something obtainable for nothing at all.”³²¹

Under perfect competition, such exploits would not be possible, of course, since all sellers and buyers would already know how much they can charge and how much they must pay. Curiously, however, if one were to position the pure entrepreneur into the system of a perfectly competitive model, he would be considered a monopolist – since Kirzner defines him as being capable of operating at no cost, any profit he makes will result in an economic ‘inefficiency’: his marginal revenue is above marginal cost. He will also be interested in limiting the amount of the good that he makes available to buyers, while not buying too much from the seller, lest he destroy his ability to earn a profit.

What follows from this is a curious paradox: on the one hand, the pure entrepreneur is able to earn a monopoly profit, which can be shown to be inefficient. But nevertheless, both the buyers and sellers benefit from the activity of the entrepreneur: if he did not exist, buyers and sellers would both suffer. The entrepreneur's interest in exploiting market arbitrage opportunity results in an increased demand for the seller's product (the volume the entrepreneur is willing to purchase), while it simultaneously results in an increased supply for the buyer's demand (by the same volume). In the market of the supplier, the price for the good increases marginally, while in the market of the buyer, the price of the good decreases marginally. Both buyer and seller are better off as a result of the entrepreneur's activity – even though the entrepreneur has not invested anything and created no value whatsoever. While the actions of the entrepreneur may be inefficient – his absence would make the market even more inefficient.

³²¹ Kirzner, p. 48

According to standard economic theory, when the cost of regulation is lower than the monopoly profit of the monopolist, than it is justifiable to regulate the monopolist and deprive him of his monopoly profit. If it were possible for regulators to force the entrepreneur to forfeit any profit above marginal costs, without incurring costs that are greater than the monopoly profit, the entrepreneur would likely not be willing to engage in his activity. As a result, there would be no monopoly profit, and the economy overall would be worse off. Regulating against this kind of monopoly would therefore be damaging to the economy. Even if the monopolist were able to maintain his arbitrage advantage indefinitely, the economy would still be worse off without him – a possibility not accountable for in the standard model of perfect competition.

But if entrepreneurial profit can be welfare enhancing in cases where the entrepreneur does little more than engage in arbitrage, how much more welfare enhancing might it be if the entrepreneur instead develops new goods and services and invests in their provision? “The cost of inventive activity, which is frequently substantial, must be incurred before – often long before – any revenues can be realized.”³²² But “if the potential for monopoly market positions were totally wiped out by (perfectly) efficient antitrust prosecution, ... investors would ... be left with investment opportunities that yield normal profits ... with their actual average profits earned across an array of investments being less than the ... normal profits.”³²³ It stands to reason that the prospect of normal profits is likely to be a much weaker motivation for entrepreneurs than the possibility of earning a monopoly profit.

Not being able to earn a monopoly profit may even reduce the ability of entrepreneurs to engage in significant innovation at all:

³²² Posner, 1969

³²³ McKenzie, 2003

“If a competitive firm has reason to anticipate that innovation will yield a substantial profit it should be able to raise the required funds in the capital markets. Thus, if the prospects of innovation seem bright, both the monopolist and the competitive firm should be able to finance the necessary R&D, the former because it has, the latter because it has access to, the necessary resources.”³²⁴

Innovation does not necessarily mean the creation of a completely new product or service – innovation, just like products generally, has to be seen in the context of a specific market. A particular good or service may already exist in one market, but introducing it into another market where it does not yet exist is innovative, too.

It could be argued that the original inventor put much more effort into the product, and therefore deserves to be rewarded more than a simple copycat who does little more than introduce the product into another market. That is, however, a nonsensical argument: imagine a product invented by somebody as the result of a brilliant intuition over breakfast. In one fell swoop he visualizes the entire mechanism and thanks to his inordinate retentive brain and gift with pen and paper is able to sketch out the entire set of necessary blueprints in less than a day. He then goes ahead and markets this in his home market as a monopolist. The invention is then noted by a second person, who thinks it might sell well in another market. He buys a license from the inventor for a lot of money, and begins a painstaking process of market research and production development over many years until he is finally able to introduce the product in the new market. To deny the latter his monopoly profit while allowing the former would on account of their mental investment would clearly be absurd. But without the possibility of monopoly profit, the latter would likely not have engaged in the entrepreneurial activity to begin with, and the customers in the target market would arguably be worse off.

³²⁴ Posner, 1969

Rather than seeing monopoly as a source of economic inefficiency, it can be argued that it is in fact a source of economic welfare:

“The net impact of even a pure monopoly cannot be judged and should not be judged the way it almost always is judged ... that is, exclusively by its impact within the limits of its own market boundaries. After all, entrepreneurs throughout the economy will take note of the pure monopolist’s economic profits. The fact that those economic profits exist and persist can motivate a host of entrepreneurs to try to acquire the same kind of market position, earning perhaps no more than normal profits...”³²⁵

It is also too simplistic to assume that the existence of an incumbent monopoly makes it too difficult for a competitor to enter the market, as the European Commission does when it argues that the abuse of so-called market power inhibits innovation because smaller competitors know that their products cannot compete on merit.

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³²⁵ McKenzie, 2003

³²⁶ Posner, 1969

The real question therefore should not be by how much the existence of the monopoly diminishes the welfare of consumers, but by how much the welfare of consumers would be diminished if the monopolized product did not exist in the first place: “[E]ven a bad monopolist can give rise to offsetting, if not more than offsetting, welfare gains in the economy.”³²⁷ Historians of economic ideas may recognise this as almost an inversion of von Mises objections to public works, whose supporters he criticises for seeing the bridges that were built, but not the goods that were not created as a result of the funds being thus allocated.

Furthermore, it is questionable in how far a monopolist is in fact able to restrain output and maximize output on any significant scale: as Posner points out, “it is not clear that an unregulated monopolist will normally charge a price that greatly exceeds what a nonmonopolist would charge for the same service,”³²⁸ for a number of reasons: from a strategic point of view, a very high monopoly profit would attract competition, and therefore increase pressure on the monopolist. Also, for a large monopolist – and it is large monopolist regulators are concerned about, as already explained above – it may actually be very difficult to determine the monopoly price due to the principal-agent problem.

More importantly, while a monopolist may be able to charge an excessive price from current consumers, an uncompetitive price relative to substitutes would be unlikely to attract new consumers to the monopolist’s product. But the most famous monopolies in history, such as Standard Oil and most recently, Microsoft, have done their utmost to expand their customer base. And if the price of the monopolist is too high relative to substitutes, it may in fact encourage the development of substitutes and entice current customers to abandon the monopolist in the long run. It is for these reason that neither Adam Smith nor Schumpeter seemed to believe that any monopoly

³²⁷ McKenzie, 2004

³²⁸ Posner, 1969

is sustainable in the long run. But unlike Adam Smith, Schumpeter and analysts working in the Schumpeterian tradition see this latter effect as one of the benefits of monopoly: the existence of the monopoly price creates competition, which in turn forces both monopolist and competitor to remain entrepreneurial and competitive in the long run.

Ironically, while trying to develop a method for measuring the extent of monopoly, Lerner in fact acknowledges two points that are essential for this revised understanding of monopoly: substitutability on the margin means that in the long run every product can be substituted by another. If this is in fact the case, then the insight that the effectiveness of a monopoly depends on the elasticity of demand for its products should lead to the conclusion that in the long run, monopolies will be meaningless. By failing to recognise that the impact of any given economic arrangement needs to be analysed in the long run, and by also failing to recognise the role of the entrepreneur, Lerner remains caught in the traditional analysis of monopoly as socially detrimental.

But where Lerner seems merely short-sighted, Tullock may be outright absurd: by comparing the effects of competition with that of thievery, he completely fails to recognise the fundamental difference between a voluntary commercial exchange and a violent act of property rights violation. The monopolist, as I hope to have demonstrated, provides consumers with a direct benefit by making available a good that would otherwise not exist. Consumers are free to avoid the product and substitute it with another, thereby exposing the monopolist to the pressures of competition in the long run, giving rise to new products through greater incentives for new entrepreneurs. The thief, on the other hand, contributes nothing to the welfare of the consumer. Worse, the action of the thief is independent of the wishes of the consumers. The consumer cannot simply put up a sign that says “I do not wish to be stolen from”, while he can easily avoid buying from a monopolist.

Tullock's analysis becomes even more absurd when he argues that there is no fundamental difference between entrepreneurs trying to become monopolists by offering newer and better goods and services to consumers with the thief's continuous development of new methods of stealing. Tullock fails to recognise that if there was no more thievery tomorrow, the pace of economic development would likely accelerate. But it is unlikely that there would be any deliberate improvement of the human condition if it were impossible even in principle for anybody to earn even a short-term monopoly profit.

If one examines the intellectual history of monopoly, one is tempted to answer in the affirmative Dudden's question whether it was not perhaps true that "popular outburst against monopoly were instigated by men who had failed in business due to their own inefficiencies, and where thereupon exploited by politicians practicing the so-called "anti-monopoly racket?"³²⁹ One also has to wonder about the ability of politicians, professional bureaucrats, and academics to judge what a 'normal profit' in fact is. The formulaic approach to the determination of 'monopoly power', 'excessive profit', and 'excessive prices' employed by regulators gives the impression that running a business and estimating risk – for which profit is, after all, the compensation – is simply a matter of putting bricks on bricks, and fulfilling customer's orders. If business were indeed such a simple process, one has to wonder why so many businesses fail, why many companies that make millions of profits only recently are on the brink of bankruptcy today. And finally, if regulators, officials, politicians, and judges were as good at understanding business as their approach to the regulation of business seems to imply, how can it be explained that state corporations and publicly owned businesses are more likely to require subsidies and bail-outs rather than make even a normal profit?

³²⁹ Dudden, 1957

Few analysts seem to recognise the curious historical sequence of monopoly regulation and monopoly analysis: as DiLonrenzo and others have shown, anti-trust rules were implemented long before there was any systematic analysis of monopoly effects – the earliest objections to the power of ‘trusts’ (not to be confused with statutory monopolies) were highly moralistic, dealing with the themes of ‘freedom’ and the protection of the ‘small businessman’, not ‘dead-weight loss’ or market power.³³⁰ Even more ironically, regulation of monopoly has more often than not been promoted by incumbent firms who wished to protect themselves against the pressures of competition. The history of so-called ‘natural monopoly’ regulation is replete with examples where the dominant companies themselves had promoted government intervention, henceforth protecting themselves against competition by arguing for the public good of avoiding ‘duplication’ and ‘ruinous competition’.³³¹

So-called natural monopoly is, at least from this point of view, a fictional creature with little relevance to real economics. Throughout history, no so-called ‘natural monopoly’ has been able to survive without government protection, and when left unregulated were quickly supplanted by new and better products and services. The concept of ‘public utility’ which provides consumers with vital services that cannot be made available at satisfactory levels was not the result of careful economic analysis, as DiLorenzo shows, but of intense political lobbying.³³² Almost all so-called naturally monopolies were at one time or other competitively operating markets: railways, trucking, airlines, electricity, and gas – both synthetic and natural – had at one time or another been supplied by unregulated firms without any form of competition policy. Today, many of these are reborn as

³³⁰ DiLorenzo, 1991, Dudden 1957

³³¹ As if competition was ever anything but ruinous to firms who do not succeed to stay ahead of the game at all times.

³³² DiLorenzo, 1991

partially competitive markets again – though with significant ‘legacy’ regulation that continues to treat them as ‘natural monopolies’.

While some of these were in fact local monopolies – particularly railways – they nonetheless competed with each other over long distances. Electricity companies were intensely competitive, until they began to be regulated by governments as the result of industry lobbying. Most relevant to this discussion is the intense and successful competition between different forms of energy, such as coal and gas, and gas and electricity. Few economists seem to be aware of the fact that electricity replaced the local city gas monopolies by being much cheaper and more convenient.

The failure to differentiate between the longevity of government protected statutory monopoly and the transitory nature of monopoly in the free market is at the root of the contradictions in current European Union competition policy as it applies to the energy sector. The monopolistic structure of the European energy market, and in particular gas market, was not the result of ‘natural monopolies’ crowding out competition, but deliberate government policy aimed at satisfying political goals. The resulting high energy prices, unsatisfactory service, and overall inefficiency should not have come as a surprise to a student of Adam Smith or any other free market theorist.

The most critical mistake of the European Union is to focus on consumer prices – and working towards keeping them as low as possible by continuously monitoring how ‘justified’ these prices are relative to the marginal costs of energy providers. If there were no possibility of future technological change, and if it could be assumed that the current arrangement of energy sources and distributions will remain unchanged, such policies might make sense.

But if it is accepted that the fundamental nature of the market is change, and that progress is at least partially the result of entrepreneurs chasing (almost always in vain) the Holy Grail of Monopoly

Power (which can never be maintained forever), than it should be apparent that keeping consumer prices low by regulation serves no beneficial purpose.

The purpose of unbundling and TPA is to eliminate every possibility of monopoly profit throughout the supply chain and provide greater competition among energy traders, both those who are the subsidiaries of energy pipeline and production companies, and those who do nothing but trade energy as pure marketing entrepreneurs. The immediate effect is likely reduced prices for energy consumers – but at the expense of long-term investment into energy supply projects and infrastructure.

Unbundling makes it difficult, if not outright impossible, for energy companies to take advantage of significant economies of scale – whether physical or administrative. Each single player within the supply chain, if he is prohibited from owning either upstream or downstream elements of the market – will be unlikely to create any surplus capacity, since this would result in higher costs. Even if the cost of building a larger pipeline does not rise proportionately to the volume of the pipeline, it is still a higher cost the operator will not want to incur unless he has certainty to recoup it in the future. However, with more players in the market competing for the same volume of natural gas, each will have less certainty about future supplies and will benefit from building too little rather than too much capacity. If he builds too little – and everybody else builds too little – any increase in demand for transmission capacity will result in higher prices for transmission services.

Creating spare capacity, as the IEA has correctly pointed out, will not be in the interest of companies working in a hyper-competitive environment of mandatory unbundling and TPA. It should therefore not come as a surprise to the EU that investment into gas transmission infrastructure is much lower than most analysts believe is necessary to achieve long-term supply security.

TPA for trading companies without a stake in production and transmission aggravates the problem further, particularly if successful: by reducing the price to final consumers through increased competition for downstream market share, the demand for gas will increase. However, since the incentives to create transmission capacity is reduced, the amount of additional supplies that can in fact be made available will be diminished – either increasing consumer prices or triggering further intervention into the market through regulations that specify spare capacity requirements. The regulations, however, will make it more difficult for new companies to enter the market, since the entry costs are increased while profits are artificially diminished.

Artificially reduced consumer prices also decrease the incentive for entrepreneurs to enter the gas market on the margins. As already discussed, LNG is widely considered to be an important factor for energy security, but LNG is also more expensive than piped natural gas. If consumer prices are depressed through regulation, there is a smaller profit to be made for those interested in providing LNG to the energy market, which in turn decreases the amount of LNG supplied to the market. LNG supplies are further diminished by the requirement for TPA for LNG facilities.

From an energy security point of view, this is a very detrimental development: low consumer prices increase demand, but diminished incentives for investment decrease the amount of transmission capacity that would be necessary to supply the demand. Furthermore, increased demand would also require greater development upstream – but since profits are artificially reduced, there is less of an incentive for production companies to invest into the development of new gas resources. It is probably not by accident that investment in natural gas production and transmission is generally considered to be less than adequate to meet future market demands.

If current trends continue, it is not impossible that the energy crisis of the 1970s may repeat itself in the gas sector. But while the oil crisis of the 1970s was largely a price crisis, a gas supply

crisis may easily take the form of a real supply shock that cannot be mitigated by a redirection of energy supplies through increased energy prices: as already discussed, most natural gas is still transported by pipelines. As spare capacity within the pipeline system diminishes, any interruption of gas supplies could result in significant system wide supply shocks that cannot be compensated by a simple redirection of gas flows. Pipelines that receive their gas from sources not affected by the disruption will continue to carry their previous capacities and are likely not capable of absorbing additional gas supplies for the purpose of transit to deficit regions. Unlike ships, pipelines cannot be simply reversed to meet demand at unusual locations. Since gas is increasingly used for the generation of electricity, a gas supply shock would automatically be an electricity supply shock as well – affecting multiple industries at once, often within very short time frames and with little possibility for fast mitigation.

Unlike the crisis of the 1970s, a disruption of gas supplies under conditions of very tight transmission capacity and low LNG supplies could in fact turn into a real supply shock resulting in an acute short-fall of physical supplies. At the same time, the gas supply system has only very limited capacity for augmenting physical supplies beyond the current balancing capacity for seasonal fluctuations. For cost and technological reasons, it is unlikely that in the future there will be any significant strategic reserves for natural gas. And even if there were strategic reserves, it is not guaranteed that their location and connection to the supply system will make it possible to make up for shortfalls in other regions. It is not without irony that the oil supply system is far better equipped to deal with the case of physical disruptions than the gas system, even though the likelihood of an actual physical supply shock is far lower in the oil than the gas sector.

EU regulators believe that energy supply security can be improved by promoting the unbundling of vertically integrated energy companies and Third Party Access to so-called ‘essential

infrastructures'. This approach is based on the assumption that vertical integration and control over essential infrastructures constitutes a so-called 'natural monopoly' that provides companies with the ability to limit the supply of goods and increase prices arbitrarily. In the preceding chapter I have argued that while competition is in fact a desirable feature of the market, as is energy security, the policies of the European Union to achieve both are likely to be unsuccessful.

The theoretical basis for the concept of natural monopoly is weak at best: it ignores that the function of goods and services matters to consumers far more than the individual good or service. The goods and services provided by different companies do not only compete with their exact equivalents, but also with their potential substitutes. The higher the price of a good or service, the greater the range of potential substitutes and in the long run an artificially inflated price will attract either new entrants into the market of the same good or it will make it economical to provide substitute products. Rather than considering a temporary monopoly profit as undesirable, regulators should recognise that without its existence, there would be little incentive for anybody to even consider entering a market directly or at the margins. Entrepreneurs do not become active to make a 'normal profit' – where marginal costs equal marginal revenue – but to make an extraordinary profit. Rather than seeing 'monopoly profit' as a bane to the economy, regulators should begin to see it as an incentive for innovation of all kinds. Without it, there would be no reason to change anything – barring dramatic extraneous influences on the market the absence of any kind of above-normal profit would discourage risk-taking and innovation. The result would be an economy devoid of Schumpeterian 'creative destruction' and in its stead we would find stagnation.

Stagnation in the energy sector, however, is the very opposite of energy security. The total supply of fossil fuels is probably sufficient to fuel the world's economy for centuries to come. But the supply of cheap and easily accessible oil and gas is coming to an end. What is needed for the

continued supply of abundant oil and gas is ever greater innovation and ever greater risk taking. Business as usual is not an option in an industry that deals with a finite resource base. As energy reserves become more difficult to find and exploit, the level of risk associated with the sector will increase, and with it the difficulty to secure investment. More than any other industry, energy requires very patient money – investors have to be willing to provide billions of euros and have to wait sometimes decades before turning a profit. The risks of the sector are tremendous: as recent events in Russia have shown, even companies the size of BP and Shell are helpless against governments determined to take away their assets. Civil and international wars, earthquakes, volcanoes and storms can destroy onshore and offshore operations. Pipelines and other facilities can be targeted by terrorists. The risks are endless and unpredictable. To apply the standard of ‘normal’ profit to an industry that operates under clearly abnormal conditions is absurd. Unless investors have at least the hope to reap extraordinary profits, there is little reason for them to engage in extraordinary risks. And the greater the possible rewards, the greater the competition for them; and with greater competition comes greater energy security.

But rather than creating the creative competition at the upstream level so desperately needed for the security of energy supplies in Europe, the current measures favoured by EU regulators encourages competition that can best be characterised as parasitical. Energy trading requires little investment, allows for very easy entry and exit into the market, and attracts investors unwilling to wait decades before seeing a return. If the EU measures will prove so successful that energy prices at the retail level will drop dramatically to the point that it is impossible to reap anything but ‘normal profits’ at any level of the energy sector. Consumers may enjoy a brief period of low-priced energy, but only at the expense of dramatically reduced investment in exploration, development, and transportation.

For the security of natural gas supplies, the long-term consequences may be catastrophic: there will be little incentive to develop alternative transportation technologies that could compete with pipelines. The state monopolies of Russia and Algeria will continue to be the main suppliers of natural gas via pipelines into the European Union. Even without the risk of politically motivated supply shocks, the long-term effect is that this will delay the development of alternative resources in unusual regions. The IEA, the European Union, and industry analysts already warn that investment into infrastructure and green-field development far below what is required for the long-term security of gas supplies into Europe.

If European regulators are serious about promoting energy security, they have to eventually learn the lessons of the oil crises in 1973 and 1978: the key to energy security is energy investment, and the key to energy investment is profits. Instead of seeing profits reaped by energy companies as immoral and damaging to consumers, regulators should consider them as the price consumers have to pay for the security of future supplies – as the internalized costs of the social benefit of energy security for all.

6. Concluding Remarks

Energy supply security matters. A stable and predictable economic environment is preferable to an unstable and unpredictable one. The less certainty there is for consumers and companies, the more resources will be devoted to dealing with these uncertainties rather than creating value and economic growth. While energy supply shocks may not be as dangerous to the macro-economy as commonly believed, they nevertheless can inflict serious damage on individual companies and households. If energy supply shocks are combined with already unstable political conditions, their impact can extend beyond the purely economic into the political realm. Politicians may be tempted to find ways and means of ‘dealing’ with the problem on an ad-hoc basis, more likely aggravating than alleviating whatever difficulties the economy is facing.

Policy makers in the European Union should realize that the best way of dealing with energy supply security problems is to leave their solution to the market. It may not be politically desirable to let energy companies reap what is perceived to be ‘excessively high profits’, but it must be recognized that these profits are necessary to motivate economic actors to invest into energy supplies. There can be no energy supply security without investment, and there can be no investment without the prospect of profit. European politicians have to realize that profits are more than just a way to recover costs. Profits are the reward for entrepreneurial risk. Few businesses are as risky as the energy business. Billions are being spent every year on projects that may or may not be profitable in the long run. Without the prospect of very high profits, nobody is likely to engage in very high risks. Energy companies are not in the business of charity and public service – energy companies are in the business of making money.

To insist on the one hand that energy is vital for the economy, and to demand on the other hand that it be cheap is absurd. Cheap energy has been at the root of the energy supply security

problem throughout the 20th century. If energy prices had reflected their true costs during the post-war era, it is unlikely that industry and consumers had used it as inefficiently and wastefully as they have done. It is even more absurd to demand that consumers and industry engage in energy conservation, but simultaneously encourage the continued wasteful consumption of what is in fact a non-renewable resource by insisting that energy prices be as low as absolutely possible. It makes little sense to ask an industry that is providing a unique product to earn only a normal profit.

European politicians and the European public have to move away from a simplistic economic thought model that treats profits as morally reprehensible, and insists that entrepreneurs must work as the servants of the public. It may be politically expedient for European politicians and policy makers to cater to the widespread idea of a ‘just price’, but it must also be recognised that medieval concepts are unlikely to contribute to the solution of modern problems. Energy supply security is first and foremost an economic problem, and its solution must be economic.

Price controls have never succeeded in achieving the goals their creators had in mind. It does not matter whether the government regulates prices crudely at the retail level, or whether it employs more sophisticated methods at the distribution and production level. Unbundling and regulated TPA are little more than complex means of regulating prices. Laws and regulations may be able to regulate energy prices, but laws and regulations cannot create new supplies of energy, and laws and regulations cannot build pipelines, tanker ships, and port facilities. But energy security needs more pipelines, tanker ships, and port facilities; it needs the promise of great profits for entrepreneurs to engage in great risks.

However – this does not mean that energy supply security should not be a concern for policy makers. While the role of government cannot be the management of long-term economic trends, of which government is inherently incapable, government has an important role to deal with short-run

problems that are the result of non-market events and hence beyond the scope of the market. Governments should also work towards limiting the political risks to the secure supply of energy by creating positive relationships with other governments, particularly those of energy exporting countries.

7. Bibliography

- Adamson, David M. "Soviet Gas and European Security." Energy Policy February (1985).
- Aghion, Philippe and Rachel Griffith. Competition and Growth. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press, 2005.
- Alger, Dan and Michael A. Toman. "Market-Based Regulation of Natural Gas Pipelines." Journal of Regulatory Economics 2.3 (1990): 263-80.
- Amsterdam, Robert. "Rolling over to Kremlin's manipulations." Financial Times 9 Nov. 2007.
- Anderson, Kym. "The political economy of coal subsidies in Europe." Energy Policy 23.6 (1995): 485-96.
- Andrews, P. W. S. On Competition in Economic Theory. New York, New York: Macmillan & Co Ltd., 1964.
- Argyris, Nicholas. "Regulatory Reform in the Electricity Sector: An Analysis of the Commission's Internal Market Proposals." Oxford Review of Economic Policy 9.1 (1993): 31-44.
- Asche, Frank, Petter Osmundsen, and Ragnar Tveteras. "European market integration for gas? Volume flexibility and political risk." Energy Economics 24.5 (2002): 249-65.
- Aune, Finn Roar. "Liberalizing the Energy Markets of Western Europe--A Computable Equilibrium Model Approach." Applied Economics 36.19 (2004): 2137-49.
- Australian Government Productivity Commission. Review of the Gas Access Regime. Book, Whole vols. Melbourne: Author, 2004.
- Austrian Economics in Debate. Ed. Willem Keizer, Bert Tieben, and Rudy van Zijp. New York, New York: Routledge, 1997.
- Axelrod, Regina S. "The European Energy Charter Treaty : Reality or illusion?" Energy Policy 24.6 (1996): 497-505.
- Azar, Ofer H. "Can Price Discrimination Be Bad for Firms and Good for All Consumers? A Theoretical Analysis of Cross-Market Price Constraints with Entry and Product Differentiation." Topics in Economic Analysis and Policy 3.1 (2003): na.
- Bahgat, Gawdat. "EU seeks energy security in stronger supplier ties." Oil & Gas Journal (2008): 22.
- Bahgat, Gawdat. "Europe's energy security: challenges and opportunities." International Affairs 82.5 (2006): 961-75.
- Bahgat, Gawdat. "Pipeline Diplomacy: The Geopolitics of the Caspian Sea Region." International Studies Perspectives 3.3 (2002): 310-27.

- Bailes, Alyson J. K., Isabel Frommelt, and Stockholm International Peace Research Institute. Business and Security - Public-Private Sector Relationships in a New Security Environment. xvi, 328 p vols. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004.
- Banks, Ferdinand E. The Political Economy of Natural Gas. Beckenham, Kent: Croom Helm Ltd., 1987.
- Baran, Zeyno. "EU Energy Security: Time to End Russian Leverage." Washington Quarterly 30.4 (2007): 131-44.
- Barnett, A. Privatising European Energy. Issues and Lessons. 1995.
- Barnett, A. Natural Gas in Europe – Competing to provide tomorrows' energy, London: Financial Times Energy Publishing, 1995
- Barnett, J. "Maintaining energy security in a global context. A report to the trilateral commission no. 48." Australian Journal of International Affairs 51.3 (1997): 442-43.
- Barsky, Robert B. and Lutz Kilian. "A Monetary Explanation of the Great Stagflation of the 1970s." NBER Working Paper No.W7547 (2000).
- Barton, Barry. Energy Security : Managing Risk in a Dynamic Legal and Regulatory Environment. Ed. Barry Barton. New York; Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004.
- Batty, James. "Race is on to build vessel with onboard liquefaction capability." Natural Gas Week 10 Jan. 2007.
- Belkin, Paul. CRS Report to Congress - The European Union's Energy Security Challenges. RL33636. 2007. Congressional Research Service.
Ref Type: Report
- Benjamin, Milton R. and MacPherson, Malcolm. "Energy: what other nations are doing." Newsweek 17 Feb. 1975.
- Berg, Sanford V. and John Tschirhart. Natural Monopoly Regulation: Principles and Practice. Book, Whole vols. Cambridge Surveys of Economic Literature series Cambridge; New York and Melbourne: Cambridge University Press, 1988.
- Bergmann, Burckhard. "Supply Prospects and Network Integration in the European Natural Gas Sector." OPEC Review 22.2 (1998): 159-67.
- Bierling, S. "Energy security in a global context. A report for the Trilateral Commission - German - Martin,WF, Imai,R, Steeg,H." Internationale Politik 52.9 (1997): 65-66.
- Block, Walter. "Austrian Monopoly Theory - A Critique." Journal of Libertarian Studies 1.4 (1977): 271-79.

- Blum, Ulrich, Christian Growitsch, and Niels Krap. "Network Investment and the Threat of Regulation - Preventing Monopoly Exploitation or Infrastructure Construction?" Diss. Halle Institute for Economic Research, IWH Discussion Papers, 2006.
- Boettke, Peter J. "Review of: Privatization, public ownership the regulation of natural monopoly." Journal of Economic Literature 32.4 (1994): 1916-18.
- Bohi, D. R. and M. A. Toman. "Energy Security - Externalities and Policies." Energy Policy 21.11 (1993): 1093-109.
- Bohi, D. R. Energy Price Shocks and Macroeconomic Performance. Washington, DC: Resources for the Future, 1989.
- Bohi, Douglas R and Michael A. Toman. The Economics of Energy Security. Boston: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1996.
- Bolonkin, Alexander A. and Cathcart, Richard B. A low-cost natural gas/freshwater aerial pipeline. <http://arxiv.org/ftp/physics/papers/0701/0701061.pdf> . 2007.
Ref Type: Electronic Citation
- Bonfiglioli, Gianpaolo. "Economics of gas imports to Europe from Opec." Oil & Gas Journal (1980).
- Bradburd, Ralph. "Privatization of Natural Monopoly Public Enterprises: A Reply." Review of Industrial Organization 11.6 (1996): 883-87.
- Bradburd, Ralph. "Privatization of Natural Monopoly Public Enterprises: The Regulation Issue." Review of Industrial Organization 10.3 (1995): 247-67.
- Bradburd, Ralph. "Privatization of Natural Monopoly Public Enterprises: the Regulation Issue." Diss. The World Bank, Policy Research Working Paper Series, 1992.
- Braeutigam, Ronald R. "Regulatory Reform: Lessons for Natural Gas Pipelines." Contemporary Policy Issues 8.2 (1990): 122-41.
- Bratland, John. "Contestable Market Theory as a Regulatory Framework: An Austrian Postmortem." The Quarterly Journal of Austrian Economics 7.3 (2004): 3-28.
- Broadman, Harry G. and Joseph P. Kalt. "How natural is monopoly? the case of bypass in natural gas distribution markets." Yale Journal on Regulation 6 (1989): 181-208.
- Brunekreeft, Gert and Sven Tweleemann. "Regulation, Competition and Investment in the German Electricity Market: RegTP or REGTP." Diss. 2005.
- Brunekreeft, Gert. "'Regulatory Issues in Merchant Transmission Investment'." Diss. 2004.
- Bucknell, Howard III. Energy and the National Defense. Lexington, Kentucky: The University Press of Kentucky, 1981.

- Burns, Philip and Thomas G. Weyman-Jones. "Is the Gas Supply Market a Natural Monopoly? Econometric Evidence from the British Gas Regions." Energy Economics 20.2 (1998): 223-32.
- Cecc, Stephen. "Remember Stagflation: the lesson of the 1970s is that tighter monetary policy is the best response to oil price shocks." Financial Times 13 Oct. 2000, London Edition ed.
- Cheung, Steven N. S. The Myth of Social Cost. London, UK: The Institute of Economic Affairs, 1978.
- Church, Jeffrey and Roger Ware. Industrial Organization: A Strategic Approach. New York, New York: McGrawHill, 2000.
- Clark, John Maurice. Competition As a Dynamic Process. Washington, DC: The Brookings Institute, 1961.
- Clingendael International Energy Programme. EU Energy Supply Security and Geopolitics. Tren/C1-06-2002. 30-1-2004. Brussels. 23-9-2007.
Ref Type: Report
- Coase, Richard H. "The Problem of Social Cost." Journal of Law and Economics 3.October (1960): 1-44.
- Coase, Richard H. "The theory of public utility pricing and its applicaiton." The Bell Journal of Economics and Management Science 1.1 (1970): 113-28.
- Commission of the European Communities. A European Strategy for Sustainable, Competitive and Secure Energy. COM(2006) 105 final. 8-3-2006. Brussels, The European Commissions. Green Paper. 23-9-2007.
Ref Type: Report
- Commission of the European Communities. White Paper on Energy Policy: An Energy Policy for the European Union. 1995.
- Conant, Melvin A. and Fern Racine Gold. The Geopolitics of Energy. Boulder, Colorado: Westview Press, 1978.
- Cootner, Paul H. and Holland Daniel M. "Rate of return and business risk." The Bell Journal of Economics and Management Science 1.2 (1970): 211-26.
- Corneli, Steven B. "Will customer choice always lower costs?" Electricity Journal 9 (1996): 21-31.
- Correlje, A. and C. van der Linde. "Energy supply security and geopolitics: A European perspective." Energy Policy 34.5 (2006): 532-43.
- Cowan, Simon. "Competition in the Water Industry." Oxford Review of Economic Policy 13.1 (1997): 83-92.

- Cowan, Simon. "Marginal Cost Pricing Versus Insurance." Diss. University of Oxford, Department of Economics, Economics Series Working Papers, 2002.
- Cowling, Keith and Dennis C. Mueller. "The Social Cost of Monopoly Power." The Economic Journal 88.352 (1978): 727-48.
- Creedy, John and Robert Dixon. "The relative burden of monopoly on households with different incomes." Economica 65.258 (1998): 285-93.
- Crooks, Ed. "Flexibility to go where the price rises the highest." Financial Times 10 Mar. 2008.
- Cuñado, Juncal and Fernando Perez de Gracia. "Do oil price shocks matter? Evidence for some European countries." Energy Economics 25.2 (2003): 137-54.
- Currier, Kevin M. "Natural Monopoly Regulation in the Presence of Cost Misreporting." Atlantic Economic Journal 32.1 (2004): 49-61.
- De Fraja, Gianni. "Entry, Prices, and Investment in Regulated Industries." Journal of Regulatory Economics 11.3 (1997): 257-70.
- De Vany, Arthur S. and W. David Walls. "The triumph of markets in natural gas." Public Utilities Fortnightly 133 (1995): 21-25.
- De Vany, Arthur S. and W. David Walls. The Emerging New Order in Natural Gas. Westport, Ct: Quorum Books, 1995.
- Demsetz, Harold. "Why Regulate Utilities." Journal of Law and Economics 11.1 (1968): 55-65.
- Dienes, Leslie. "Energy prospects for Eastern Europe." Energy Policy 4.2 (1976): 119-29.
- DiLorenzo, Thomas J. "The Antitrust Economists' Paradox." Austrian Economics Newsletter 1991.Summer (1991): 1-6.
- DiLorenzo, Thomas J. "The Myth of Natural Monopoly." Review of Austrian Economics 9.2 (1996): 43-58.
- Doré, Julia and Robert De Bauw. The Energy Charter Treaty Origins, Aims and Prospects. xvi, 89 p vols. London: Royal Institute of International Affairs, Energy and Environmental Programme, 1995.
- Drottboom, Michael and Wolfgang Leininger. "On the Scope of Indirect Regulation of Monopolies in the Presence of Large Entry Cost." Empirica 20.1 (1993): 69-80.
- Dudden, Arthur P. "Men against Monopoly." Journal of the History of Ideas 18.4 (1957): 587-93.
- Dweck, Jacob. "European LNG developes face complex commercial landscape." Oil & Gas Journal 2007.April (2007): 20.

- Ebinger, Charles K. The Critical Link: Energy and National Security in the 1980s. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The Center for Strategic and International Studies, 1982.
- Egenhofer, Christian, Gialoglou, Kyriakos, Luciani, Giacomo, Boots, Maroeska, Scheepers, Martin, Constantini, Valeria, Gracceva, Francesco, Markandya, Anil, and Vicin, Giorgio. Market-based Options for Security of Energy Supply. 2004. The Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei. Ref Type: Report
- Emmons, William M., I. "Franklin D. Roosevelt, Electrical Utilities, and the Power of Competition." Journal of Economic History 53.4 (1993): 880-907.
- Erickson, J. "Russia will not be trifled with!: Geopolitical facts and fantasies." Journal of Strategic Studies 22.2-3 (1999): 242-+.
- Esnault, Benoît. "The need for regulation of gas storage: the case of France." Energy Policy 31.2 (2003): 167-74.
- Estache, Antonio and Martin Rodriguez-Pardina. "Light and Lightning at the End of the Public Tunnel: Reform of the Electricity Sector in the Southern Cone." Diss. The World Bank, Policy Research Working Paper Series, 1999.
- Estrada, Javier et al. Natural Gas in Europe. London, UK: Pinter Publishers Limited, 1988.
- EUguides - Energy Policy in the European Union. 2004.
Ref Type: Report
- European Commission and Directorate General for Energy and Transport. Security of supply - Europe spins its energy web. 2004. Brussels, European Commission Directorate-General for Energy and Transport.
Ref Type: Computer Program
- European Commission. Green Paper - towards a European strategy for the security of energy supply. 2000. Brussels, Belgium, European Commission.
Ref Type: Report
- Fell, Mike. "Is Human Security the our Main Concern in the 21st Century?" Journal of Security Sector Management 4.3 (2006): 1-11.
- Finon, Dominique. "Reforms in the French power system: from weak contestability to effective competition?" Energy Policy 29.10 (2001): 755-68.
- Flavin, Christopher and Seth Dunn. "A new energy paradigm for the 21st century." Journal of International Affairs 53.1 (1999): 167-90.
- Fox, Liam. "Energy: the new cold war." Sunday Times 15 July 2007.
- Funk, Cara. "How Can Natural Gas Markets be Competitively Organized?" Economies et Societes 26.1-2 (1992): 239-61.

- Gasmi, F., J. J. Laffont, and W. W. Sharkey. "The Natural Monopoly Test Reconsidered: An Engineering Process-Based Approach to Empirical Analysis in Telecommunications." International Journal of Industrial Organization 20.4 (2002): 435-59.
- Gasteyer, Curt Walter. The Future for European Energy Security. 177 p vols. New York: St. Martin's Press, 1985.
- Geddes, R. Richard. "A historical perspective on electric utility regulation." Regulation 15 (1992): 75-82.
- Goel, Rajeev K. "Research Spending under Regulatory Uncertainty." Journal of Technology Transfer 32.6 (2007): 593-604.
- Goldthau, Andreas. "Rhetoric versus reality: Russian threats to European Energy Supplies." Energy Policy.36 (2008): 686-92.
- Golombek, R., M. Hoel, and Visile J. Natural Gas Markets and Contracts. New York, New York: 2008.
- Gomez, Brian. "ExxonMobil PNG project to cost \$9.5 billion; oil search earmarks \$190 million for exploration in 2007." Platts Oilgram News 7 May 2007, 85 ed.
- Gordon, D. V., K. Gunsch, and C. V. Pawluk. "A Natural Monopoly in Natural Gas Transmission." Energy Economics 25.5 (2003): 473-85.
- Gordon, Richard L. "Don't restructure electricity: deregulate." Cato Journal 20.3 (2001): 327-58.
- Greene, Harold H. "Natural monopoly, consumers, and government." New York Law School Law Review 34.2 (1989): 249-65.
- Gregory, Paul R. and Robert C. Stuart. Comparative Economic Systems. Boston, MA: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1999.
- Grenier, Edward J. Jr. "Natural Gas - Everyone's Holy Grail." Natural Gas 2000.March (2000).
- Griffin, James M. and Henry B. Steele. Energy Economics and Policy. Orlando, Florida: Academic Press, In.c, 1986.
- Grossman, Peter Z. "Does the End of a Natural Monopoly Mean Deregulation?" Ed. Peter Z. Grossman and Daniel H. Cole. Book, Section vols. Economics of Legal Relationships, vol. 7. Amsterdam; London and New York: Elsevier Science, JAI, 2003. 215-43.
- Grossman, Peter Z. "The Zenith of the Natural Monopoly System." Ed. Peter Z. Grossman and Daniel H. Cole. Book, Section vols. Economics of Legal Relationships, vol. 7. Amsterdam; London and New York: Elsevier Science, JAI, 2003. 89-106.
- Grossman, Peter Z. and Daniel H. Cole. The End of a Natural Monopoly: Deregulation and Competition in the Electric Power Industry. 7 ed. Book, Whole vols. Amsterdam; London and New York: Elsevier Science, JAI, 2003.

- Growitsch, Christian and Thomas Wein. "Negotiated Third Party Access--An Industrial Organisation Perspective." European Journal of Law and Economics 20.2 (2005): 165-83.
- Growitsch, Christian and Thomas Wein. "Network Access Charges, Vertical Integration, and Property Rights Structure--Experiences from the German Electricity Markets." Energy Economics 27.2 (2005): 257-78.
- Guidlines on the assessment of horizontal mergers. <http://europa.eu/scadplus/leg/lvb/l26107.htm>
. 21-2-2007. 27-3-2008.
Ref Type: Electronic Citation
- Hall, Darwin C. "Oil and national security." Energy Policy 1992.November (1992): 1089-96.
- Handbook of Natural Resource and Energy Economics, Volume 1. Ed. Allen V. Kneese and James L. Sweeney. New York, New York: Elsevier Science Publishing Company, Inc., 1985.
- Handbook of Natural Resource and Energy Economics, Volume 2. New York, New York: Elsevier Science Publishing Company, Inc., 1985.
- Handbook of Natural Resource and Energy Economics, Volume 3. Ed. Allen V. Kneese and James L. Sweeney. 1993: 1985.
- Happ, Richard. Schiedsverfahren Zwischen Staaten Und Investoren Nach Artikel 26 Energiechartavertrag - Eine Studie Zum Wandel Der Streitbeilegung Im Investitionsschutzrecht Unter Den Bedingungen Einer Globalen Weltwirtschaft. 220 p vols. Frankfurt am Main: P. Lang, 2000.
- Helm, Dieter. "Energy policy: security of supply, sustainability and competition." Energy Policy 30.3 (2002): 173-1.
- Hira, Anil and Libardo Amaya. "Does energy integrate?" Energy Policy 31.2 (2003): 185-99.
- Hoffman, George W. "THE ROLE OF NUCLEAR POWER IN EUROPE'S FUTURE ENERGY BALANCE *." Annals of the Association of American Geographers 47.1 (1957): 15-40.
- Hoj, Jens and Michael Wise. "Product Market Competition and Economic Performance in France." Diss. OECD Economics Department, OECD Economics Department Working Papers, 2006.
- Hoppe, Hans-Hermann. A Theory of Socialism and Capitalism. Norwell, Massachusetts: Kluwer Academic Publishers, 1988.
- Hoppe, Hans-Hermann. The Myth of National Defense: Essays on the Theory and History of Security Production. Auburn, Alabama: The Ludwig von Mises Institute, 2003.
- Hubbard, R. Glenn. "Managing the Strategic Petroleum Reserves: Energy Policy in a Market Setting." Annual Review of Energy.10 (1985): 515-56.
- Independent Thinking. Utility Week (2006).

- Indjehagopian, J. P., F Lantz, and V Simon. "Dynamics of heating oil market prices in Europe." Energy Economics 2.26 (2000): 225-52.
- Institute of Energy (Great Britain). Energy in the Single Market - Papers and Synopses of Presentations Given at a Conference Held on 14 May 1992, London, UK. 1 v. (various pagings) vols. London, UK: The Institute, 1992.
- International Energy Agency and Charter Secretariat Energy. Caspian Oil and Gas - the Supply Potential of Central Asia and Transcaucasia. 297 p vols. Paris: The Agency, 1998.
- International Energy Agency and Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. The Energy Charter Treaty a Description of Its Provisions. 36 p vols. Paris: International Energy Agency, 1994.
- International Energy Agency, Charter Secretariat Energy, and Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Black Sea Energy Survey. Paris: OECD/IEA, 2000.
- International Energy Agency, Charter Secretariat Energy, and Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. Russia Energy Survey, 2002. 278 p vols. Paris: OECD/IEA, 2002.
- International Energy Agency. Energy Policies of the IEA Countries - 2003 Review. Paris: IEA Publications, 2003.
- International Energy Agency. Energy Security and Climate Policy: Assessing Interaction. Brussels: OECD/IEA, 2007.
- International Energy Agency. Regulatory Reform: European Gas. Book, Whole vols. Paris and Washington, D.C.: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2000.
- Izundu, Uchenna. "Resource nationalism among hot topics at WEC." Oil & Gas Journal (2007): 22.
- Johnson, Debra. "EU-Russian Energy Links: A Marriage of Convenience?" Government and Opposition 40.2 (2005): 256-77.
- Johnson, Eric. "LPG: a secure, cleaner transport fuel? A policy recommendation for Europe." Energy Policy 31.15 (2003): 1573-77.
- Joskow, Paul and Jean Tirole. "Merchant Transmission Investment." Diss. 2003.
- Joskow, Paul L. "Regulation of Natural Monopolies." Diss. 2005.
- Julius, DeAnne and Afsaneh Mashayekhi. The Economics of Natural Gas. Oxford, UK: The Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 1990.
- Juris, Andrej. "The Emergence of Markets in the Natural Gas Industry." Diss. The World Bank, Policy Research Working Paper Series, 1998.

- Kalicki, J. H. and David L. Goldwyn. Energy & Security. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson Center Press, 2005.
- Kalicki, J. H. and David L. Goldwyn. Energy and Security - Toward a New Foreign Policy Strategy. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson Center for Scholars, 2005.
- King, Stephen P. "Access Pricing under Rate-of-Return Regulation." Australian Economic Review 30.3 (1997): 243-55.
- Kirzner, Israel M. Competition and Entrepreneurship. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 1973.
- Klaassen, Ger, Alan McDonald, and Jimin Zhao. "The future of gas infrastructures in Eurasia." Energy Policy 29.5 (2001): 399-413.
- Knieps, Gunter. "Railway (de-)regulation in Germany." CESifo DICE Report 3.4 (2005): 21-25.
- Kreutzer, David W. and William C. Wood. "Private Monopoly vs. Public Shortsightedness: Private the Natural Monopoly Rationale Revisited." Journal of Private Enterprise 13.1 (1997): 68-80.
- Krupnick, Alan J. and Dallas Burtraw. "The social costs of electricity: do the numbers add up?" Resources and Energy Economics 18.4 (1996): 423-66.
- Kulczycka, J. and A. Lipinska. "Barriers to liberalisation of the Polish energy-sector." Applied Energy 76.1-3 (2003): 229-38.
- Kwoka, John E. "The Role of Competition in Natural Monopoly: Costs, Public Ownership, and Regulation." Review of Industrial Organization 29.1-2 (2006): 127-47.
- Laffont, Jean Jacques and Jean Tirole. "Cartelization by Regulation." Journal of Regulatory Economics 5.2 (1993): 111-30.
- Lai, H. H. "China's oil diplomacy: is it a global security threat?" Third World Quarterly 28.3 (2007): 519-37.
- Land, Thomas. "Gas transport investment to top Dollars 200bn over 20 years." Lloyd's List 7 Sept. 1994.
- Land, Thomas. "Spotlight falls on gas transport: two studies look at the challenge facing industrialised countries in pumping investment into infrastructure - the industrialised world must invest heavily in energy transport infrastructure. Thomas Land reports on two analyses of the options." Lloyd's List 9 July 1994.
- Landsberg, Hans H. Making National Energy Policy. Book, Whole vols. Inc.: Resources for the Future, 1993.
- Lang, K. O. "Between security policy and economics: Poland's energy economy." Osteuropa 54.9-10 (2004): 203-22.

- Law, Stephen M. "The Problem of Market Size for Canadian Cable Television Regulation." Applied Economics 34.1 (2002): 87-99.
- Lawrey, Roger. "Pricing and Access under National Competition Policy: The Case of the Natural Gas Pipeline Sector." Australian Economic Review 31.2 (1998): 91-106.
- Leblond, Doris. "Commission proposes EU energy strategy." Oil & Gas Journal (2006): 33.
- Leblond, Doris. "IEA: open gas markets improve supply reliability, security." Oil & Gas Journal (2004).
- Lebow, Richard Ned and Thomas Risse-Kappen. International Relations Theory and the End of the Cold War. CIAO Online edition ed. New York: Columbia University Press, 1997.
- Legendre, Thierry. "The North Atlantic Treaty Organization's Future Role in Energy Security." The Whitehead Journal of Diplomacy and International Relations 2007.Summer/Fall (2007): 29-35.
- Lerner, Abba Ptachya. "The concept of monopoly and the measurement of monopoly power." The Review of Economic Studies 1.3 (1934): 157-75.
- Lichtblau, John H. "What factors influence oil prices?" Oil & Gas Journal (1981): 198.
- Liesen, Rainer. Der Vertrag Über Die Energiecharta Vom 17. Dezember 1994 - Ursprung, Voraussetzungen, Inhalt, Bedeutung. xl, 302 p vols. Bochum: Ruhr-Universität Bochum, 2004.
- Lipschutz, Ronnie D. On Security. Ed. Ronnie D. Lipschutz. New York: Columbia University Press, 1998.
- Littlechild, S. C. "Misleading Calculations of the Social costs of Monopoly power." The Economic Journal 91.362 (1981): 348-63.
- Littlechild, S. C. The Fallacy Of the Mixed Economy. 2 ed. Lancing, Sussex: The Institute of Economic Affairs, 1986.
- Lohmann, Heiko. The German Path to Natural Gas Liberalisation: Is It a Special Case? Book, Whole vols. Oxford: Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2006.
- Lowry, Edward D. "Justification for Regulation: The Case for Natural Monopoly." Ed. Samuel H. Baker and Catherine S. eds Elliott. Book, Section vols. Lexington, Mass. and Toronto: Heath, 1990. 356-64.
- Lubell, H. "Security of Supply and Energy-Policy in Western-Europe." World Politics 13.3 (1961): 400-22.
- Lucas, N. J. D. Energy and the European Community. London, UK: Europa Publications Limited, 1977.

- Lugar, Richard R. Opening Statement of Richard G. Lugar Ranking Member Committee on Senate Foreign Affairs. 15-3-2008. Committee on Senate Foreign Relations.
Ref Type: Hearing
- Mabro, Robert and Ian Wybrew-Bond. Gas to Europe - the Strategies of Four Major Suppliers. vii, 278 p vols. Oxford: Published by the Oxford University Press for the Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 1999.
- Macavo, P. W. and R. S. Pindyck. The Economics of the Natural Gas Shortage (1960 - 1980). New York: American Elsevier Publishing Company, Inc., 1975.
- MacAvoy, Paul W. The Natural Gas Market. New Haven, Connecticut: Yale University Press, 2000.
- Maddox, John. Beyond the Energy Crisis. London : Hutchinson & Co. (Publishers) Ltd, 1975.
- Mallaby, Sebastain. "What 'Energy Security' Really Means." The Washington Post 3 July 2006, Final Edition ed.
- Mancuso, Paolo and Pierfrancesco Reverberi. "Operating Costs and Market Organization in Railway Services: The Case of Italy, 1980-1995." Transportation Research: Part B: Methodological 37.1 (2003): 43-61.
- Mane-Estrada, A. "European energy security: Towards the creation of the geo-energy space." Energy Policy 34.18 (2006): 3773-86.
- Martin, William Flynn et al. Maintaining Energy Security in a Global Context - a Report to the Trilateral Commission. xiv, 117 p vols. New York: The Trilateral Commission, 1996.
- Matlary, Janne Haaland. Energy Policy in the European Union. New York, New York: St. Martin's Press, 1997.
- Mazighi, Ahmed El Hachemi. "Some Risks Related to the Short-Term Trading of Natural Gas." OPEC Review 28.3 (2004): 227-39.
- McDonald, Robert. "Energy in the single market: vested interests resist liberalisation." European Trends.4 (1993): 69-79.
- McKenzie, Richard B. "Monopoly: A Game Economists Love to Play: Badly!" Southern Economic Journal 70.4 (2004): 714-30.
- McKenzie, Richard B. and Dwight R. Lee. In Defense of Monopoly. Ann Arbor, Michigan: The University of Michigan Press, 2008.
- McKie, James W. "Regulation and the Free Market." The Bell Journal of Economics and Management Science 1.1 (1970): 6-26.
- Mendershausen, Horst, United States, and Office of the Assistant Secretary of Defense (International Security Affairs). Europe's Changing Energy Relations. R-2086-ISA ed. xx, 104 p vols. Santa Monica: Rand, 1976.

- Milov, V., L. L. Coburn, and I. Danchenko. "Russia's energy policy, 1992-2005." Eurasian Geography and Economics 47.3 (2006): 285-313.
- Moen, Ketil Boe. "The Gas Directive: Third party transportation rights - But to what pipeline volumes?" Journal of Energy and Natural Resources Law 21.1 (2003).
- Morse, E. L. and J. Richard. "The battle for energy dominance." Foreign Affairs 81.2 (2002): 16-31.
- Moussa, H. and J. E. Davies. "Natural Monopoly and the Invisible Hand." Economic Studies Quarterly 39.2 (1988): 118-31.
- Müller-Jentsch, Daniel and World Bank/European Commission Programme on Private Participation in Mediterranean Infrastructure. The Development of Electricity Markets in the Euro-Mediterranean Area - Trends and Prospects for Liberalization and Regional Integration. x, 70 p vols. Washington, D.C: World Bank, 2001.
- Muller, F. "Energy security - Risks of international energy supply." Internationale Politik 58.3 (2003): 3-10.
- Nauges, Celine and Caroline van den Berg. "How " Natural " Are Natural Monopolies in the Water Supply and Sewerage Sector ? Case Studies From Developing and Transition Economies." Diss. The World Bank, Policy Research Working Paper Series, 2007.
- Nelson, Richard R. The Limits of Market Organization. New York, New York: Russel Sage Foundation, 2005.
- New Horizons in Natural Gas Deregulation. Ed. Jerry Ellig and Joseph P. Kalt. Westport, CT: Praeger Publishers, 1996.
- Noland, Robert B., William A. Cowart, and Lewis M. Fulton. "Travel demand policies for saving oil during a supply emergency." Energy Policy 2006.34 (2006): 2994-3005.
- O'Driscoll, Gerald P. and Mario J. Rizzo. The Economics of Time and Ignorance. New York, New York: Routledge, 1985.
- OECD/IEA. Natural Gas Information 2003. Paris, France: OECD, 2003.
- OECD/IEA. Oil Supply Security - The Emergency Response Potential of IEA Countries in 2000. Paris: OECD/IEA, 2001.
- OECD/IEA. Regulatory Reform: European Gas. Paris, France: OECD/IEA, 2000.
- OECD/IEA. World Energy Outlook 2002. Paris, France: OECD/IEA, 2002.
- Oil Shock. Ed. Alvin L. Alm and Robert J. Weiner. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Ballinger Publishing Company, 1984.
- Onshore pipeline spend to be \$180 billion by 2012. Oil & Gas Journal (2007): 25.

- Pagliari, Mario. "Strategic interaction on the UK Gas Transportation System; the St. Fergus and Bacton constraints." Energy Economics 25.4 (2003): 345-58.
- Pagnamenta, Robin. "Shell puts 'hundreds of billions' price tag on Siberian Arctic gas." The Times 22 Nov. 2007.
- Palacio, Loyola de. EU Energy Supply Security and Geopolitics (Speech).
<http://europa.eu/rapid/pressReleasesAction.do?reference=SPEECH/04/432&format=PDF&aged=1&language=EN&guiLanguage=en> . 29-9-2004. 23-9-2007.
 Ref Type: Electronic Citation
- Papandreou, Andreas G. "Market Structure and Monopoly Power." The American Economic Review 39.5 (1949): 883-97.
- Parisi, Anthony and Stephen B. Shepard. "The case against energy taxes and rationing." Business Week (1975): 66.
- Parker, D. "Economic Regulation: A Review of Issues." Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics 73.4 (2002): 493-519.
- Parzych, Kenneth M. Public Policy and the Regulatory Environment. Book, Whole vols. and London: University Press of America, 1993.
- Patel, Bipin. Gas Monetisation: a Techno-Economic Comparison of Gas-to-Liquid and LNG. Reading, UK: Foster Wheeler Energy Limited, 2005.
- Percebois, Jacques. "Limits of deregulation in the natural gas industry: the European case." Fuel and Energy Abstracts 36.4 (1995): 256.
- Percebois, Jacques. "The gas deregulation process in Europe: economic and political approach." Energy Policy 27.1 (1999): 9-15.
- Piebalgs, Andris. European energy security policy - Speech at the European Business Summit. 21-2-2008.
 Ref Type: Generic
- Pindyck, Robert. S. "The measurement of monopoly power in dynamic markets." Journal of Law & Economics 28.1 (1985): 193-222.
- Pint, Ellen M. "Government Control of Natural Monopoly: Regulation or Nationalization?" (1989).
- Plott, Charles R. Collected Papers on the Experimental Foundations of Economics and Political Science. Volume 2. Market Institutions and Price Discovery. Book, Whole vols. and Northampton, Mass.: Elgar; distributed by American International Distribution Corporation, Williston, Vt., 2001.
- Plott, Charles R., Alexandre Borges Sugiyama, and Gilad Elbaz. "Economies of Scale, Natural Monopoly, and Imperfect Competition in an Experimental Market." Ed. Charles R. Plott. Book, Section vols. Economists of the Twentieth Century series. Cheltenham, U.K. and

- Northampton, Mass.: Elgar; distributed by American International Distribution Corporation, Williston, Vt., 2001. 282-308.
- Posner, Richard A. "Natural Monopoly and its regulation." Stanford Law Review 21.3 (1969): 548-643.
- Posner, Richard A. "The Social Cost of Regulation and Monopoly." Journal of Political Economy 83.4 (2001): 807-28.
- Powel, William. "EU's 25 member states set to fully open gas markets at mid-year; piecemeal implementation of policy could lead to delays." Platts Oilgram News 8 Jan. 2007.
- Practice Note: Quantitative Tests for Market Power.
<http://www.ictregulationtoolkit.org/en/practicenote.aspx?id=2880> . 2008. ICT Regulation Toolkit. 20-3-2008.
 Ref Type: Electronic Citation
- Primeaux, Walter. J. Direct Electric Utility Competition - the Natural Monopoly Myth. New York, New York: Praeger Publishers, 1986.
- Quester, George H. "Energy Dependence and Political Power: some paradoxes." Demokratizatsiya: The Journal of Post-Soviet Democratization 15 (2007): 459-64.
- Quiggin, John. "The Premature Burial of Natural Monopoly: Telecommunications Reform in Australia." Agenda 5.4 (1998): 427-40.
- Radetzki, Marian. "European natural gas: market forces will bring about competition in any case Radetzki, Marian pp. 17-24." Energy Policy 27.1 (1999): 17-24.
- Reference List
- Reisch, Lucia A. and Hans W. Micklitz. "Consumers and Deregulation of the Electricity Market in Germany." Journal of Consumer Policy 29.4 (2006): 399-415.
- Rempel, H. "Natural gas for Europe - Present state and predictions for a stable supply in the future." Energy Exploration & Exploitation 20.2-3 (2002): 219-37.
- Ribeiro, Clarisse. Investment Arbitration and the Energy Charter Treaty. 1 v. (various pagings) vols. Huntington, NY: JurisNet, LLC, 2006.
- Ringel, M. "Liberalising European electricity markets: opportunities and risks for a sustainable power sector." Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews 7.6 (2003): 485-99.
- Ripsman, Norrin M. "Globalization and the National Security State: A Framework for Analysis." International Studies Review 7 (2005): 199-227.
- Roberts, Cynthia A. Russia and the European Union - the Sources and Limits of "Special Relationships". ix, 133 p vols. Carlisle Barracks, PA: Strategic Studies Institute, U.S. Army War College, 2007.

- Rohatyn, Felix G. "The case for an international oil bank." Business Week 10 Feb. 1975.
- Roller, Lars Hendrik and Christian Wey. "Merger Control in the New Economy." Netnomics 5.1 (2003): 5-20.
- Rossi, Jim. "Universal Service in Competitive Retail Electric Markets: Refin(Anc)Ing the Duty to Serve for a Post-Natural Monopoly Era." Ed. Peter Z. Grossman and Daniel H. Cole. Book, Section vols. Economics of Legal Relationships, vol. 7. Amsterdam; London and New York: Elsevier Science, JAI, 2003. 141-67.
- Rothbard, Murray. "Towards a Reconstruction of Utility and Welfare Economics." 2 (1956).
- Rothbard, Murray. Man, Economy, and State, Volume 1. Princeton, New Jersey: D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc, 1962.
- Rothbard, Murray. Man, Economy, and State, Volume 1. Princeton, New Jersey: 1962.
- Rothbard, Murray. Power & Market. Menlo Park, California: Institute for Humane Studies, 1970.
- Runci, P. J. Energy R&D in the European Union. PNNL-12218. 1999. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory.
- Sanders, M. Elizabeth. The Regulation of Natural Gas - Policy and Politics, 1938-1978. Philadelphia: Temple University Press, 1981.
- Schiller, Timothy. "Rewiring the System: The Changing Structure of the Electric Power Industry." Federal Reserve Bank of Philadelphia Business Review (2001): 26-33.
- Schlesinger, James R. Statement of The Honorable James R. Schlesinger - Senior Advisor, Lehman Brothers. 16-5-2005. Committee on Senate Foreign Relations.
Ref Type: Hearing
- Schmitt, Dieter. "Wie viel und welche (De-)Regulierung braucht die Energiewirtschaftsbranche? (With English summary)." Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftspolitik 54.1 (2005): 92-100.
- Schmlanese, Richard. "Economics of Scale and Barriers to Entry." The Journal of Political Economy 89.6 (1981): 1228-38.
- Schmlanese, Richard. "Sunk Costs and Antitrust Barriers to Entry." AEA Papers and Proceedings 2004.May (2004): 471-75.
- Schumpeter, Joseph A. Capitalism, Socialism, and Democracy. New York, New York: Harper & Row Publishers, 1950.
- Schumpeter, Joseph A. Economic Doctrine and Method. New York: Oxford University Press, 1954.
- Schurmann, K. J. "Overall energy price increase." Atw-Internationale Zeitschrift für Kernenergie 43.6 (1998): 426.

- Schwartzmann, David. "The burden of monopoly." The Journal of Political Economy 68.6 (1960): 627-30.
- Schwarz, Jiri. "Deregulation vs. Re-regulation." Journal des Economistes et des Etudes Humaines 11.4 (2001): 669-84.
- Segal, Paul. Why Do Oil Prices No Longer Shock? Oxford: Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2007.
- Shabad, Theodore. "Energy in the Soviet Union." Energy Policy 4.2 (1976): 177-79.
- Shenfield, A. Myth and Reality of Anti-Trust. London, UK: The Institute of Economic Affairs, 1983.
- Sherman, Robert. The Regulation of Monopoly. New York, New York: Cambridge University Press, 1989.
- Shogren, Jason F. The Political Economy of Government Regulation. Book, Whole vols. Topics in Regulatory Economics and Policy Series Norwell, Mass.; Dordrecht and London: Kluwer Academic, 1989.
- Siddayao, Corazon Morales. "Power Transmission Pricing in a Reformed Sector: Can US Solutions Be Transferred to Developing Countries?" Pacific and Asian Journal of Energy 7.2 (1997): 133-55.
- Simons, Paul. Using Energy as a Weapon. 16-5-2006. Committee on House Government Reform, Subcommittee on Energy Policy, Natural Resources and Regulatory Affairs.
Ref Type: Hearing
- Skeath, Susan E. et al. "Consistent Comparisons Between Monopoly and Perfect Competition." The Journal of Economic Education 23.3 (1992): 255-61.
- Slay, Ben and Vladimir Capelik. "The Struggle for Natural Monopoly Reform in Russia." Post-Soviet Geography and Economics 38.7 (1997): 396-429.
- Smith, Christopher E. "2007 construction lags 2006, but more projects lie ahead." Oil & Gas Journal 19 Feb. 2007.
- Smith, Christopher E. and Koottungal, Leena. "Global pipeline plans expand." Oil & Gas Journal 18 Feb. 2008.
- Stead, D. "Transport Intensity in Europe - indicators and trends." Transport Policy 8.1 (2001): 29-46.
- Stegg, H. "Energy security in global competition." Internationale Politik 51.8 (1996): 49-54.
- Stelzer, Irwin. Lectures on Regulatory and Competition Policy. London, UK: The Institute of Economic Affairs, 2001.

- Stelzer, Irwin. Productivity, Regulation, and Competition: Policies for Natural and Unnatural Monopolies. Book, Whole vols. Inc.: Hudson Institute, 2006.
- Stern, Jonathan P. and Oxford Institute for Energy Studies. The Future of Russian Gas and Gazprom. xvii, 270 p vols. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.
- Stern, Jonathan P. Competition and Liberalization in European Gas Markets - A Diversity of Models. London, UK: The Royal Institute of International Affairs, 1998.
- Stern, Jonathan P. European Gas Markets - Challenges and Opportunities in the 1990s. Aldershot, Hants: The Royal Institute of International Affairs, 1990.
- Stern, Jonathan P. International Gas Trade in Europe - the Policies of Exporting and Importing Countries. London: Heinemann Educational Books Ltd., 1984.
- Stern, Jonathan P. International Gas Trade in Europe. Guildford, Surrey: Biddles Ltd., 1984.
- Stern, Jonathan P. The New Security Environment for European Gas: Worsening Geopolitics and Increasing Global Competition for LNG. Oxford: Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2006.
- Stern, Jonathan P. The Russian Natural Gas "Bubble". Washington: Royal Institute of International Affairs, 1995.
- Stigler, George J. "The theory of economic regulation." The Bell Journal of Economics and Management Science 2.1 (1971): 3-21.
- Sullivan, John A. "LNG plays key role in nation's future energy security." Natural Gas Week (2007).
- Sung, Nakil and Michael Gort. "Economies of Scale and Natural Monopoly in the U.S. Local Telephone Industry." Review of Economics and Statistics 82.4 (2000): 694-97.
- Taliaferro, Jeffrey w. "Security Seeking under Anarchy: Defensive Realism revisited." International Security 25.3 (2000): 128-61.
- Teplitz-Sembitzky, W. and Internat.Bank for Reconstruction and Development.Industry and Energy Dept. Regulation, Deregulation, or Reregulation--What Is Needed in the LDCs Power Sector? Book, Whole vols. Internat Bank Reconstruction and Development, 1990.
- The Geopolitics of Resource Wars. Ed. Phillipe Le Billon. New York: Frank Cass, 2005.
- The Netherlands: special report. Petroleum Economist 62 (1995): 19-21.
- The peasants are revolting. Energy Economist (1994): 2-6.
- Thierer, Adam and Clyde Wayne Crews, Jr. What's Yours Is Mine: Open Access and the Rise of Infrastructure Socialism. Book, Whole vols. Washington, D.C.: Cato Institute, 2003.

- Thomas, Steve. "Electric utility regulation in the European Union: A country by country guide : Eugene D Cross Wiley, London (1996), 357 pp." Energy Policy 24.9 (1996): 855.
- Tomain, Joseph P. "Whither Natural Monopoly? The Case of Electricity." Ed. Peter Z. Grossman and Daniel H. Cole. Book, Section vols. Economics of Legal Relationships, vol. 7. Amsterdam; London and New York: Elsevier Science, JAI, 2003. 111-39.
- Train, Kenneth E. Optimal Regulation: The Economic Theory of Natural Monopoly. Book, Whole vols. and London: MIT Press, 1991.
- True, Warren R. "WGC: reversing natural gas misperceptions a must." Oil & Gas Journal (2006): 26.
- Tsakiris, Theodore. "Energy Security Policy as Economic Statecraft: A concise overvie of the last 100 years." Agora without Frontiers 9.4 (2004): 307-29.
- Tschirhart, John. "Monopsony Power and the Existence of Natural Monopoly in Energy Utilities." Resource and Energy Economics 17.4 (1995): 327-40.
- Tschirhart, John. "Partial Regulation of Natural Monopoly." Ed. Jason F. Shogren. Book, Section vols. Topics in Regulatory Economics and Policy Series Norwell, Mass.; Dordrecht and London: Kluwer Academic, 1989. 55-81.
- Tullock, Gordon. "The Welfare Costs of Tariffs, Monopolies, and Theft." Western Economic Journal (now Economic Inquiry) 5.11 (1974): 224-32.
- Ulbrich, Holley H. "Natural Monopoly in Principles Textbooks: A pedagogical note." Journal of economic Education 1991 (1991): 179-82.
- Umbach, Frank. Globale Energiesicherheit . Munich, Germany: Oldenbourg Wissenschaftsverlag, GmbH, 2003.
- van Oostvoorn, F. "Impacts of Market Liberalisation on the EU Gas Industry." Paper for the 1st Austrian-Czech-German Conference on Energy Market Liberalization in Central and Eastern Europe 1999.October (1999).
- Verrastro, Frank and Sarah Ladislaw. "Providing Energy Security in an Interdependent World." Washington Quarterly 30.4 (2007): 95-104.
- Victor, David G., A. M. Jaffe, and Mark H Hayes. Natural Gas and Geopolitics: From 1970 to 2040. 1 ed. Cambridge, New York: Cambridge University Press, 2006.
- Viscusi, W. Kip, John M. Vernon, and Joseph E. Jr Harrington. Economics of Regulation and Antitrust. Book, Whole vols. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2000.
- Viscusi, W. Kip, John M. Vernon, and Joseph E. Jr Harrington. Economics of Regulation and Antitrust. Book, Whole vols. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 1995.
- Viscusi, W. Kip, Joseph E. Jr Harrington, and John M. Vernon. Economics of Regulation and Antitrust. Book, Whole vols. Cambridge and London: MIT Press, 2005.

- von Hirschhausen, Christian. "Reform der Erdgaswirtschaft in der EU und in Deutschland: Wie viel Regulierung braucht der Wettbewerb?" Perspektiven der Wirtschaftspolitik 7.1 (2006): 89-103.
- Waelde, Thomas W. The Energy Charter Treaty an East-West Gateway for Investment and Trade. xxvii, 700 p vols. London: Kluwer Law International, 1996.
- Wallace, Donald H. "Monopolistic Competition and Public Policy." The American Economic Review 26.1 (1936): 77-87.
- Wallace, Helen and William Wallace. Policy-Making in the European Union. 3rd ed ed. xxvii, 509 p vols. Oxford England: Oxford University Press, 1996.
- Waterson, Michael. Regulation of the Firm and Natural Monopoly. Book, Whole vols. Oxford and New York: Blackwell, 1988.
- Weichenrieder, Alfons J. "Second Degree Price Discrimination and Natural Monopoly." Bulletin of Economic Research 56.2 (2004): 189-200.
- Weichenrieder, Alfons. "How Efficient Is a Contestable Natural Monopoly?" Diss. CESifo GmbH, CESifo Working Paper Series, 1999.
- Weisser, H. "The security of gas supply - a critical issue for Europe? - Viewpoint." Energy Policy 35.1 (2007): 1-5.
- Wells, Mike. "Energy charter charts changes." (1991).
- Wenders, John T. "Entry and Monopoly Pricing." The Journal of Political Economy 75.5 (1967): 755-60.
- Wickstrom, Bengt Arne. "Regulation of Natural Monopoly: A Public-Choice Perspective." Ed. Atle Midttun and Eirik Svindland. Book, Section vols. Houndmills, U.K. and New York: Palgrave, 2001. 55-73.
- Wieczorek, A. J., O. Kuik, and F. Berkhout. "Flows of carbon between East and West: between economic efficiency, energy security, and carbon dependence." Osteuropa 54.9-10 (2004): 292-300.
- Willner, Johan. "A Comment on Bradburd: "Privatisation of Natural Monopolies."." Review of Industrial Organization 11.6 (1996): 869-82.
- Wilson, Wesley W. and Yimin Zhou. "Telecommunications Deregulation and Subadditive Costs: Are Local Telephone Monopolies Unnatural?" International Journal of Industrial Organization 19.6 (2001): 909-30.
- Wood, David. "Could a future gas OPEC shape LNG import plans?" Oil & Gas Journal (2007): 22.
- Wood, David. "Supply diversity cuts risk exposure." Oil & Gas Journal (2007): 65.

- Wood, Geoffrey E. Fifty Economic Fallacies Exposed. London: The Institute for Economic Affairs, 2002.
- Wright, Philip. Gas Prices in the UK. Oxford, UK: Oxford Institute for Energy Studies, 2006.
- Yergin, Daniel and Michael Stopgard. "The Next Prize." Foreign Affairs 82.6 (2003): 103-14.
- Yergin, Daniel. "Ensuring Energy Security." Foreign Affairs 85.2 (2006).
- Yergin, Daniel. Using energy as a weapon. 16-5-2006. Committee on House Government Reform, Subcommittee on Energy Policy, Natural Resources and Regulatory Affairs.
Ref Type: Hearing
- Zweifel, P. and S. Bonomo. "Energy Security - Coping with Multiple Supply Risks." Energy Economics 17.3 (1995): 179-83.
- "Chapter 3: Liberalisation of European Energy Markets: Challenges and Policy Options." Ed. European Commission. Brussels: European Commission, 2007. 31-58.
- "ENERGY: Back unbundling, Kroes tells users." Utility Week 6 July 2007.
- "EU competition commissioner to press ahead with utilities unbundling." Datamonitor NewsWire 21 Mar. 2007.
- "EU energy ministers dodge the big issue of full unbundling of distribution, supply." Global Power Report 22 Feb. 2007.
- "EU energy shake-up: industry balks at proposed emissions cuts; commission threatens to break up leading companies." Chemical Week 17 Jan. 2007.
- "Gas Pipelines will still be king in Europe, says S&P report." Lloyd's List 3 July 2006.
- "Infrastructure, Natural Monopoly, and Equitable Access." Ed. Richard R. Nelson. Book, Section vols. New York: Russell Sage Foundation, 2005. 25-26.
- "Kissinger's Wedge." The Economist 15 Feb. 1975.
- "Oil demand falls on high prices." Euro News 13 Nov. 2007, English version ed.
- "The future for gas in Europe; gas industry; gas in europe: a special report; industry overview." Gas World International 1995, 4912 ed.
- "The worldwide search for oil." Business Week 3 Feb. 1975, Industrial Edition ed.
- "United We Stand?" The Economist 2 Aug. 1975.